

Chapter 4

POLICY AND SOCIOPOLITICAL OPTIONS ACROSS THE NEXUS THAT COULD FACILITATE AND ACCELERATE THE TRANSITION TO A RANGE OF SUSTAINABLE FUTURES¹

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Note

The Nexus Assessment chapters share a common thread of case studies highlighting Indigenous Peoples' and local communities' (IPLC) food systems. **Chapters 1 to 4, 5.1 to 5.5 and 6** include one or more of these case studies. The case studies are presented in boxes and are distinguished by *box titles in italicized font*. Lessons learned from the common case studies are presented in **Chapter 7**, online **Supplementary material 7.1**.

Disclaimer on maps

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Chapter 4

POLICY AND SOCIOPOLITICAL OPTIONS ACROSS THE NEXUS THAT COULD FACILITATE AND ACCELERATE THE TRANSITION TO A RANGE OF SUSTAINABLE FUTURES

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Chapter 4 explores how policy and sociopolitical options, the scaling of these options and decision-support tools can improve fragmented policymaking across interconnected biodiversity, water, food, health and climate systems, and how these options are enabled or constrained by certain factors, actors, scales and contexts to support and accelerate transitions towards just and sustainable futures (*well established*) {4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5, 4.6}. Given the siloed and fragmented nature of many decision-making processes, it is important to understand how existing frameworks and options can better consider trade-offs and synergies across the nexus elements. Opportunities for transitions and transformations can identify who needs to act, at what scale and with what mechanisms to amplify synergies and reduce entrenched social-ecological inequities (*well established*) {4.2.2, 4.2.3, 4.2.4}. There are a range of decision-support tools that address nexus interactions, trade-offs and synergies that can support existing policies and sociopolitical options for the scaling of nexus transformations towards just and sustainable futures (*well established*) {4.6.2, 4.6.3, 4.6.4} (Table 4.13).

Existing governance and policy literature explicitly linked to the nexus focuses mostly on connections between water and food with much less evidence on interlinkages involving the other nexus elements of biodiversity, health and climate change (*well established*) {4.3} (Figure 4.3). The governance of water and food interactions, often coupled with energy, are the most studied nexus elements, often associated with the nexus challenges of complexity and governance, followed by values (*established but incomplete*) {4.3.2} (Figure 4.3). However, most governance and policy literature fail to account for all five elements, indicating a major gap (*established but incomplete*) {4.3, 4.7}. Energy, poverty, equity and economic growth are among the most salient cross-cutting issues that nexus-related policy and

sociopolitical options target (*established but incomplete*) {4.3.6} (Figure 4.12). Much of the literature on governance and policy instruments on elements of the nexus specific to Indigenous Peoples and local communities, especially those based on Indigenous and local knowledge, focus on the connections between biodiversity and food, alongside water, highlighting their holistic and integrated conceptualization of the nexus (*well established*) {4.5.2, 4.6.3.1} (Figure 4.15). A review of actors in governance of nexus elements revealed high diversity: the most common were civil society and community-based organizations, followed by local/national governments and municipalities, the private sector and business organizations, and global/regional institutions and science-policy interfaces. Indigenous Peoples and local communities and media and the arts were the least discussed actors, indicating potential for improved engagement (*established but incomplete*) {4.3.4}.

Nexus governance emerges as a specific form of governance to ensure that policy and sociopolitical options are approached through a holistic lens by integrating knowledge and value systems of diverse actors and institutions across sectors and scales and foregrounding equity and justice to deliver sustainable and just nexus-wide benefits (*well established*) {4.2.2, 4.5.1, 4.5.2, 4.5.3, 4.5.4}.

Nexus governance, if successfully implemented, helps to proactively plan for and maximize synergies by navigating and negotiating trade-offs and capturing synergies (*well established*) {4.5.4}. Policy and sociopolitical options that are co-developed through transdisciplinary engagement can result in outcomes that are integrative, inclusive, adaptive, accountable and can increase transformative potential to overcome nexus challenges relating to complexity, values, scaling and financing (*established but incomplete*) {4.2.4, 4.3.3, 4.5.5}. Governance approaches that more clearly address nexus challenges have characteristics that enhance policy coordination and integration (e.g., through network and hierarchical governance mechanisms) as opposed to governance approaches that do not (e.g., market

governance (*established but incomplete*) {4.3.3}. However, there is limited focus on options or solutions that can address the nexus challenges of values, scaling and finance (*established but incomplete*) {4.3.3}. Greater efforts are needed on documenting evidence of success for integrating the nexus in policies and action, including how to amplify or scale these successes, in addition to a comprehensive analysis of challenges related to financing nexus solutions (*established but incomplete*) {4.7}.

Nexus governance is enhanced by explicit consideration of several enabling features, defined as five components for nexus governance (*well established*) {4.5.4} (Figure 4.17). These components include: (1) integrative, holistic and transdisciplinary framing of problems and solutions; (2) inclusive approaches that bring about enhanced arenas of actor engagement; (3) normative considerations of equity and justice, alongside accountability; (4) enhanced mechanisms and processes for collaboration and coordination across scales and sectors; and (5) adaptive, reflexive and experimental approaches to learn from what works and to scale these solutions (*well established*) {4.5.4} (Figure 4.17). These components can be facilitated by strengthening specific capacities linked to analytical, bridging, negotiation, social network and motivational capacities (*well established*) {4.5.5}.

Important enablers and barriers to nexus governance include policy design and implementation, equity and diversity, institutional capacity, finance and economics, behaviour, lifestyle and values, technology and material/non-material endowments (*well established*) {4.2.5, 4.3.5}. Policy design and implementation and institutional capacity were the most common enablers and barriers of response options to address nexus challenges (*well established*) {4.3.5} (Figure 4.10). Finance and economics tended to be the most important enablers and barriers for addressing nexus challenges linked to values and governance. Barriers are often not a result of a lack of scientific knowledge or data, but a lack of consideration of interlinkages among nexus elements across sectors and this often arises from structural challenges, which can be social, political or economic (*established but incomplete*) {4.7.1}.

Supporting integrative solutions and nexus governance requires a whole of society approach. All actors have a part to play in leveraging change, but some actors and institutions are more influential than others (*well established*) {4.2.6, 4.5.1}. Governing nexus interactions is most effective when including the engagement of multiple actors and institutions through horizontal and vertical channels aimed at policy coherence and minimization of trade-offs, as well as through recognizing and supporting the actions of societal actors through recently emerging arenas of engagement {4.5.1}

(Table 4.7); this includes combinations of formal and informal and public and private institutions (including their associated norms, rules and rulemaking systems) across actor networks at multiple levels for integrated decision-making (*well established*) {4.2.6}. While the range of actors involved in decisions linked to governing the nexus is broad, the involvement of Indigenous Peoples and local communities and their knowledge systems are underrepresented in the nexus literature (*established but incomplete*) {4.3.4, 4.5.2}.

By promoting meaningful and inclusive participation, ensuring representation of diverse actors, including those marginalized in policy formulation, planning and implementation, can have more transformative outcomes for people and nature (*well established*) {4.5.1, 4.5.2, 4.5.3}. Enhancing nexus governance through a focus on equity and justice considerations can be facilitated through a deeper consideration of the different dimensions of justice, including recognitional, procedural and distributive dimensions (*well established*) {4.5.3} (Figure 4.16, Table 4.8). Consideration of rights-based approaches, including a human-rights based approach and an intersectionality lens which foregrounds the role of power, can facilitate a more equitable acknowledgement of the diverse values, needs, interest and rights of actors, many of whom remain marginalized (*well established*) {4.5.3} (Box 4.11, Box 4.12). This includes considerations of how to transform inequitable power dynamics, acknowledge diverse knowledge systems, facilitate more context-specific data collection and analysis, ensure more participatory decision-making, and cultivate solidarity (*established but incomplete*) {4.5.3}. Dialogues, including the IPBES-facilitated Indigenous and local knowledge dialogues, provide strong evidence on how Indigenous Peoples and local communities conceptualize and govern the interconnections between biodiversity (which many Indigenous Peoples and local communities depend on for their livelihoods), food and water systems, well-being and spirituality, and climate change based on holistic approaches and world views (*established but incomplete*) {4.2, 4.5.2} (Figure 4.15).

Greater attention to the multiple dimensions of scaling within the context of nexus interactions can help enhance the impacts of successful or promising policy and sociopolitical options that operate at a given scale (*established but incomplete*) {4.4.1}. The scaling of response options entails accelerating their adoption and implementation, amplifying their impacts, and normalizing them as mainstream solutions. Scaling involves institutionalizing nexus response options at the level of policy, rules and laws (scaling up); replicating and/or transferring response options to new contexts (scaling out); and provincializing/localizing innovative nexus response options on the ground that are well adapted to local

contexts (scaling down), while gradually and ultimately changing relationships, world views, mindsets or beliefs, and cultural values that shape institutions and contexts as well as response options (scaling deep) (*established but incomplete*) {4.4.1, 4.4.2} (**Figure 4.14**). Realizing transitions to sustainable and just futures relies on the scaling of nexus response options which involves the disruption of existing unsustainable regimes and the creation of new ways of thinking, interacting and organising (*well established*) {4.4.1}. Policy and sociopolitical options that are integrative across nexus elements may be fostered into a scaling process that will in turn support, amplify, normalize and provincialize nexus governance (*established but incomplete*) {4.3.2, 4.3.3}.

Tools supporting nexus governance are rapidly emerging to help address nexus challenges and strengthen capacities for nexus considerations in decision-making (*well established*) {4.6.1, Table 4.13}.

These tools can facilitate governance by (1) setting nexus-relevant objectives and targets {4.6.2}, (2) facilitating response option choices {4.6.3}, and (3) highlighting opportunities for scaling {4.6.4}. Current tools to address nexus challenges have strong links to water, food, climate change and biodiversity but health linkages are commonly absent (*well established*) {4.6.1} (**Table 4.13**). While most tools that address nexus challenges are holistic (i.e., support a diversity of Sustainable Development Goals), many of them require substantial technical capacity to implement. The most common tools focus on assembling data and knowledge (including monitoring) and assessment and evaluation, which are less inclusive and have less transformative potential than other types of tools (*well established*) {4.6.1} (**Table 4.13**). Governments are the most frequent actors using tools to both understand and address nexus challenges; however, most tools involve multiple partners with intergovernmental organizations, non-governmental organizations, the private sector, and researchers playing key roles, while Indigenous Peoples and local communities are under-represented (*established but incomplete*) {4.6.1} (**Table 4.13**). Tools that support knowledge co-production processes to strengthen bridging capacities (bringing together different ways of knowing and doing), negotiation capacity (helping to navigate trade-offs, uptake and impact) and social network capacities (learning to adapt and act together) can support better inclusion of Indigenous Peoples and local communities and Indigenous and local knowledge concerns in decision-making (*well established*) {4.5.2, 4.6.3} (**Figure 4.15**).

There are critical knowledge gaps regarding Indigenous and local knowledge-specific nexus governance and the inclusion of Indigenous and local knowledge and Indigenous Peoples' and local communities' concerns in current nexus response options, tools and scaling options in the literature

(*well established*) {4.7.1}. This gap is not a reflection of how Indigenous Peoples and local communities consider the nexus, as many Indigenous Peoples and local communities conceptualize biodiversity, water, food, health and climate change as an integral whole {4.5.2}; rather, it is a gap on how Indigenous and local knowledge is understood and valorised by scientists and decision makers, documented in widely spoken languages and included in published literature and scientific assessments (*established but incomplete*) {4.7.1}. Greater attention is needed to engage with and learn from examples of governance regimes led by Indigenous Peoples and local communities that effectively conserve natural resources while ensuring livelihoods from terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems with more traditional governance approaches (*well established*) {4.3.7, 4.5.2}. This is particularly important as Indigenous Peoples- and local communities-specific and Indigenous- and local knowledge-based governance focuses on different elements of the nexus and uses different policy instruments and decision-support tools than those used in non-Indigenous Peoples and local communities contexts. Considering the ongoing challenges Indigenous Peoples and local communities around the world experience to use such governance systems and transmit Indigenous and local knowledge-based policy instruments and support tools, partnering with Indigenous Peoples and local communities is key to supporting approaches that consider interlinkages among nature, food systems, water systems, well-being, spirituality and climate change (*established but incomplete*) {4.5.2}.

While there have been some advances on integrating nexus considerations into policy and sociopolitical response options, there is limited empirical assessment of nexus response options and most insights are derived from theory or conceptual models (*established but incomplete*) {4.3, 4.4, 4.5}.

There is a lack of engagement between various nexus elements and the health sector which is the result of both limited conceptual engagement as well as a gap in current governance research and literature (*established but incomplete*) {4.7.1}. Additionally, more research is needed on the temporal dynamics of nexus dynamics in relation to both nexus elements and actors involved in the implementation of nexus response options (*established but incomplete*) {4.7.1}. There are also knowledge gaps on the transboundary impacts of nexus interactions, which occur at the borders of geopolitical entities, especially between nation-states (*established but incomplete*) {4.7.1}.

4.1 INTRODUCTION

While current challenges of biodiversity loss and its impact on human well-being are rooted in previous decisions and actions, future options for responding to social-ecological changes are shaped by decisions and actions taken today. The imperative to act swiftly to address interlinked human and ecological crises has been highlighted by numerous science-policy assessments in recent years (see **Chapter 1, section 1.4.2**). While these have provided a suite of options for addressing many environmental and development challenges, none have had an explicit nexus focus. In particular, none have identified the policy and sociopolitical options, and the actors and institutions involved in decision-making processes, that can lead to just and sustainable outcomes by explicitly considering the interlinkages, feedbacks and relationships between biodiversity, water, food, health and climate change. It is therefore important to understand how existing frameworks and options for decision-making can consider nexus issues, such as trade-offs, opportunities for transitions, benefits and burdens, in addition to identifying who needs to act, at what scale and with what mechanisms to amplify synergies and reduce entrenched social-ecological inequities.

In previous chapters of the assessment, the conceptual foundations for the nexus and five nexus challenges have been established (**Chapter 1**), and key trends, drivers (**Chapter 2**) and pathways for more just and sustainable futures (**Chapter 3**) have been assessed. The aim of this chapter is to identify, assess, synthesize and classify existing policy and sociopolitical frameworks and options that address biodiversity, water, food, health and climate change issues. This includes classifying and identifying response options that address the nexus challenges introduced in **Chapter 1, section 1.1.2**. **Chapter 4** also identifies cross-cutting issues and enablers and barriers that impact these options, as well as decision-support tools for facilitating holistic decisions across different sectors, actor groups, institutions and scales. These policy and sociopolitical options, decision-support tools and frameworks have been assessed in terms of their strengths for improved governance of nexus interlinkages. This informs further development of the concept of nexus governance, a term increasingly used in the scientific literature, but which remains incomplete and poorly implemented in practice. Based on reviews of the nexus governance literature and existing theory and implementation gaps, the chapter defines the core components of nexus governance that enable improved holistic decision-making and identifies the related policy and sociopolitical options that have transformative potential. This broad framework serves as a basis for **Chapters 5 and 6** to assess and outline actionable response options across the nexus for catalysing change, which are then summarized in **Chapter 7** into a practical implementation roadmap for just and sustainable futures.

Chapter 4 focuses on addressing the following policy-relevant question from **Chapter 1, section 1.1.3**:

“Which factors (economic and financial, technical, social, political, institutional, cultural and behavioural) facilitate or obstruct pathways to achieve a sustainable future, and which tools and policy options exist to help decision makers navigate the complexity of the nexus and take into account the existence of a diversity of values, including perspectives and knowledge of Indigenous Peoples and local communities (IPLC)?”. Within this broad framing, the chapter addresses specific questions to elaborate on key concepts and concerns, and answers these through reviews of key literature:

- 1) What policy and sociopolitical options have been used to guide decision-making across the nexus, in which contexts and across which scales? (acknowledging the diversity of contexts and scale mismatches)
- 2) How are these policy and sociopolitical options supported, amplified or constrained through specific enabling conditions and tools?
- 3) Which actors and arenas of engagement are involved in the governance of nexus interactions and which are key influencers that can facilitate and accelerate change?
- 4) What are key features that need to be considered for improved nexus governance and how can more transformative potential be realized?

This chapter consists of eight sections, which link to other assessment chapters as indicated in **Figure 4.1**.

- **Section 4.1** describes the background, objectives and overall structure of the chapter. A glossary of key terms for the chapter is provided in **Table 4.1**.
- **Section 4.2** provides key definitions related to policy and sociopolitical options linked to governing nexus interactions, and reviews existing approaches and challenges of governance generally. It also reviews existing approaches to how nexus governance has been defined in the literature as a specific form of governance, and what gaps exist in these approaches.
- **Section 4.3** identifies, assesses and categorizes a range of governance approaches and policy instruments and their suitability for solving the key nexus challenges across scales, based on a systematic review of literature. This section synthesises existing evidence and gaps, with a focus on what governance approaches and policy instruments have been used to address nexus challenges, including assessment of their key enablers and barriers.

Table 4.1 Glossary of key terms of Chapter 4.

Policy and sociopolitical options	A range of theoretical and practical frameworks for implementing sustainable management approaches, including diverse sets of human actions to address specific issues, needs, objectives and opportunities in the governance and management of nexus challenges (see Chapter 1, section 1.1.2 for further detail on the nexus challenges). The policy and sociopolitical options that are the focus of this chapter include those that account for a diversity of world views, behaviours, norms and values and which are aimed at accelerating transitions towards just and sustainable futures.
Nexus governance	Refers to the systematic coordinating structures and processes that enhance the engagement of multiple actors through horizontal (e.g., across various nexus elements at one scale) and vertical (e.g., cross-scale connectivity or multilevel governance) channels to address nexus challenges, identify policy and sociopolitical options, and manage their implementation towards just sustainable futures.
Scaling	Accelerating the adoption and implementation of policy and sociopolitical options/response options, amplifying their impacts and normalizing them as mainstream solutions to nexus challenges. Includes scaling up, scaling out, scaling down and scaling deep.
Enablers and barriers	Specific characteristics or contexts of a nexus challenge that facilitate or impair the implementation, operationalization or effectiveness of nexus response options (including governance approaches).
Policy instruments	The different interventions (formal rules, laws, social norms and processes etc.) made by decision makers (governments and public authorities, intergovernmental organizations, companies etc.) to ensure that (public) policy objectives are supported and achieved by influencing the behaviour of other stakeholders. These can include economic and financial, legal and regulatory, social and cultural, rights-based and customary policy response options to support nexus governance.
Decision-support tools, including policy support	Methods, approaches and techniques that can inform, assist and enhance relevant decision-making, policymaking, governance and implementation at the local, national, regional and international levels, based on science and other knowledge systems including Indigenous and local knowledge.

- **Section 4.4** outlines different scaling processes (scaling up to institutionalize response options, scaling out to increase their uptake in other contexts, scaling down to provincialize them in local unique contexts, and scaling deep to change mindsets and values that underpin the design and adoption of responses) and explores the enabling mechanisms for these scaling processes.
- **Section 4.5** returns to the concept of nexus governance and synthesizes findings from the systematic review together with reviews of identified gaps around actors and arenas of engagement, the role of IPLC and the importance of equity, justice and intersectionality. It combines these findings into a consolidated approach to nexus governance, identifying key components to help address how governance should be framed, who should be involved, what should be included, and where and when should it be enacted to improve implementation and scaling of policy and sociopolitical options.
- **Section 4.6** focuses on reviewing existing decision-support tools for various users at different scales that can facilitate decision-making to support the different components of nexus governance.
- **Section 4.7** identifies key remaining knowledge gaps concerning the policy and sociopolitical options governing the nexus and highlights emerging issues, blind spots and limitations in the current academic literature regarding these options.
- **Section 4.8** summarizes the chapter and presents conclusions.

4.2 GOVERNING THE NEXUS: CONCEPTS, DEFINITIONS AND GAPS

The IPBES Global Assessment Report on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (Global Assessment) (IPBES, 2019) identified fragmentation and complexity within environmental governance, as well as between environmental governance and other governance domains, as a major barrier towards the realization of the SDGs. This provides a justification for governance approaches for the nexus to actively enhance synergies and address trade-offs in realizing multiple policy goals. One of the aims of this chapter is to identify policy and sociopolitical options and tools that are well suited to simultaneously achieving positive outcomes for biodiversity and the other nexus elements of water, food, health and climate change and

for navigating trade-offs while accelerating the transitions towards just and sustainable futures. These options need to account for not only the complexity of interactions and how they are framed and negotiated (Keune *et al.*, 2013), but also the indirect and direct drivers of change and the normative aims for positive outcomes across all nexus elements.

Moreover, many existing policies and sociopolitical options and tools do not necessarily reflect the priorities and values of IPLC, who often do not conceptualize the different elements of the nexus separately but interpret them holistically and broadly as an integrated whole (see **Chapter 1, section 1.2.2**). While the holistic approach taken by this assessment is in line with such world views, it differs in one important point: for many IPLC, biodiversity, food, water, health and climate change do not need to be brought together because they are already conceptualized holistically across nature, food systems, water systems, well-being and spirituality in a single system. The idea of a “nexus” has some parallels in concepts rooted in ILK (**Chapter 1, Table 1.1**) but these are not necessarily explicit or exactly concordant. Accordingly, this chapter pays attention to multiple values and knowledge systems throughout and draws from engagements with IPLC through the three ILK dialogue workshops, works authored by Indigenous scholars and other information transmitted by IPLC. Evidence suggests that this approach, grounded in methods used in past IPBES assessments to ensure IPLC voices, contributions and knowledges are reflected in the assessment, can lead to changes in policies and institutions that support local-level sustainability pathways (Hill *et al.*, 2020; McElwee *et al.*, 2020). ILK is mainstreamed in this chapter’s review of policy and sociopolitical options, decision-support tools and scaling sections, in addition to featuring in a section (**section 4.6.3.1** and **Figure 4.15**) focused specifically on a review of IPLC governance, world views, beliefs and practices grounded in ILK.

4.2.1 Policy and sociopolitical options across the nexus: key terms and concepts

Based on a review of key literature on response and policy options (**section 4.3**; online **Supplementary material 4.3**) and expert review, the chapter defines policy and sociopolitical options as the frameworks that enable actions to be undertaken to achieve solutions and accelerate the transition towards just and sustainable futures (see **Box 4.1**). Understanding of broad policy and sociopolitical options, including governance frameworks, helps in designing improved systems to govern across the nexus, as the structural choice and design of options can hinder coordination of actors, or the use of certain governance frameworks can create path-dependency.

Box 4 1 How policy and sociopolitical options for governing the nexus are understood in this assessment.²

This assessment distinguishes between policy and sociopolitical options (this chapter) and response options (Chapter 5).

Policy and sociopolitical options consist of a range of theoretical and practical frameworks for implementing sustainable management approaches, including diverse sets of human actions to address specific issues, needs, objectives and opportunities in the governance and management of nexus challenges (see Chapter 1, section 1.1.2 for further information on nexus challenges). The policy and sociopolitical options that are the focus of this chapter include those that account for a diversity of world views, behaviours, norms and values and which are aimed at accelerating transitions towards just and sustainable futures.

Response options are one type of policy and sociopolitical options. Response options are defined as actions or policies available to a range of actors that address specific challenges or opportunities in the governance and management of one or more elements of the nexus, with the goal of achieving positive and equitable outcomes across multiple nexus elements (W. B. Chambers *et al.*, 2005; Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005). These response options can include voluntary or mandatory policies, strategies, measures and interventions intended to change nexus elements, interlinkages between them and direct or indirect drivers shaping them. Broad categories of response options include legal, regulatory, economic and financial mechanisms, human rights-based

tools, social, behavioural, cultural and technological approaches and management instruments implemented by diverse actor groups and institutions. These can operate across different time scales (short/long term), spatial scales (national, regional, local etc.), jurisdictions and through the involvement of a diversity of actors, and coalitions of actors such as IPLC, researchers, members of civil society and those representing private and public sector interests. Chapter 5 assesses a range of response options in terms of their impacts on each nexus element, social acceptability, alignment with political priorities, economic implications, technical feasibility, equity, alignment with targets of international frameworks and transformative potential.

Policy and sociopolitical options are broader than response options. They include different theoretical and practical frameworks and governance approaches, enablers, capacities, decision-support tools, social movements and social actions, and other options which are designed, implemented and carried out to deliver on just and sustainable futures, such as those enshrined by the 2050 vision of living in harmony with nature of the Convention on Biological Diversity. This definition of policy and sociopolitical options purposefully takes a holistic approach and includes options from different world views, behaviours, norms and values and different knowledge systems, including science and ILK systems (IPCC, 2022; Leonard *et al.*, 2022; Redvers *et al.*, 2022). The policy and sociopolitical options presented in this assessment are a non-exhaustive list, with implementation dependent on national and local circumstances.

4.2.2 Types of governance approaches

The choice or implementation of any given policy and sociopolitical option is influenced by governance approaches in a specific context (sometimes also referred to as modes of governance). Governance is an umbrella concept for the full range of means for deciding, managing, implementing and monitoring policies and measures, including the ways that combinations of formal and informal and public and private institutions (including actions, norms, rules and rulemaking systems) are structured, sustained and regulated (IPBES, 2019, 2023c). Governance approaches determine the processes and channels through which decisions are made and implemented, and how power and responsibilities are distributed and exercised between actors. Governance approaches therefore reflect varying degrees and patterns of centralization, participation, relational structures and adaptation to change, each with different principles, societal rules or norms, to organize and

coordinate collective actions. They differ in the mechanisms through which change is assumed to occur (e.g., through the state, market or society), the actors involved and how actors interact with the policy instruments applied. Over time the literature on this topic has shifted from a focus on 'government' to 'governance' recognizing the role of multiple actors and institutions in society in governing beyond the state. This framing is used in this chapter.

Table 4.2 summarises four key governance approaches commonly encountered in the literature: hierarchical, market, network and community governance. Each of these reflects different possible relationships between actors and institutions in addition to assumptions about where change comes from in society and how this is brought about, thus leading to different choices about which policy and sociopolitical options, instruments or tools might be most appropriate.

In addition to these four governance approaches that relate to structures and actors, there has been increasing attention to other related governance issues, particularly adaptive governance and integrative governance.

² The data management report describing the literature review for this section of Chapter 4 is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13913225>.

Table 4.2 Definitions of key governance approaches and their focus.

Governance approaches	Definition and focus
Hierarchical Governance	Hierarchical governance involves nested levels of state authority, wherein each unit is subordinate to its vertical superior, and in which tasks are divided into more manageable forms (Bednar & Henstra, 2018; Lukat <i>et al.</i> , 2023).
Market Governance	Market modes of governance prioritize responses to complex issues as best coordinated through the “invisible hand of the market” or to a lesser extent, the use of market-driven behavioural change (Bednar & Henstra, 2018). Market governance may be achieved by states steering markets through regulation and activity via market-based instruments, such as subsidies and taxes and voluntary industry-led approaches (Benson <i>et al.</i> , 2017).
Network Governance	In network governance, the boundaries between the spheres of public, private and community sectors are blurred and permeable, e.g., as networks of actors in the water-energy-food nexus (Covarrubias <i>et al.</i> , 2019). This reflects multiple and dynamic horizontal flows resulting in heterogeneous power relations.
Community Governance	Community level management and decision-making that is undertaken by, with, or on behalf of a community, by a group of community stakeholders (Totikidis <i>et al.</i> , 2005). Tenbenschel (2005) notes that community governance embraces many of the same consensual and participatory ideals of network governance but steering rests at the local level. In some instances, influence might be pressed upwards to acquire resources for locally developed, but otherwise autonomous, policies (Hall, 2012).

Adaptive governance is governance that enables society to adapt to disturbances and changes by navigating the dynamic, multi-scalar nature of social-ecological-institutional systems (Cosens *et al.*, 2014). Adaptive governance requires a deep understanding of the limits and possibilities of adaptation, and the form of adaptive governance depends on the governance path, the history of co-evolution of actors and institutions, power and knowledge (Van Assche *et al.*, 2017).

The concept of **integrated** or **integrative governance** broadly seeks to bring together different sectors, actors, policies and/or levels of governance around a specific social-ecological system or problem (Haapasaari *et al.*, 2021), particularly at multiple scales (both time and geographical) and across multiple issues and sectors (IPBES, 2019; Stout & Love, 2019; Visseren-Hamakers, 2015, 2018). However, there are varying definitions as to what ‘integration’ among sectors can and should entail (Frazer *et al.*, 2022), and different potential approaches vary in terms of their emphasis on entry points, focus and ways of governing. Some examples include:

- **Integrative governance** aims to bring together different sectors and policies and levels of governance around a specific social-ecological system and/or groups of people (Haapasaari *et al.*, 2021); examples include integrated landscape management, supply chain governance and integrated water management (Al-Saidi & Elagib, 2017; Giampietro, 2018; Sayer *et al.*, 2015; Visseren-Hamakers, 2015; Weitz *et al.*, 2017). Integrative governance acknowledges the relationships between governance instruments (policies and rules) and the governance system (the total of the instruments

and the relationships between them) (Visseren-Hamakers, 2015).

- **Intersectoral or multi-sectoral governance** describes distinct entities or procedures within government and administrations that use the structures in place to facilitate collaboration between various ministries, departments and sectors. Some actions, such as evidence support, objective setting and goal setting can be facilitated by intersectoral governance structures aimed at aligning governance policies (McQueen *et al.*, 2012). The concepts of **institutional interplay** and inter-action management also relate to identifying options for enhancing integrative governance, such as through (inter)national institutions (Zelli *et al.*, 2020).
- **Policy coherence** can be defined as “the systematic promotion of mutually reinforcing policy actions across government departments and agencies, creating synergies towards achieving the defined objective,” (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, 2001;p.90). Policy coherence, particularly for sustainable development, refers to focusing on a strategic vision for achieving the SDGs underpinned by clear political commitment and institutional leadership, effective and inclusive institutional and governance mechanisms across scales and policy domains, and a set of responsive and adaptive tools to anticipate, assess and address domestic, transboundary and long-term impacts of policies (OECD, 2019). Mainstreaming and environmental policy integration refer specifically to aims to integrate biodiversity concerns and the opportunities that biodiversity provides into other

sectors and policy domains (Tudose *et al.*, 2021; Venghaus *et al.*, 2019).

- **Meta-governance** (or governance of governance) aims to design and manage sound combinations of hierarchical, market and network governance to achieve the best possible outcomes (Meuleman, 2020).
- **Multi-level governance** aims to realize policy coherence across levels of governance, ranging from city and sub-national level to national and global level policymaking. Multi-level governance primarily requires vertical coordination across sectors and across scale to ensure coherence and effectiveness (Melloni *et al.*, 2022). Five key gaps in this governance approach of relevance to the nexus have been identified: (i) accountability gaps, (ii) administrative gaps, (iii) policy gaps, (iv) capacity gaps, and (v) data and information gaps (Melloni *et al.*, 2022).
- **Polycentric governance** as defined by Ostrom *et al.* (1961) refers to the presence of many centres of decision-making, which are formally independent of each other. The decision-making units in a polycentric governance arrangement are often overlapping as they are nested at multiple jurisdictional levels (e.g., local, state and national) and in governance units that cut across jurisdictions (McGinnis & Ostrom, 2012; E. Ostrom, 2009). Studies of nexus interactions, such as across food-energy-water links, have increasingly characterized these systems as polycentric, given roles for governments, intergovernmental and non-state actors through intermediary organisations and soft modes of influence (Villamayor-Tomas, 2018).

Much of the integrated governance literature deals with fragmentation of current governance systems, which has been blamed for resource-use inefficiencies and redundancies and antagonism between policies. Public policies remain predominantly sector-based in terms of objectives, goals and institutions (Affolderbach & Schulz, 2016). Sector-based, or siloed, policymaking causes unintended and potentially negative impacts of one sector on others, and eventually undermines resource availability (Artioli *et al.*, 2017). Some of this fragmentation has also been linked to structures of power (e.g., actors in silos attempting to retain their power and avoiding building bridges across sectors that might diminish this).

However, integrated governance approaches have not been a panacea to these dilemmas. They have been critiqued for depoliticizing political choice (Maas, 2023); searching for optimal solutions and forgetting about surprise, experimentation and variation to deal with complexity (Chaffin *et al.*, 2016); and limited attention to challenging established institutions and agency of actors, resulting in a

potential weakness in addressing power imbalances and the structural barriers that perpetuate sectoral thinking (Blackstock *et al.*, 2023). There has been perception by some actors that integration across policies means more meetings and plans but less action (Mitchell *et al.*, 2015). Moreover, the frequent emphasis of this literature on specific sectors may contribute to a less comprehensive understanding of the interconnectedness within the nexus (Stout & Love, 2019).

Within the leading political and scientific debates, the nexus is often described as a neutral and apolitical concept (Wiegleb & Bruns, 2018), but this represents an important misconception, as “[i]nfluential concepts in policymaking are not merely neutral or scientific; they do not emerge by chance but, rather, are the emanation of complex webs of interests, ideologies and power” (Molle, 2008: p.132). Thus, despite growing attention to different types and approaches to integrated and adaptive governance, much of this literature does not explicitly deal with social, political and normative aspects among nexus elements (Wiegleb & Bruns, 2018), nor the question of how to achieve better outcomes across biodiversity, water, food, health and climate change and the contributions various actors can make to these goals (Artioli *et al.*, 2017; Venghaus *et al.*, 2019; Weitz *et al.*, 2017). Accordingly, authors have increasingly turned to the concept of ‘nexus governance’ to deal with these deficiencies, as discussed in **section 4.2.3** below.

4.2.3 Existing definitions of nexus governance and their challenges

Various authors have started to define the concept of “nexus governance” e.g., (Newell *et al.*, 2019; Opejin *et al.*, 2020; Urbinatti *et al.*, 2020). Nexus governance is widely seen as involving public, private and civil society actors and organizations coordinating activities across policy domains, governance levels and geographical boundaries (Leck *et al.*, 2015). The concept of nexus governance broadly highlights innovative and holistic perspectives to identify, analyze and manage interdependencies through an interdisciplinary approach with consideration of how sectors and policies interact (Koulouri & Mouraviev, 2019). However, there is no current consensus on what nexus governance should or does encompass (see **Table 4.3**).

Given the current lack of agreement and consensus, there is considerable room for more systematic and clear definitions of nexus governance. For example, none of the definitions in **Table 4.3** emerge from systematic reviews or intergovernmental assessment processes. Several authors have also pointed to persistent gaps in the existing nexus governance literature, including “(i) conditions for cross-sector coordination and collaboration; ii) dynamics that

Table 4.3 Definitions of nexus governance in the literature.

Proposed definition and components of nexus governance	Source
Nexus governance is “the relational structures and processes that connect actors across sectors, governance levels, geographical boundaries and/or public, private and civic spheres, and that provide steering mechanisms for the integration of management and governance systems across different policy domains. Nexus governance may involve participant-governed networks such as regional round tables and centralized governance characterized by an asymmetrical power distribution, as well as governance through an administrative organization set up for this purpose”. Key components include three dimensions of network structure, relations and narratives in the governance systems.	Stein & Jaspersen (2019)
Nexus governance is approached from three perspectives: assessment (cross-scale and cross-sectoral coherence), awareness (co-design and co-delivery of solutions to stakeholders) and accessibility (cohesive system of principles). Nine principles are identified, including connectivity, innovation, equitability, participation, coordination, sharing, legitimacy, empowerment and strategy. These nine guiding principles are based on the experience of the authors and lessons learned from case studies and approaches in projects related to food-energy-water nexus governance.	Yuan <i>et al.</i> (2021); Yuan & Lo (2020, 2022)
“Nexus governance encompass all the public and private actions, reactions, actors, formal and informal processes, and institutions that enable or constrain integrated planning and implementation across the water, energy and food sectors. ... Effective WEF [water, energy, food] nexus governance is thus interested in enhancing policy, legislative, institutional, technological, financial and stakeholder coherence in a manner that sector integration is actively pursued, synergies enhanced, and trade-offs managed at different levels with little conflict.”	Oulu <i>et al.</i> (2023)
Nexus governance “entails legal, political and administrative arrangements and decisions to mitigate conflicts and ensure equitable access to high-quality water, food and energy services, as well as protection of the ecosystems that support provision of these services.”	Takaes Santos (2020)
“Governing the nexus necessarily involves governing the trade-offs between the different sectors and dealing with the plurality and interactions of policies that are in place. It requires appropriate legal, political and administrative arrangements and decisions on applicable and suitable instruments (economic and otherwise) to mitigate trade-offs and ensure access to high-quality water, food and energy services for all while safe-guarding the ecosystems that provide these services. Cross-sectoral governance also needs to respond to growing risks and uncertainties, with a focus on processes of change.”	Bhaduri <i>et al.</i> (2015)
“Food-energy-water nexus governance considers the process of integrated management, policy and decision-making across the three sectors for coordinated governance approaches and achievement of shared outcomes”. Key components and indicators include institutional support, actor inclusivity, intentional leadership, shared resources, knowledge sharing, shared goals, open communication, power balance, trust, commitment and shared values.	Jones-Crank <i>et al.</i> (2022)

influence the nexus beyond cross-sector interactions; and (iii) political and cognitive factors as determinants of policy change” (Weitz *et al.*, 2017: p.165). Furthermore, much of the existing literature on nexus governance focuses on what isn’t working, e.g., governance failures as a result of fragmented, reactive, exclusive and opaque systems (Lebel *et al.*, 2020), while there has been significantly less work on empirical examples of nexus governance and on positive examples of successes.

Nexus governance can also be related to **transformative governance**, a recent approach that refers to strategies, actions and roles of key actors implemented at different spatial scales (from local to global) aimed at enabling transformative change, either for governing transformative change or transforming governance to open up avenues for transformative change (Visseren-Hamakers *et al.*, 2021; Visseren-Hamakers & Kok, 2022). In line with the IPBES Transformative Change Assessment, this assessment defines transformative change as fundamental, system-wide shifts across views, structures and practices. When such shifts address the underlying causes of biodiversity loss and nature’s decline, transformative change contributes to

a just and sustainable world. Transformative governance thus refers to an alteration of existing configurations of views, structures and practices to enable effective and just biodiversity governance. Actions include integrative governance that revises decision-making processes, an inclusive governance that creates ownership and deliberation among stakeholders, a global and multi-level governance that addresses global interdependencies, as well as an adaptive governance that continuously evaluates and revises regulatory and holds responsible actors accountable for addressing biodiversity related issues (IPBES Transformative Change Assessment). Yet it is currently unclear to what extent nexus governance might contribute to transformative change while also addressing nexus-related sustainability problems more generally (Pascual *et al.*, 2022; Visseren-Hamakers & Kok, 2022).

Given these limitations, a systematic review of existing policy and governance literature has been undertaken to identify gaps and highlight empirical examples of where governance that focuses on interconnections among two or more nexus elements is happening (see **section 4.3**). Building on the review, **section 4.5** proposes a more

comprehensive definition and operationalization of the concept of nexus governance and provides case study examples of it in real-world practice. This includes examples of scaling nexus governance (as introduced in **section 4.4**). This more comprehensive approach to nexus governance includes a deeper and more systematic assessment of enablers and barriers; enhanced understanding of the key actors and arenas of engagement involved and/or excluded in the governance of nexus interactions; and examination of the key cross cutting issues of equity, justice and intersectionality. This section also discusses how to bring nexus governance into alignment with transformative governance in terms of aiming for more transformational changes. **Section 4.6** then highlights the important role of decision-support tools to address some of the complexities involved in governing nexus interactions.

4.2.4 Policy instruments and their relationship to the nexus

Policy instruments are the different interventions (formal rules, laws, social norms and processes, etc.) made by decision makers (including governments and public authorities, intergovernmental organizations, or companies) to ensure that policy objectives are supported and achieved by influencing the behaviour of other stakeholders. IPBES has classified four primary types of policy instruments: (i) economic and financial instruments; (ii) legal and regulatory instruments; (iii) rights-based instruments and customary norms; and (iv) social and cultural instruments (**Table 4.4**). These instruments are used across different types of governance approaches in different ways.

Table 4.4 General categories of policy instruments.

Source: IPBES (2016).

Policy instruments	Description	Examples
Economic and financial policy instruments	Economic and financial instruments include regulations that financially incentivize or constrain specific activities by handing out or taking away economic resources, including for example subsidies, taxes, charges and fiscal transfers (IPBES, 2016).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Natural capital/ecosystem accounting Socially responsible investments Water funds Debt for nature swaps Green bonds Reducing Emissions from Deforestation and Forest Degradation and the role of conservation, sustainable management of forests and enhancement of forest carbon stocks in developing countries (REDD+)
Legal and regulatory policy instruments	Legal and regulatory policy instruments include formal rules and regulations that legally regulate (prohibit, sanction or inhibit) certain activities. Planning instruments sometimes take the form of environmental management plans, which outline programmes of actions, which have been identified as part of the environmental management systems (IPBES, 2016).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rights-based approaches including human rights-based approach and rights of nature Multilateral agreements Marine and terrestrial protected areas / no-take zones Social and environmental standards National Biodiversity Strategic Action Plans
Social and cultural policy instruments	Social and cultural policy instruments include information-based instruments and voluntary or collective actions with an emphasis on the intertwined relationships between ecosystems and sociocultural dynamics. Awareness based voluntary interventions may include for example (i) information-related instruments like environmental education, eco-labelling, pollutant release and transfer registers, biodiversity registers, awareness raising (including award schemes), information dissemination and community right to know; (ii) self-regulation, voluntary agreements, corporate social responsibility, buyer-supplier relations; (iii) participation (social pressure, worshipping etc.); and (iv) enhancement of collective action of Indigenous Peoples and local communities (IPLC) and local resource users, etc (IPBES, 2016).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Voluntary certification Co-management of land and seas with IPLC Scientific and technological policy instruments Behaviour nudges for reduced consumption Indigenous and community conserved areas Other effective area-based conservation measures Sacred sites and landscapes Indigenous institutions that govern management of resources
Rights-based and customary policy instruments	Rights-based and customary instruments aim to strengthen collective rights and customary institutions of IPLC that promote an equitable and fair management of natural resources (IPBES, 2016).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Official government institutions that acknowledge IPLC's rights to govern their lands, territories and resources International and national human rights instruments

An important consideration is that many governance and policy options for the nexus are likely to consist of packages of policies, actions, management activities and governance arrangements rather than single interventions (Howlett, 2005; Kern *et al.*, 2019; United Nations

Economic Commission for Europe, 2018). Although individual governance approaches and policy instruments are discussed in the literature, the reality is that many sociopolitical options will consist of these combinations of instruments, often referred to as a policy packages, policy

Table 4.5 **Examples of governance approaches and policy instruments highlighting the need for policy mixes consisting of different sociopolitical options, drawn from illustrative cases.**

Gray icons for nexus elements refer to non-direct relations. The diversity of actors (see Chapter 1, section 1.3.3 and Table 1.2), relevant cross-cutting issues (see section 4.3.6) and enablers/barriers (see section 4.2.5) are also identified for each example.

Cases	Nexus elements 	Governance approach	Policy instruments	Actors	Enablers & barriers	Cross-cutting issues (SDGs)	References
EU emissions standards		Hierarchical	Legal & Regulatory Instruments	Global & regional institutions Private sector & business Organizations National Governments	Policy design & Implementation Finance & Economics Institutional capacity	SDG 9	Hoofman <i>et al.</i> (2018)
Payments for ecosystem services in Costa Rica		Hierarchical	Economic & Financial Instruments	National Governments	Policy design & Implementation		Sterner & Coria (2012)
EU Farm to Fork (F2F) and revision of Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) under the EU Green Deal		Network	Economic & Financial Instruments	National Governments Civil Society Organizations	Finance & Economics	SDG 7	Bierzoza <i>et al.</i> (2021)
South African water management reform (exclusive rights; water allowances)		Network	Rights-based & customary norms	Global & Regional Institutions National Governments Civil Society Organizations Local Governments & municipalities	Policy design & Implementation	SDG1, SDG10	Movik (2011); Schyff (2007)
Modified Taungya System, Ghana – community and collaborative forest management		Network	Social & cultural Instruments	IPLCs National Governments Global & Regional Institutions Financing Institutions	Policy design & Implementation		Akamani & Holzmueller (2017)
Pollution labelling system in Indonesia		Hierarchical	Social & cultural Instruments	National Governments Private Sector & Business Organizations	Technology & knowledge Behaviour & lifestyle	SDG 1	Sterner & Coria (2012)
Community forest management in Quintana Roo, Mexico		Community	Social & cultural Instruments Legal & Regulatory Instruments	National & Local Government Indigenous Peoples and local communities	Policy design & Implementation Finance & Economics Institutional capacity	SDG 10, SDG 12	Ellis <i>et al.</i> (2015)

mixes or bundles of response options (the approach taken in **Chapter 5**) (Barton *et al.*, 2017; Capano & Howlett, 2020; Dubash *et al.*, 2022a; Howlett, 2019; Kelemen *et al.*, 2022; Park *et al.*, 2022). Therefore, identifying which combinations of governance and policy approaches are well suited to simultaneously achieve synergistic outcomes for biodiversity and the other nexus elements of water, food, health and climate change is crucial for informing response option choices. For example, the EU Green Deal bundles several response options together, such as the EU Farm to Fork and Common Agricultural Policy, which aim to address the challenges of agricultural production regulation and effects on water quality in Europe. **Table 4.5** provides some specific examples of mixes of sociopolitical options in relation to the nexus.

4.2.5 Enablers and barriers to governing the nexus

Effectively governing the nexus can be facilitated or constrained by a number of enablers and barriers. In this chapter and throughout the assessment enablers and barriers are considered as specific characteristics or contexts of a nexus challenge that facilitate or impair the implementation, operationalization or effectiveness of response options (including governance approaches), while noting that a particular factor can sometimes be either an enabler or a barrier or both (Dubash *et al.*, 2022b; Park *et al.*, 2022). **Table 4.6** presents a typology of enablers and barriers affecting the governance of nexus interactions derived from an expert review of enablers and barriers

Table 4.6 Enablers and barriers of the governance of nexus interactions organized as a structured typology.

In **Chapter 4** enablers/barriers to governance are analysed to identify those policy and sociopolitical options that have transformative potential. In **Chapter 5**, enablers/barriers are analysed with respect to assessment of promising response options.

Categories	Examples of enablers/barriers (Chapter 4)	Criteria to assess response options (Chapter 5)	Key literature
Policy design & implementation	Consideration of synergies/trade-offs.	Impacts on each nexus element	Denton <i>et al.</i> (2022)
	Clarity and measurability of targets and effectiveness of monitoring		
	Policy alignment with social, political, and international priorities/values	Alignment with political priorities Alignment with international frameworks Social acceptability	
	Existence of a common understanding of nexus challenges/opportunities		
	Consideration of spatial and temporal scale of implementation (as well as interlinkages with other scales)	Geographic scale Temporal scale	
Equity & diversity	Consideration of equity, actor diversity and diverse values (including IPLC perspectives and across generations)	Equity Transformative change potential	Denton <i>et al.</i> (2022); Kelemen <i>et al.</i> (2022); Lecocq <i>et al.</i> (2022)
Institutional capacity	Number and quality of partnerships, level of participatory and collaborative planning/ implementation, and level of coordination among sectors	Equity Transformative change potential	Dubash <i>et al.</i> (2022)
	Attention to power asymmetries and redistribution of power	Equity Transformative change potential	
	Characteristics of political systems and cycles (separation of powers, electoral system, democratic representation, opposition in political parties)	Transformative change potential	
	Organizational learning and course correction capability	Transformative change potential	
	Complexity and uncertainty		
	Degree of corruption/corruption incidence	Transformative change potential	

Table 4.6

Categories	Examples of enablers/barriers (Chapter 4)	Criteria to assess response options (Chapter 5)	Key literature
Finance & economics	Amount of financial investments (including ratio of short- to long-term funding) and whether it is siloed or not	Economic implications	Denton <i>et al.</i> (2022); Lecocq <i>et al.</i> (2022)
	Costs, cost/benefit ratios and variability in costs and benefits (across space and over time)	Economic implications	
	Valuation and commodification of nature	Economic implications	
	Evaluation of externalities		
	Prevalence of financial incentives crowding out other incentives	Economic implications	
Behaviour & lifestyle	Acceptability of social movements and citizen engagement, extent of individual and collective agency and leadership, and ability to implement environmental litigation	Transformative change potential	Denton <i>et al.</i> (2022); Dubash <i>et al.</i> (2022)
	Nature of habits, beliefs, norms and values	Transformative change potential	
	Amount and quality of awareness and education	Transformative change potential	
	Role of social innovation	Transformative change potential	
	Consideration of ethical concerns with respect to influencing behaviour/lifestyle	Transformative change potential	
	Media coverage		
Technology	Access to technology	Technical feasibility Transformative change potential	Denton <i>et al.</i> (2022)
	Existence of technological lock-in	Technical feasibility Transformative change potential	
	Trust in technological solutions	Technical feasibility Transformative change potential	
	Access to technology for integrated monitoring	Technical feasibility Transformative change potential	
Material/ non-material endowment (non- financial)	Availability of natural capital	Impacts on each nexus element Social acceptability	Denton <i>et al.</i> (2022)
	Availability of produced capital	Impacts on each nexus element Social acceptability	
	Availability of human capital	Impacts on each nexus element Social acceptability	
	Availability of social capital	Impacts on each nexus element Social acceptability	

identified in recent IPCC and IPBES assessments reports, as well as other nexus-related literature. In doing this review, specific attention was given to existing structured typologies relevant to nexus challenges. These enablers and barriers also relate to the criteria used in **Chapter 5** to assess response options (see **Chapter 5.0**) and the governance sections of each of the subchapters of **Chapter 5** also evaluate different response options against these categories (see **Chapters 5.1.3, 5.2.3, 5.3.3, 5.4.3 and 5.5.3**) (**Table 4.6**).

4.2.6 Actors and their roles governing the nexus

There are multiple actors involved in governance and decision-making for the nexus and the implementation of diverse response options across sectors and scales (see also **Chapter 5**). **Chapter 1** has identified the categories of actors likely to be of importance (**Chapter 1, section 1.3.3, Table 1.2**) and highlighting the scale at which they operate. This chapter analyses actors' participation in governance

approaches and implementation of policy and sociopolitical options, including through a systematic review of the literature (**section 4.3**).

Actors seek to influence public decisions and enable action to address societal aspirations, needs and concerns (Kooiman, 2003). The main actors described in the **Chapter 1** categorization can be divided into three different (but not mutually exclusive) groups according to their level of influence or power and affectedness in relation to response options and governance across the nexus (Chevalier & Buckles, 2008; Kelemen *et al.*, 2022). This includes:

- **Actors with influence:** actors and institutions who influence decision-making processes related to the nexus and therefore have an impact on those who implement decisions. This also includes institutions/actors that can act as lobbyists or as watchdogs to foster accountability through advocacy.
- **Affected actors:** people, including communities and marginalized groups who are directly involved in (and

dependent on) the implementation of nexus-related decisions, and have their own stakes and interests (outlined in more detail in **Chapters 5, 6 and 7**).

- **Key players:** people and institutions who can both influence and become affected by decisions.

There are clear differences in the level of influence that different actors can exert depending on their social groups, sector or scale of intervention (Alonso Roldán *et al.*, 2015; Felipe-Lucia *et al.*, 2015). Understanding asymmetries in power and influence, information and capacities among these actors is therefore critical for considering who benefits or is burdened by decisions and who has both the power and/or the responsibility to make changes linked to nexus interlinkages, and the drivers that act on these interlinkages (M. S. Reed *et al.*, 2009; Vallet *et al.*, 2019). Power can be exerted through formal and informal institutions, as key actors from government, global and regional institutions, knowledge communities, financing institutions, media and the arts, civil society and the private sector seek to influence the trajectory of development. Interactions and relationships between

Box 4.2 **Fisherwomen networks in Brazil promoting governance and the rights and interests of women in the fishing sector.**

Southern Bahia, in the northeast region of Brazil, has experienced significant changes in weather patterns, including rising temperatures, reduced rainfall, and rising sea levels. These changes are affecting the livelihoods of many people, including fisherwomen, who depend on the ocean for their income and survival. The community is in front of Abrolhos Bank, the largest coral reef area in the South Atlantic and home to the greatest marine biodiversity of the region, including tuna and marlin, but species are suffering the effects of climate change, including coral bleaching (Duarte *et al.*, 2020). Fisherwomen in the region report a reduction in the availability of fish and crustaceans due to changes in ocean currents and water temperature (ICES, 2022). This has made it difficult for them to support their families, communities and way of life. In addition, rising sea levels have made it difficult to access fishing grounds, in addition to causing damage to homes and infrastructure, and displacement of communities, resulting in increased food insecurity and health risks (Galappaththi *et al.*, 2020). These changes have all affected the availability of fish and seafood that these women depend on for their income and food security. Changes in weather patterns can also affect agricultural productivity, leading to food shortages and malnutrition. The loss of biodiversity can also lead to the loss of traditional knowledge and practices related to food and health.

In response to these challenges, initiatives aimed at promoting sustainable fishing practices and protecting marine biodiversity have helped to mitigate the impacts of climate change on fisherfolks and their communities (Hanich *et al.*, 2018). The fisherwomen organized various networks to provide a platform for women to come together, share their experiences and

develop collective strategies to address common challenges. An example is the Bahia Fisheries Extractive Community Women's Network, established in 2009 to promote the empowerment of women in the fisheries sector and improve their access to resources and opportunities by offering training and capacity building programmes on issues such as sustainable fishing practices, gender equality and human rights (D. O. D. Gonçalves *et al.*, 2021).

These regional networks connect with the Articulação Nacional das Pescadoras, a national network founded in 2006 that brings together fisherwomen from all over Brazil to defend policies that promote the rights and interests of women in the fishing sector. Networks are connected and collaborating on various issues related to the empowerment of fisherwomen and the promotion of their rights and interests, and more recently on the discussion of strategies to address the impacts of climate change. Currently there is already a network of women in several other places: Pará, Rio de Janeiro, Santa Catarina, Maranhão, Piauí and Northern Brazil. Working together, these networks can amplify their impact and promote a more inclusive and sustainable fisheries sector that benefits all community members and positively impacts multiple nexus elements. Amplifying these efforts through peer-to-peer learning and solidarity building through coalitions with other women-led initiatives such as the Sea Women of Melanesia initiative (Sea Women of Melanesia, 2024) has outlined a methodological approach that incorporates cultural and social aspects of fisheries and which can strengthen marine conservation, promote adaptation to climate change and enhance local livelihoods.

governance actors are foundational to understanding the power asymmetries that affect governance across the nexus (Bodin, 2017; Bodin & Crona, 2009; Bréthaut *et al.*, 2019; Crona & Bodin, 2010; Srigiri & Dombrowsky, 2022; Stein *et al.*, 2018; Weitz *et al.*, 2017). For example, **Box 4.2** presents a case study from Brazil emphasizing how actors affected by environmental challenges can self-organize in networks, build collective strategies and capacity and therefore become key players in governance. This highlights the importance of the relative capacities of actors.

To understand how capacities may function as either enablers or barriers to effective nexus governance, it is necessary to understand the context in which these capacities operate. Such a context is defined not only by the actors and institutions themselves, but also the physical, social and political spaces (referred to here as the “arenas of engagement”, see **section 4.5**) in which these actors and institutions engage with each other and with the nexus. **section 4.5.1** provides a more complete discussion of actors and their corresponding arenas of engagement to elucidate the role of context in determining governance of nexus interactions. This is followed by a fuller discussion of capacities in **section 4.5.5**.

4.3 SYSTEMATIC REVIEW OF GOVERNANCE APPROACHES AND POLICY AND SOCIOPOLITICAL OPTIONS FOR THE NEXUS

4.3.1 Introduction

As identified in **section 4.2**, governance approaches and policy and sociopolitical options provide the broad context for the nexus, while governance and policy settings can provide the enabling conditions to address the five nexus challenges identified in **Chapter 1, section 1.1.2** (complexity, governance, values, scaling, and financing). This section presents a structured review of the literature on governance and policy options for the nexus (see data management report for the detailed review methodology³) and how these relate to the nexus challenges, actors and scales, enablers and barriers, and cross-cutting issues.

The review of governance and policy options for the nexus in this section draws primarily on the four key governance approaches identified in **section 4.2** (hierarchical

governance, market governance, network governance and community governance). These governance approaches reflect a diversity of governance structures and have been used previously to assess climate governance (Bednar & Henstra, 2018). The review also draws on the four IPBES classes of policy instruments: legal and regulatory instruments; rights-based instruments and customary norms; economic and financial instruments; and social and cultural instruments (**section 4.2.4**). These classifications of governance and policy options provide a framework to assess in the academic literature which combinations of governance approaches and policy instruments are proposed, associated with, or effective at achieving nexus outcomes and for which nexus challenges (United Nations Economic Commission for Europe, 2018, 2021).

The success of governments and society in purposefully responding to the nexus challenges depend on their ability to design governance and policy that are effective at achieving outcomes across multiple nexus elements and potentially transformative. Yet, the most appropriate options will likely depend on the specific challenges present in any given context, the actors and institutions involved in the nexus, the enablers/barriers present, and the specific nexus elements in focus (Blicharska *et al.*, n.d.; Scott *et al.*, 2011; Scott & Sugg, 2015). Therefore, explicit consideration of these factors is important for assessing sociopolitical options for the nexus. Previous assessments of the water-food-energy-ecosystem nexus propose a conceptualization of nexus options consisting of bundles of different types of “solutions” (cooperation, governance, economic and policy instruments, and infrastructure and innovation) that are matched to specific water-related problems in a “dual-axis” framework (UN ECE, 2021; United Nations Economic Commission for Europe, 2018). In the review undertaken in this section, a similar approach is adopted where the likely efficacy of different bundles of governance approaches and policy instruments for addressing different nexus challenges and nexus elements is assessed. This aims to improve understanding of nexus sociopolitical options in terms of the governance of what (i.e., which nexus challenges and nexus elements), by whom (i.e., which actors and institutions), and how (i.e., which governance and policy instruments) (Hölscher & Frantzeskaki, 2020).

Achieving positive outcomes across the nexus is unlikely to be the only objective of public policy, and so there is also the need to consider cross-cutting issues such as equity and justice, poverty, economic growth, employment, education, gender and values (including Indigenous values and knowledge) and other aspects related to the SDGs (Forestier & Kim, 2020; Jacouton *et al.*, 2022; Meilland & Lecocq, 2024; United Nations, 2015), noting that some of these may trade-off strongly with nexus elements, e.g., economic growth and biodiversity (Otero *et al.*, 2020) (**Chapter 2, section 2.3.2.1**). Failing to take account of these broader

3. The data management report for the **section 4.3** systematic literature review is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13913214>.

cross-cutting issues can block policy implementation and outcomes, as they may lack acceptance and support from civil society, IPLC and other actors. For example, in France in 2018, the Yellow Vests movement (arising from public discontentment that resulted in mass demonstrations, blockades and street violence) emerged as a response to a carbon tax on fossil fuels that would have strongly affected household purchasing power and perception of loss of income, with no redistribution mechanism (Douenne & Fabre, 2020). Furthermore, since there are strong links between the nexus elements themselves and the SDGs, there is an imperative to understand the implications of sociopolitical options for the nexus for a range of cross-cutting issues from a sustainable development perspective. Although biodiversity, water, food, health and climate change are embedded in many of the SDGs, there is a broader set of cross-cutting issues that are important in considering governance and policy options for the nexus. These cross-cutting issues can also act as entry-points for setting policy agendas so are an important focus for policy development from a nexus viewpoint.

The aims of the structured review were to interrogate which bundles of governance approaches and policy instruments may be most appropriate for tackling which nexus challenges and in which contexts, with the aim of providing policymakers with diagnostic insights. The review thus aimed to:

- Assess evidence for associations between different governance approaches, policy instruments and nexus challenges for different nexus elements.

- Identify the key actors involved in managing the nexus and how these vary across different nexus challenges and nexus elements.
- Assess the enablers/barriers encountered across different governance approaches, policy instruments and how these vary across different nexus challenges and nexus elements.
- Assess which cross-cutting issues are considered across different governance approaches, policy instruments and how these vary across different nexus challenges and nexus elements.

4.3.2 General review summary

The review approach consisted of searching (using online databases in English) the peer-reviewed literature for articles on governance and policy related to managing nexuses of at least two of biodiversity, water, food, health and climate change using well-defined search criteria (see the data management report for the detailed review methodology²). Information was extracted from relevant articles related to governance and policy instruments studied and the nexus elements and challenges considered as well as other contextual information. Two hundred and two relevant articles were identified, which were used to assess evidence for the association between proposed governance and policy options, nexus challenges, relevant actors, enablers/barriers and cross-cutting issues. The review methods, data underpinning the review results, and

the code used to analyse the data can be found in the data management report².

Of the peer-reviewed literature, 21% of papers ($n = 43$) were purely conceptual, perspective or opinion articles, while 46% ($n = 92$) were reviews. Only 32% ($n = 65$) contained analysis or interpretation of empirical data (either quantitative or qualitative) and a very small number (12%; $n = 24$) were based on modelling studies. Formally assessing the effectiveness of policy and governance options is a priority for research and better monitoring of the nexus is crucial (Pettorelli *et al.*, 2021; Stoy *et al.*, 2018). However, the literature that this review looked at suggests that little

attention has been paid to this problem to date, with only a small proportion containing empirical analysis.

Around 32% ($n = 64$) of the studies were based on no specific geographical location, reflecting the large number of reviews and perspectives (Figure 4.2). Where a particular geographical location was studied, there was a wide spread of geographic regions with the greatest number of studies from Sub-Saharan Africa ($n = 35$) followed by Latin America and the Caribbean ($n = 24$) (Figure 4.2). The least represented regions were Northern Africa ($n = 5$), Micronesia ($n = 2$), Melanesia ($n = 2$), and Polynesia ($n = 1$). A wide spread of spatial scales was studied, ranging from multi-

regional scales to site scales. The most common scales of study were national (whole country) ($n = 50$), sub-national >100 km² (watershed) ($n = 50$), regional (multiple countries, whole continents) ($n = 27$) and local >1 km² to 100 km² (neighbourhood to municipality) ($n = 22$) scales. However, multi-regional (multiple continents/geographic regions/global) and site (field to farm) scales of study were rare ($n = 6$ and $n = 3$ respectively). Thus, studies at very large and very small scales were rarely found in the literature.

The most common nexus challenges studied were the governance ($n = 132$) and complexity ($n = 115$) challenges, while the scaling ($n = 42$) and financing ($n = 27$) challenges were the least studied (Figure 4.3). The high frequency of representation of the governance and complexity challenges may reflect the focus in the keywords used to search for articles on governance. In most cases papers that focused on the scaling challenge did so with respect to monitoring and knowledge generation, indicating a lack of consideration of these more broadly (consistent with the finding of few empirical studies). The limited focus on financing reflects a considerable research gap in linking the role of governance to economic and financial tools (see Chapter 6).

The nexus elements considered in the review were dominated by water ($n = 168$) and food ($n = 167$) and explained by the strong emphasis in the nexus governance and policy literature on the food-energy-water (FEW) nexus (Figure 4.3). Biodiversity ($n = 68$) and health ($n = 40$) were the least considered nexus elements. However, the review suggests that many of the governance and policy challenges that apply to the food-water (and energy) nexus may also apply more broadly to biodiversity, health and climate change. For example, the literature on food and water nexuses focused predominantly on the complexity and governance challenges, and this was similar for the biodiversity, climate change and health nexuses, suggesting that the challenges may be similar regardless of the specific nexus elements considered (Figure 4.3). Further understanding of this is key to the design of effective nexus governance and policy settings and remains a major gap in our understanding.

Studies considered between two and five nexus elements, with the most common number of nexus elements considered being two ($n = 118$) and a consideration of all five nexus elements being rare ($n = 12$). The low number of nexus elements considered suggests that examples of governing the nexus and setting policy across a wide range of nexus elements may be rare and therefore remains a major gap in the nexus governance literature. Interestingly, when biodiversity, climate change and health were considered then the number of nexus elements tended to be higher than when food and water alone were considered (Figure 4.3), reflecting the bias of the nexus governance literature towards water and food in isolation.

4.3.3 Results: existing governance approaches and policy options

The most common of the four governance approaches in the review were hierarchical ($n = 49$) and network ($n = 39$) governance, while community ($n = 28$) and market ($n = 22$) governance were considered less often. However, 21 other governance approaches ('other') were also specifically discussed in the literature and these included most commonly: integrative governance ($n = 11$), multi-level governance ($n = 6$), adaptive governance ($n = 4$) and polycentric governance ($n = 4$) (see Table 4.2). Other governance approaches included in the 'other' category included collaborative governance, coordinated governance, nexus governance and system governance, among others. Interestingly, transformative governance in the context of the nexus was not encountered in the articles reviewed. The most common policy instruments were legal and regulatory instruments ($n = 102$) and economic and financial instruments ($n = 69$), while social and cultural instruments ($n = 28$) and rights-based instruments and customary norms ($n = 25$) policy instruments were proposed or described less often.

These governance approaches and instruments were examined in relation to each of the nexus challenges (Figure 4.4). The most commonly studied nexus challenges were the governance and complexity challenges. The most common governance and policy bundles encountered were hierarchical/network governance coupled with legal and regulatory/economic and financial policy instruments.

The focus on hierarchical and network governance in addressing nexus challenges may reflect the need for greater integration and policy coordination across broad sectors and scales, including across national boundaries, depending on the actor and institutional context (Pahl-Wostl *et al.*, 2021; Primmer *et al.*, 2015). For example, one review of the governance challenges in 22 study case studies in Europe and Latin American countries observed that a lack of intersectoral coordination and vertical integration was an obstacle to multifunctionality and the upscaling of policy options such as green and blue infrastructure and landscape planning (Saarikoski *et al.*, 2018). Although community governance may also be successful in achieving policy coordination, this is most likely to be relevant at the local scale and there were few local studies reflected in the review. Market governance was least often associated with nexus solutions, suggesting that it may be ineffective at achieving targeted policy coordination without being used in combination with other approaches. Interestingly, economic and financial instruments were commonly considered policy instruments but were often embedded within network or hierarchical governance approaches, not solely market governance approaches. For example, payments

Figure 4.4 Associations among nexus challenges, governance approaches and policy instruments based on the review.

The grids on the left show the number of studies reflecting each governance and policy instrument combination proposed or assessed as a solution to each nexus challenge in the reviewed articles. The single grid on the right is a legend and shows the governance and policy instrument combination that each grid square represented in the grids on the left. The width of the arrows linking the coloured grids to nexus challenges reflects the relative number of articles focused on each nexus challenge.

Icons from Flaticon under licence CC-BY-NC 4.0.

for ecosystem services as part of the Hidrosogamoso hydropower project in Colombia for water, food, biodiversity and energy are delivered within a largely hierarchical governance approach (Rodríguez-de-Francisco *et al.*, 2019).

The similarity of bundles of governance and policy instruments across the different nexus challenges (Figure 4.4) suggests that other factors may be more important than the specific nexus challenge. In particular, specific governance and policy recommendations vary more strongly among and within the different combinations of nexus elements (Figure 4.5 and Figure 4.6). This is possibly due to the different contexts and actors related to the management of these nexus elements within element combinations. For example, both Brack *et al.* (2019) and Ataur Rahman & Rahman (2015) study governance and

policy solutions that consider all five nexus elements but the context and actors in each case lead to different possible solutions. In the Bangladesh coastal zone, Ataur Rahman & Rahman (2015) consider possible legal and regulatory planning mechanisms within a community governance setting for coastal defences to protect local communities and nexus elements including food and biodiversity. On the other hand, in addressing the challenge of research to achieve a non-toxic environment, sustainable management of water resources and ecosystem management in the European Union, Brack *et al.* (2019) focus more on solutions related to financial and economic incentives. This suggest that variation in the specific contexts for each nexus problem is likely to be a key factor even if broad generalisations across nexus challenges can be made.

Figure 4.5 Associations among governance approaches and combinations of nexus elements based on the review.

Colours of the boxes denotes the percentage of occurrences for each nexus element combination. There is considerable variation in governance approaches across the different nexus element combinations, likely due to the different contexts within which they are managed.

Figure 4.6 Associations among policy instruments and combinations of nexus elements based on the review.

Colours of the boxes denotes percentage of occurrences for each nexus element combination. There is some variation in policy instruments across the different nexus element combinations likely due to the different contexts within which they are managed.

4.3.4 Actors involved in the governance of nexus interactions

The review showed a large diversity of actors involved in governing the nexus, with the most common actors being civil society and community-based organisations ($n = 150$), local/national governments and municipalities ($n = 146$), private sector and business organisations ($n = 101$), and global/regional institutions and science-policy interfaces ($n = 94$). IPLC ($n = 18$) and media and the arts ($n = 9$) were the least discussed actors in the review,

indicating the potential for a significant knowledge gap with respect to these actors. These patterns largely held across different nexus element combinations (Figure 4.7) but with some variation, especially for knowledge and educational communities and IPLC, possibly reflecting the importance of context for these actors. Examples of some of the common combinations of actors found in the review include: interactions between government ministries and civil society to deliver Reducing emissions from Deforestation and Forest Degradation and the role of conservation, sustainable management of forests

and enhancement of forest carbon stocks in developing countries (E+) programmes (through the Civil Society National REDD and Climate Change Platform) in Cameroon to address carbon, biodiversity, and poverty alleviation

(Mbatu, 2015), and how government regulations influence the biofuels private sector in Brazil and the European Union to drive nexus outcomes across water, biodiversity, and energy (Takaes Santos, 2020).

Figure 4 7 Associations among actors and nexus elements based on the review.

Colours of the boxes denotes the percentage of occurrences for each nexus element combination.

Figure 4 8 Association between actors participating in the nexus and how these vary across spatial scales (extent).

Based on the review (percentage of occurrences for each spatial scale).

Importantly, relevant actors and institutions need to interact across scales to achieve desirable outcomes for the nexus, from local to global (Brondizio *et al.*, 2016; Covarrubias *et al.*, 2019). Yet, the diversity of actors involved did not vary significantly across scales (Figure 4.8), except for a low diversity of actors observed at the site (field to farm) scale and likely explained by the relatively low number of studies at this scale. In general, IPLC and the media and the arts are the actors who are the least represented in the nexus governance studies reviewed, no matter the scale of the reviewed studies, but particularly at larger regional and multi-regional spatial scales. Consideration of IPLC is most prevalent at the site scale (i.e., in place-based research) and multi-regional scale. Governments, the private sector and civil society are frequently involved at all scales. Finally, financial institution involvement varies depending on scale of governance: they are rarely mentioned in studies from local to national scales but are more frequently mentioned in regional and multi-regional studies (Figure 4.8).

4.3.5 Enablers and barriers

Out of the 202 reviewed studies, 188 identified or discussed enablers or barriers of nexus challenges. On average, studies mentioned slightly more enablers (3.26 ± 1.69) than barriers (2.99 ± 1.46). The review revealed that the most common factors were related to policy design and

implementation, institutional capacity, and finance and economics, and this was consistent across different nexus challenges and nexus element combinations (Figure 4.9 and Figure 4.10). These factors could equally be enablers or barriers (Figure 4.9A), highlighting that in different contexts and scales the same type of factor can enhance or hinder achievement of outcomes for the nexus. For example, financial investment, if sufficient, could enhance nexus outcomes, but if lacking, could be a barrier to the implementation of nexus sociopolitical options (Guta *et al.*, 2017; Schmidt & Matthews, 2018; Suardi & Kurian, 2015; UN ECE, 2021). Similarly, consideration of equity and actor diversity in nexus sociopolitical options can facilitate their implementation, but conflicts are often reported when it was disregarded (Middleton *et al.*, 2015; Sharma & Kumar, 2020; Tejada & Rist, 2018; van Gevelt, 2020). This suggests that many of the factors identified as enablers and barriers in the review affect nexus sociopolitical options across a continuum and so could be conceptually represented as a gradient.

Behaviour and lifestyle, technology, and material and non-material endowments were more common as enablers than as barriers (Figure 4.9A and Figure 4.10). For instance, Shahbaz *et al.* (2022) showed that access to the internet and knowledge about climate change or sustainable consumption were key determinants of nexus practices at the household level in Pakistan. In contrast, finance and

economics were found slightly more often as a barrier than as an enabler, such as in Schmidt & Matthews (2018), who observed a significant shortfall in international aid for projects targeting the water-energy-food-climate nexus, as

well as difficulties to secure required fundings because of credit risk and low credit ratings, especially in developing regions. Equity and diversity were identified less frequently than other factors (Figure 4.9A), but it is unclear if this is

because this factor has less effect on addressing nexus challenges (Figure 4.9B), or whether it is the consequence of a gap in the literature (see further discussion in 4.7). Policy design & Implementation, Institutional capacity, as well as Finance & Economics were the most frequently mentioned factors across all nexus challenges, indicating their pervasive importance in overcoming or addressing complex systemic issues (Figure 4.9B). For example, several reviewed studies concluded that finance is a barrier for the biodiversity-health-water nexus (Figure 4.10B), as illustrated by Kotzé & Kim (2022), who argue that fragmented international environmental law and the lack of integrated financial mechanisms hinder effective nexus governance, underscoring the need for reformed financial and governance structures to address interconnected nexus challenges at global scales. Behaviour and lifestyle showed the highest variation across nexus element combination, suggesting the influence of sociocultural context for this factor (Figure 4.10). The limited variation observed across nexus element combinations for technology, equity and diversity, and material and non-material endowments barriers stems from the scarce number of articles that address these factors.

Identifying the presence of enablers and barriers is important for facilitating the successful implementation of specific response options (see Chapter 5). Most reviewed studies considered at least one enabler/barrier related to the assessment criteria used by Chapter 5 (i.e., transformative change potential, consideration of equity, impacts on nexus elements, alignment with political priorities and international frameworks, social acceptability, technical

feasibility, economic implications, geographic and temporal scales of intervention) (Figure 4.11). The most common enablers/barriers observed in the systematic review were related to transformative change potential, followed by equity and impacts on each of the nexus elements criteria (Figure 4.11). In contrast, temporal change was rarely mentioned. As an example, Artioli *et al.* (2017) identified cross-sectoral integration and urban governance innovations as enablers of transformative change in relation with the water-energy-food nexus, and observed that governance fragmentation, entrenched power structures, and a reliance on techno-managerial solutions were important barriers.

4.3.6 Cross-cutting issues

Cross-cutting issues related to the SDGs, such as equity and justice, poverty, employment, economic growth and political stability, all play an important role in shaping sociopolitical options for the nexus. Overall, 89% of reviewed studies mentioned at least one cross-cutting issue. On average the reviewed studies mentioned 2.1 cross-cutting issues in addition to the nexus elements (with a standard deviation of ± 1.40). In the review, energy supply and demand were the most frequent cross-cutting issues (130 articles of the 179 mentioning at least one cross-cutting issue, or 73%). This can be explained by the predominance of studies focusing on the food-energy-water nexus in the reviewed literature (55% of reviewed papers). Energy was followed by equity and justice (35%) and poverty (23%) (Figure 4.12A). The relatively common focus on equity and justice as a cross-cutting issue in the literature

contrasts with the few studies identifying equity and diversity as an enabler or barrier (section 4.3.5). Furthermore, ILK was often considered as a cross-cutting issue in the reviewed studies (12%). There were some patterns of co-occurrence observed among cross-cutting issues, with education, employment, poverty and the economy often associated with each other. Energy supply and demand often occurred alone rather than with other cross-cutting

issues, and similar patterns were observed for access to land (Figure 4.12A, inset). Studies addressing health (Figure 4.12B) or addressing higher numbers of nexus elements (Figure 4.12C) statistically also addressed higher numbers of cross-cutting issues.

Mentions of cross-cutting issues varied across combinations of nexus elements (Figure 4.13). Energy showed the most

Figure 4.12 Cross-cutting issues mentioned in the reviewed articles.

Panel (A): Most frequently mentioned cross-cutting issues (those found in more than 5 reviewed articles). Percentages correspond to the number of reviewed articles mentioning the cross-cutting issues ($n=179$). The inset displays the co-occurrence between cross-cutting issues (i.e., calculated by dividing the number of articles that mention both cross-cutting issues in a pair by the total number of articles that address each issue individually in the pair). Panel (B): Mean number of cross-cutting issues across nexus elements. Panel (C): Mean number of cross-cutting issues across nexus complexity. In panels B and C, the whisker lines above the bars represent standard error and the letters indicate significant differences in the number of cross-cutting issues (Tukey's pairwise test, with $\alpha = 0.05$).

Figure 4 13 Occurrences of cross-cutting issues across the different combinations of nexus elements based on the review.

significant differences across combinations, likely due to its prominence in a subset of the reviewed literature that focuses on the food-energy-water nexus. ILK consideration also varied strongly across nexus element combinations, with more mentions in the articles addressing biodiversity. This is likely due to the nature and challenges of biodiversity governance being highly location and context-dependent, with IPLC participation and consideration of ILK being shown to contribute to more effective and sustainable biodiversity management when their historical stewardship and rights are acknowledged (Haq *et al.*, 2023; Kadykalo *et al.*, 2021; Vallet *et al.*, 2023; Wheeler & Root-Bernstein, 2020).

4.3.7 Conclusions and implications

The systematic review showed the disproportionate focus on the governance and policy settings of the water, food (and energy) nexus, with limited attention to biodiversity, health and climate change. The review also illustrated a diversity of bundles of policy instruments and governance approaches relevant to the nexus, but the most common approaches (i.e., network and hierarchical governance and economic/financial and regulatory policy instruments) were largely similar across nexus challenges. Therefore, generalizations about response options to manage the nexus (at least in broad terms) may be possible. For example, the common emphasis on economic and financial and legal and regulatory instruments across all nexus challenges may indicate that these are appropriate response option for managing the nexus in a wide variety of contexts. Similarly, hierarchical and network governance being the most common governance approaches was also relatively consistent across the different nexus challenges. However, the specific context and actors involved in each nexus problem is likely to be a key determinant of appropriate nexus solutions in any given situation. Importantly, there were few empirical assessments of either governance approaches or policy instruments in terms of their effectiveness in managing the nexus. This highlights the need for more research focusing on evaluation of effectiveness and comparisons across different response option configurations.

The review also identified a broad range of actors involved in the nexus, but IPLC tended to be underrepresented in the literature, despite their known roles in managing across nexus elements (further discussed in **section 4.5.2**). How these actors are involved in, and interact with, a specific nexus problem is likely to be key to determining appropriate response options; this is the focus of the subchapters of **Chapter 5** (see **Chapters 5.1.2, 5.2.2, 5.3.2, 5.4.2 and 5.5.2**).

Several factors were found to enhance or hinder attempts to govern the nexus and are important criteria to take into consideration when assessing the potential of

different options (see also **Chapter 5.6, section 5.6.5**). Strengthening the consideration of enablers and managing barriers is key to ensuring that the available response options will effectively address nexus challenges, and this is particularly important for their scaling (see **section 4.4**). The review also revealed that in addition to the five nexus elements (biodiversity, water, food, health and climate change), the literature on governance of response options also explicitly addressed multiple and diversified cross-cutting issues, with energy, poverty, equity and economic growth among the most salient and highly relevant to the broader SDGs. Fostering positive outcomes across all nexus elements while at the same time meeting other societal demands and needs is crucial for the design of sustainable and just transformations, requiring more research at the interface between science and policy to meet the 2030 Agenda.

Finally, better empirical monitoring and assessment is likely to be required in many cases to inform the design of nexus governance and policy responses as there was a lack of focus on this in the literature. Without this, adaptive learning and improved decisions for addressing the nexus challenges over time may fail to be realized (Pascual *et al.*, 2022). For example, in the Blue Nile region, uncertainties associated with climate change and inadequate meteorological and hydrological data interact with uncertainties about institutional responsibilities, which compromise institutional learning and adaptation (Pahl-Wostl *et al.*, 2021; Stein *et al.*, 2018).

The overall conclusions and implications of the systematic review include:

- There is limited empirical assessment of combinations of governance and policy options for the nexus, with most insights derived from theory or conceptual models, representing a key research gap. There were also only a limited number of studies at the local scale, another important research gap. Solutions to nexus financing challenges are also underrepresented and a priority for future knowledge generation.
- The governance and policy literature related to the nexus focuses on water and food predominantly with less knowledge about interactions with other elements of the nexus including biodiversity, health and climate change. The range of actors involved in the nexus is broad, but IPLC are underrepresented.
- Governance approaches for the nexus share many common characteristics, such as enhancing policy coordination and integration (e.g., network and hierarchical governance) as opposed to governance approaches that do not (e.g., market governance). This is likely to be important for achieving effective nexus

governance. Furthermore, broad governance and policy mixes do not appear to be associated strongly with specific nexus challenges. This means generalizable solutions may be possible, but the specific context and actors involved in each specific nexus problem will likely be key factors.

- Policy design and implementation as well as institutional capacity were the most common enablers and barriers of nexus challenges and so they are important criteria to take into consideration when assessing the potential of different response options and enabling their scaling (section 4.4).

4.4 SCALING RESPONSES FOR NEXUS TRANSFORMATIONS

4.4.1 Defining scaling

Scaling is important to achieve wider impacts, for options to be normalized in policymaking and governance at all levels (through, for example, the demonstration and enhancement of the evidence and knowledge base) and, in turn, to advance towards sustainability transformations (Hoff *et al.*, 2019). Such transformations need to overcome business-as-usual approaches including vested and short-term interests, path dependencies and other disincentives, thereby reforming and encouraging nexus thinking and

action (Hoff *et al.*, 2019). Expanding on individual and innovative response options, often in a pilot format or scale, can be helpful to challenge persistent siloed thinking and incumbent norms of working and demonstrate the benefits and added value of nexus approaches. Scaling can help successful or promising nexus response options that operate at a given scale to build up their impacts, facilitating integrated action on the SDGs, minimizing trade-offs and further enabling synergies across sectors and scales (Box 4.3). Through scaling processes, the nexus evidence and knowledge base could be further strengthened, to promote the wider and faster adoption of nexus response options.

Although the importance, potential and benefits of response options for promoting a more just and sustainable future have been widely acknowledged, their uptake and operationalization in practice are still slow and limited (Hoff *et al.*, 2019). There is thus significant scope for the scaling of response options in both policy and practice. Since it is important to consider the implications of specific innovations, policies or case studies for scaling, or processes through which scaling nexus response options may occur, this section describes cases worldwide and across different scales and sectors to show how different types of scaling works in practice. The term scaling in this section thus recognizes the potential of accelerating, replicating and/or spreading response options to quantitatively accumulate impacts and promote wider adoption and diffusion, while emphasizing that through scaling, a qualitative shift towards more fundamental and

Box 4.3 Scale versus scaling.

Decision-making within the context of the nexus necessitates a nuanced understanding of scale and scaling, diverging from traditional concepts by employing various scales for effective problem resolution (Hoff, 2018a). “Scale” conventionally denotes the static size or extent of a system (Cash *et al.*, 2006) while “scaling” is dynamic, entailing adjustments in system size or scope, including expansion, contraction, replication or adaptation to new contexts (IIRR, 2000). **Section 4.4** introduces “scaling up” (expanding impact), “scaling down” (focusing on localized contexts), “scaling out” (replicating or spreading across contexts), and “scaling deep” (achieving profound systemic changes), each addressing the interconnectedness of biodiversity, water, food, health and climate change. These processes navigate different levels within a continuum, affecting temporal and spatial dimensions, where “scaling up” extends impacts from local to broader scales, and “scaling down” focuses on efforts at local or community levels (Padt *et al.*, 2014).

Cash *et al.* (2006) highlight the importance of scale for effective governance, such as nested jurisdictional levels and decision-making rules (institutional scale) affected by spatial (fields to

landscape and ecosystem) and temporal (short to long term) factors (Termeer & Dewulf, 2014). Governance scales can reflect hierarchies – national to municipal – whereas institutional scales impact temporal considerations; constitutions endure, policies evolve biennially, and operational rules may frequently change (Wiegant *et al.*, 2020). Effective nexus governance, inherently adaptive, multi-dimensional and inter-sectoral, must garner wide-ranging consensus and tackle social inequality, and thus is acutely tied to scale.

Scales are interconnected and interwoven, influencing and being influenced by scaling activities that extend the reach, integration and impact of initiatives across varying dimensions (O’Brien *et al.*, 2023). The process of scaling can affect these scales and levels by broadening the influence of interventions to encompass more individuals, span diverse governance levels, cover larger ecological expanses and incorporate different time frames. Realizing such expansion necessitates meticulous planning, coordination and flexibility to tailor scaling endeavours to the specific needs and situations of target communities, aiming for enduring benefits (O’Brien *et al.*, 2023).

transformational changes can also be achieved (Augenstein *et al.*, 2020; Nardi, 2022).

Four types of scaling are discussed in this section: first, institutionalizing nexus response options at the level of policy, rules and laws (**scaling up**); second, replicating and/or transferring response options to new places or geographies with similar contexts (**scaling out**); third, provincializing or localizing innovative nexus response options on the ground that are well adapted to local contexts (**scaling down**); and fourth, changing relationships, world views, mindsets or beliefs and cultural values that shape institutions and contexts as well as response options (**scaling deep**) (Figure 4.14). Despite their distinctiveness, the four options for scaling are not mutually exclusive; rather, they exhibit interdependencies. For instance, the core concept of scaling down, which is related to contextualization, can co-occur within the processes of both scaling out and scaling up. Additionally, scaling down, scaling up and scaling out are all part of an ongoing process of adapting and evolving world views,

beliefs, values and mindsets, referred to as scaling deep. Each of these types of scaling and the evidence for their implementation are reviewed in this section.

4.4.1.1 Scaling up

Scaling up, often termed as upscaling, usually refers to institutional structural change, impacting law, policy and institutions that generally direct societal responses. Moore *et al.* (2015) define it as impacting “higher levels of institutions through policy change”, which can be achieved through policy adjustments, new policy development, partnerships and advocacy. Hermans *et al.* (2016) describe scaling up as institutionalizing of innovation and a shift in the institutional logics of the incumbent regime. This involves identifying opportunities and barriers within institutional structures to effectively introduce innovation. During this process, actors play a crucial role, employing strategies like technology refinement, intermediary activities, advocacy, lobbying, mobilizing influential supporters and introducing alternative perspectives (Hermans *et al.*, 2016). Despite different

Box 4.4 **Scaling up: Large scale forest conservation with Indigenous Peoples in the highly threatened southeastern Amazon of Brazil.**

Over the last 40 years, the Kayapo Indigenous People have defended their land rights amid the expanding frontier of settlement and resource extraction in Brazil's southern Amazon, a region facing significant environmental threats. Their relentless efforts have successfully halted deforestation, safeguarding over 9 million hectares of their ancestral lands. This remarkable achievement was made possible through the strategic collaboration started in 1992 by the leaders of the Kayapo village of A'Ukre with the NGO Conservation International aimed to build alternative development vision for the community based on sustainable resource management and forest conservation.

The success of the collaboration to ensure economic autonomy and territorial control for the community garnered interest from other Kayapo villages which adopted the same approach. By 2001, a consensus was reached among the Kayapo to establish their own local NGO, Instituto Raoni, representing most of the Kayapo territory, which provided an opportunity for Kayapo leaders to reinforce traditional bonds and unite under a single vision for

the future. By 2006, most Kayapo leaders chose to ally with the NGO and reject illegal activity and predatory resource exploitation on their land. As a result, the legally recognized Indian reserves in Brazilian Amazonia now span over 100 million hectares, with the Kayapo initiative setting a precedent in conservation efforts.

This case study exemplifies the scaling up of institutional level responses through collaborative coalitions that supported large scale forest protection. It also illustrates how targeted conservation and development investment can empower Indigenous groups, ensuring the preservation of their territories and cultural heritage in areas plagued by deforestation and governance challenges. Factors of success included equitable benefits sharing, culturally appropriate income generation, support for Indigenous NGOs and long-term conservation policies. It highlights a transformative pathway for engaging with other Indigenous communities, ensuring their empowerment and the sustainable management of their territories.

Source: Zimmerman *et al.* (2020).

interpretations, scaling up is generally understood as vertical scaling to reach higher institutional levels, changing rules and bringing fundamental changes in the dominant way societal challenges are addressed. Scaling up response options thus can be understood as the institutionalization of nexus approaches at different levels, requiring political commitment, capacity development and the establishment of collaborative governance structures involving key stakeholders (UNESCO, 2021) (see **Box 4.4**).

One example of scaling up is the One Health approach in post-COVID global health governance as the interest in the linkages between nature and human health has dramatically increased. One Health, rooted in an interdisciplinary collaboration between veterinarians and international agencies to control zoonoses, is now seen as an appropriate approach to challenges such as the COVID-19 pandemic (IPBES, 2020). Global networks have scaled up these concerns such that governments are considering integrating the One Health approach in policies and frameworks including national biodiversity strategies and action plans alongside national health plans (CBD, 2018). The One Health approach can be also scaled down within specific projects.

4.4.1.2 Scaling out

Scaling out, also known as horizontal scaling, involves increasing the uptake of nexus approaches across various contexts to benefit greater numbers of people, aligning with the widespread perception of 'scaling' (Pachico & Fujisaka, 2004). It involves both replicating promising

nexus response options in another geographic or thematic context (UNESCO, 2021), extending innovations to serve large or new categories of populations (Do, 2019), or transferring and/or spreading key principles of successful innovations while adapting them to new contexts through, for example, knowledge co-generation and social mobilization through education (Moore *et al.*, 2015). The implementation of scaling out relies on the existence of political will and feasibility in each context and may have implications and consequences depending on existing situations (**Box 4.5**).

4.4.1.3 Scaling down

Scaling down, often used interchangeably as downscaling, primarily emphasizes the vertical devolution of responsibility and accountability from higher-level institutions and actors to lower levels to support and improve the local policy and decision-making process (M. G. Reed & Bruyneel, 2010). By devolving authority to the local level, scaling down recognizes and respects the local capacity to identify and address specific challenges and opportunities at the local level (Barakat & Kapisazovic, 2003; Lawford, 2019). Furthermore, scaling down is closely intertwined with geographical scale, emphasizing the materialization and localization of response options from larger scales (e.g., international or national) to the local level (also referred to as down-zoning) (Lampinen *et al.*, 2019; Taylor *et al.*, 2013), including down to the household level (Itayi *et al.*, 2021). It also underscores the importance of downsizing and tailoring broad response options or criteria to better align with the local context (J. Liu, Hull, *et al.*, 2018) (see **Box 4.6**).

Box 4.5 **Adoption of technologies by regional member countries from the Knowledge Park of the International Centre for Integrated Mountain Development.**

The ICIMOD Knowledge Park provides initial capacity building training on various technologies and livelihood options based on its member country demands, which are then further scaled out by local NGOs and partners for commercial productions. For example, ICIMOD provided kiwi seedlings and technical and crop management training on kiwi orchard establishment and management through local NGOs and partners, such as in Bhutan through the Bhutan Chamber of Commerce and Industry, in Pakistan through the Pakistan Agricultural Research Centre, and within Nepal where now these activities have been replicated as a source of income generation for 1400 farmers in 35 villages. In addition, inter-cropping techniques of kiwi with tea and other

perennial crops have been spread, which provide additional income to farmers and also addressed unemployment.

This case study exemplifies transboundary scaling out by replicating, spreading and transferring technology and practice-based responses through collaborative efforts. The same type of scaling out has been used by ICIMOD for bio-briquette technology, water harvesting, Shitake mushroom cultivation and sloping agricultural land technology adoption, replication and transfer in Afghanistan, Bangladesh, Myanmar, Pakistan, India and within Nepal.

Source: ICIMOD (2019).

Box 4.6 **Scaling down: Tailoring environmental management to local needs with the Community Development and Knowledge Management for the Satoyama Initiative.**

The Community Development and Knowledge Management for the Satoyama Initiative (COMDEKS) Programme illustrates a successful model for “scaling down” environmental and developmental interventions to address local conditions effectively. Focusing on specific regions such as the Bogo region in Cameroon, the Datça-Bozburun Peninsula in Turkey and the Laborec-Uh region in Slovakia, COMDEKS empowers local communities by providing small-scale finance to community organizations. This support fosters biodiversity and ecosystem management tailored to each area’s unique environmental and socioeconomic challenges.

In Cameroon, the programme targets the Sahelian zone of the Lake Chad Basin and the Mandara Mountains’ foothills,

supporting initiatives that harmonize with the arid climate and pastoral livelihoods. In Turkey, efforts focus on the coastal landscapes of the Datça-Bozburun Peninsula, where conservation works alongside sustainable tourism and fishing practices. In Slovakia, the initiative embraces the wetlands and agricultural lands of the Eastern Slovakia Lowland, promoting practices that benefit both biodiversity and agriculture. This approach highlights the importance of localizing conservation efforts to enhance their effectiveness and sustainability. By customizing strategies to fit the ecological and cultural contexts of each region, COMDEKS not only contributes to ecological resilience but also supports sustainable livelihoods, ensuring that conservation benefits are felt directly by the communities involved (Satoyama Initiative, 2017a, 2017b, 2017c).

4.4.1.4 Scaling deep

By focusing on the underlying causes of how problems are created (such as the indirect drivers of biodiversity loss) and how responses are shaped, scaling deep (or deep scaling) changes ways of thinking about problems and solutions. This often involves the work of innovative and/or pilot initiatives that foster new mindsets, change perceptions and world views, and introduce new ways of relating and knowing as well as new value systems (Lam *et al.*, 2020; Moore *et al.*, 2015). Scaling deep, as emphasized by Moore *et al.* (2015), acknowledges the powerful role of culture in reshaping problem domains, and underscores the need for change deeply rooted in individuals, relationships, communities and cultures. Scaling deep is directly associated with identifying and assessing underlying assumptions and values in how one thinks and acts in their day-to-day practices (Sterling, 2011). Scaling deep generally consists of two strategies: (1) disseminating significant cultural concepts and reshaping narratives to alter beliefs

and norms through knowledge sharing and new practices via participatory approaches and learning communities and platforms; and (2) “investing in transformative learning, networks and communities of practice” (Moore *et al.*, 2015). Successful or promising response options that are scaled deep to change people’s values, norms and beliefs can thus be an important component of transformative change.

Scaling deep places a greater emphasis on a longer-term process due to its involvement in altering sociocultural roots. This structural change resembles a “seeding” process focusing on long-term efficacy rather than short-term efficiency, as it does not offer individual solutions but instead initiates changes within the regime, making it more effective for future solutions to emerge or be adopted (Constantino *et al.*, 2022) (Box 4.7). For example, understanding the sociocultural factors that influence the tendency of local communities in Uganda to use wood fuel instead of clean energy would enable a tailored approach for local energy transition (UNDP, 2020).

Box 4.7 Inclusive climate-resilient water, sanitation and hygiene in Vanuatu.

77% of Vanuatu's total population of around 319,000, lives in rural areas, 64% within 1km of a coastline and 99% within 10km of a coastline, making the population extremely vulnerable to the cascading effects of climate change on the oceans and to saltwater intrusion of freshwater sources. Two-thirds of all households have unreliable water access, and half the population only have access to basic sanitation. Community and household structures and cultural practices in Vanuatu can result in higher vulnerability among some groups, particularly women, children and people with disabilities, which often prevents them seeking or accessing safe shelter during disasters (Morrison *et al.*, 2020).

Water for Women partnered with World Vision and local partners to deliver inclusive climate-resilient water, sanitation and hygiene (WASH) in Vanuatu to reach over 22,000 people vulnerable to impacts on water, sanitation and hygiene from climate change living in Vanuatu's two northernmost provinces of Sanma and Torba. The project supports community WASH

committees to model and upgrade existing infrastructure to be climate-resilient and able to withstand the increasing extreme weather events, while also incorporating the bespoke needs of the most vulnerable and at-risk groups. Improved gender equality and social inclusion in climate-resilient planning and service delivery within communities and local institutions has occurred, with women, people with disabilities and people from sexual and gender minority communities contributing to climate-resilient inclusive WASH discussions, policy, planning and service delivery. Working closely with community leaders and engaging them in dialogue about equity and inclusion as well as amplifying the voices of people with lived experience proved to be key to influencing others' perceptions and attitudes on equity and inclusion and shifting mindsets.

This example shows that by focusing on the underlying causes of a problem and how responses are shaped, scaling deep can change ways of thinking and foster new mindsets.

Source: Water for Women (2023).

4.4.2 Enabling the scaling of response options for the nexus

Effectively scaling the impact and the magnitude of response options is dependent on identifying the *factors* and *mechanisms* that either can enable or inhibit implementation. The scaling of response options largely depends on enablers, such as better considerations of equity and justice and inclusion of ILK and IPLC concerns, which can itself further enable multifunctional actions and outcomes and benefit a diversity of actors. In turn, scaling of response options can promote actions towards transformative change, which occurs when the development and implementation of sustainability initiatives and changes in structure, process and mindsets lead to a broader systemic impact (Lam *et al.*, 2020).

The successful scaling of nexus response options presents significant challenges (Bouman, 2017). Factors and enabling mechanisms that have been identified in the literature to overcome the challenges of scaling up/out/down/deep can be broadly categorized into political, practical and personal dimensions. These factors critically influence the effectiveness and expansion of response options, underscoring the complexities of their implementation across diverse contexts.

Political Factors:

- **Political will, awareness and capacity:** Bouman (2017) and UNESCO (2021) underscore the significance of strong political will, heightened awareness among stakeholders and the capacity to implement and sustain response options.

- **Governance:** FAO (2022) identifies governance-related challenges, such as lack of policy coherence, weak institutional coordination and disparities in stakeholder power and politics, as significant barriers to scaling nexus response options. These can be overcome by building analytical, bridging, negotiation, social networking and motivational capacities (see **section 4.5.5**), which can promote coherence, collaboration, and equitable stakeholder engagement.

Practical Factors:

- **Timing:** UNESCO (2021) stresses the importance of considering the scaling of nexus responses from their inception. Early integration of scaling objectives ensures that response options are designed with a vision for broader impact, facilitating smoother transitions from pilot to larger-scale implementations.
- **Resources:** The availability of resources, including financial and human resources, is a crucial determinant of the scalability of response options (Bouman, 2017; UNESCO, 2021). Adequate resourcing ensures the necessary support for expansion and can overcome operational challenges.
- **Social and cultural sensitivity:** Bouman (2017) identifies the importance of social and cultural sensitivity in the scaling process. Understanding and respecting local contexts and values is fundamental for ensuring the acceptability and sustainability of response options within communities, and this is especially crucial for

scaling down when tailoring broad response options to specific local contexts.

- ▶ **Knowledge exchange and learning:** Continuous knowledge exchange and learning processes are vital for the scaling of response options (Cole & Hagen, 2023; UNESCO, 2021). These processes facilitate the adaptation of response options to meet changing conditions and needs, drawing on both successes and challenges experienced.

Personal Factors:

- ▶ **Knowledge and awareness:** Cole and Hagen (2023) highlight the role of mental models in shaping perceptions and approaches to response options. Transforming these models is essential for fostering a holistic understanding of nexus challenges and response options among stakeholders, thereby enhancing collaborative efforts and innovative thinking.

These key political, practical and personal factors are fundamentally rooted in sociopolitical and economic systems. Insights from literature on scaling sustainable innovations highlight the following three promising *enabling mechanisms* for promoting scaling, including overcoming power imbalances; integrating financial mechanisms with institutional and policy reform; and fostering inclusive knowledge systems and enhancing collaborations.

Overcoming power imbalances

Power disparities between various actors and institutions, often rooted in the ownership structures of incumbent systems (e.g., assets, infrastructure and land), can restrict the scaling of response options. The complexity in navigating these imbalances is exacerbated by the multiplicity of institutions and the diversity of legal environments in which any nexus policymaking process takes place. Addressing these power imbalances – through stakeholder engagement, fostering dialogue, enhancing participation and distributing decision-making – can lay a foundational basis for effectively scaling response options. However, the diversity of institutional and sectoral contexts across countries and scales indicates that there is no universal solution to these challenges. Different governance models (e.g., hierarchical vs. community) and dynamics significantly influence the ability to formulate and scale response options (Averchenkova *et al.*, 2016). Resistance to legal, policy and regulatory changes that challenge established systems and power structures further complicates scaling efforts (Larkin *et al.*, 2020).

Promising approaches to overcoming these challenges include integration and innovation across scales, forming supportive coalitions, adopting equitable strategies and building social tipping points (Pascual *et al.*, 2022). While

empirical examples are limited, there is potential for developing institutional capacities for negotiating, designing and implementing governance arrangements. Such efforts facilitate coordinated, multi-level governance systems conducive to nexus approaches, as evidenced by initiatives in the bioenergy sector in Brazil and the integration of global governance frameworks like the SDGs into subnational policymaking (Lazaro *et al.*, 2021; Pahl-Wostl, 2019).

In summary, overcoming power imbalances through inclusive and innovative governance practices is crucial for the scaling of response options, requiring tailored approaches that consider unique institutional and sectoral contexts.

Integrating financial mechanisms with institutional and policy reform

Securing robust financial incentives and support, in tandem with the strategic redesign of institutions and policies, forms a comprehensive approach for effectively scaling nexus approaches and just transitions. This dual strategy addresses the intertwined challenges of sectoral silos and poor collaboration, inertia and path-dependency, and inadequate stakeholder integration as highlighted in the literature as significant barriers to scaling (Hoff *et al.*, 2019). Innovative financial mechanisms such as public-private partnerships, green bonds, dedicated nexus funds and targeted tax incentives play a pivotal role in mobilizing resources and engaging a wide array of actors (Clark *et al.*, 2018). Governments, international organizations and private investors can contribute to nexus-oriented funds, while governments can use tax incentives to stimulate investments in projects to support positive benefits to nexus elements. The private sector is key in unlocking new financing sources and attracting additional investors through certification networks (Prakash & Sethi, 2022; A. K. Tiwari, 2022). (see **Chapter 6, section 6.2**).

In parallel, redesigning institutions and policies is essential, especially in contexts lacking policy coordination, as evidenced in the food-energy-water nexus in Brazil (Mercurio *et al.*, 2019) and the solar energy and energy efficiency sectors in India (Rattani, 2018). Establishing intermediary organizations seems to be an appropriate pathway for enhancing intersectoral and integrated planning and policymaking across levels (Hoff *et al.*, 2019), supported by institutional interplay and co-management strategies (Cash *et al.*, 2006). Such redesign not only aims at addressing power imbalances but also at modifying the framework within which policies and institutions operate, thus facilitating broader and deeper scaling of nexus response options.

Fostering inclusive knowledge systems and enhancing collaborations

Promoting the scaling of response options fundamentally requires fostering inclusive knowledge systems and

enhancing collaborations. This effort encompasses not only improving the exchange and coordination within and across knowledge and innovation systems but also actively involving a diverse array of stakeholders in decision-making processes, with a particular focus on groups such as IPLC (Bream McIntosh *et al.*, 2023; Thornton, T.F. & Bhagwat, S., 2021). Given the intrinsic characteristics of governance, institutions and the nexus concept itself, scaling efforts must inherently integrate a variety of knowledge and innovation systems, bridging policy, ILK and scientific insights. Where disparities exist among these systems, bolstering collaboration is essential and often contingent on overcoming power imbalances and reconfiguring institutions and policies (Körner, J. *et al.*, 2021; Muhl *et al.*, 2023).

Furthermore, enhancing coordination both within and between knowledge and innovation systems can act as a lever for addressing other scaling factors, offering a pathway to upscale locally identified nexus response options through engagements with IPLC and ILK, contingent on the adaptability of larger institutions (Martin *et al.*, 2022). In configurations where bridging the gap between these systems clashes with entrenched cultural beliefs or economic interests, deep scaling becomes imperative to challenge and transform these prevailing norms, fostering sustainable change (Peddi *et al.*, 2023).

Among the various scaling types, scaling deep presents the greatest challenge, requiring cross-scalar collaboration among key stakeholders to facilitate social learning and innovation. This collaboration aims to dismantle silos and bridge the gap between knowledge holders and those in greatest need, sharing best practices within academic circles and extending them into nexus partnerships (Flammini *et al.*, 2014). Networks like The International Partnership for the Satoyama Initiative exemplify how multi-level collaborations can offer locally relevant solutions across different ecosystems and scales, fostering knowledge sharing within the network to enhance integration with science and policymaking (Kozar *et al.*, 2019). Additionally, confronting equity issues in knowledge creation and integrating diverse insights across scales pose further challenges in scaling efforts, necessitating a concerted focus on inclusivity and cross-sectoral engagement (Westermann *et al.*, 2018).

Developing robust data and modelling tools is a critical component of fostering inclusive knowledge systems and enhancing collaborations. By gathering comprehensive data and integrating multi-sectoral information, these tools empower stakeholders to effectively identify synergies and trade-offs (see **section 4.6**). The lack of empirical evidence and the subsequent knowledge gap in nexus governance can be addressed through these integrated knowledge systems. This approach supports the establishment of a shared understanding and collaborative efforts among diverse stakeholders, including decision makers, by making

accessible, comparable data and meta-data a cornerstone of effective nexus implementation and scaling. It highlights the importance of co-designing these tools with decision makers to ensure they meet the practical needs of planning and decision-making, thereby overcoming one of the significant barriers to nexus implementation (Lawford, 2019).

4.5 TOWARDS A VISION FOR IMPROVED NEXUS GOVERNANCE

As previous sections have noted (**sections 4.2.3, 4.3.2, 4.3.3**), an existing focus on policy coherence and integrated policymaking is unlikely to be sufficient to achieve positive outcomes for people and nature across the nexus and to accelerate transitions towards just and sustainable futures. Many existing policy and sociopolitical options in practice catalyse only incremental changes for nexus elements. Yet there is strong evidence that governance mechanisms and policy processes that are deliberately co-designed, co-implemented and co-managed, and that recognize enablers and barriers for change, can better account for and address nexus challenges, especially those relating to complexity, values and governance (**section 4.3.3**).

This section thus builds up evidence to address gaps identified previously, including the lack of a common definition for nexus governance (**section 4.2.3**); gaps around enablers and barriers to governing across the nexus (**sections 4.2.5 and 4.3.5**); gaps in the literature around actors (**section 4.2.6**) and how power differentials can be overcome; gaps around attention to the role of IPLC in governing across the nexus (**section 4.3.4**) and how acknowledgement of their role and ILK can strengthening inclusivity of nexus outcomes; gaps in attention to equity and justice, including how an intersectionality lens can specifically spotlight asymmetrical benefits and burdens of nexus outcomes; and gaps in linkages to transformative change (**section 4.2.3**). In considering and addressing each of these gaps, this section concludes with a consolidated and comprehensive definition of nexus governance that includes a description of the components of nexus governance most associated with successful implementation of a nexus approach.

4.5.1 Actors, institutions and arenas of engagement

Actors interact in a multitude of decision-making contexts, also called “arenas of engagement”, which describes the many different settings, places, spaces and contexts

within which governance actors interact to shape nexus approaches and initiatives (Schipper *et al.*, 2022).⁴ These governance interactions are not confined to political or policy domains but rather occur in diverse arenas, such as sociocultural and ecological; economic and financial; knowledge, science and technological and political and government arenas (Table 4.7). Arenas of engagement span from the local to global scale, through diverse forums and settings, and do not exist in isolation (Schipper *et al.*, 2022). Therefore, some problems and responses spread from one arena to another, necessitating an attention to scaling, while others remain confined to particular arenas.

In this chapter, attention to arenas of engagement spotlights the interactions between governance actors, their aims, and the arenas in which they interact (Hofer & Kaufmann, 2023), recognizing that these interactions and settings are historically situated. For example, governance interactions between colonizing governments and Indigenous Peoples are fraught even in post-colonial settings (Loong *et al.*, 2023). Societal choices made in arenas of engagement shape different policy and sociopolitical response options, actions and systems (see also Chapter 6, section 6.3). Politics and power invariably shape the interactions between governance actors in their arenas of engagement, with actors sometimes being highly powerful in one arena, but also being potentially powerless in another. Governance decisions within arenas of engagement often centre on a specific contestation, challenge or opportunity around a specific topic (see Table 4.7 for illustrative examples) and interactions reflect varying levels of inclusion and exclusion in decision-making spaces, as well as uneven power relations.

This argues for attention to the spaces, formats, and types of participation that take place within arenas (Felt, 2016; Hofer & Kaufmann, 2023).

Spaces are not only physical sites of engagement, but they are also socially constructed sites that reflect history and spatial features and can include more institutionalized and formalized practices or those that are informal and *ad hoc*, and can serve as popular spaces that are more likely to be counter-hegemonic and even insurgent (Cornwall, 2004; Gaventa, 2006; Lefebvre, 1991).⁵ These spaces can also be interconnected, with diffusion between participatory spaces (Miraftab, 2020) and formal spaces can also transform in novel ways through practices that challenge the status quo and articulate a counter-narrative (Hilbrandt, 2017).

Engagement in these arenas takes place in different formats – from public hearings and meetings (Walker *et al.*, 2006; Wiebe, 2019) to deliberative fora (Dore & Lebel, 2010; Muro & Jeffrey, 2012; Parkins & Mitchell, 2005) to community interactions (Cumming *et al.*, 2022; Head, 2007; Vaughan, 2014) and online engagements (Hestres, 2015; Pettit & Nelson, 2004; Segerberg, 2017). Core lessons learned are to tailor engagement approaches to the needs of the people one is engaging (Ojha *et al.*, 2016). For instance, some engagements are one-off encounters whereas others are long-term or ongoing processes (Furman *et al.*, 2018; Stratoudakis *et al.*, 2019). While enduring forms of engagement are less common, there are nonetheless a wide variety of ways for engagement to manifest in different arenas of engagement (Nabatchi & Leighninger, 2015) (Table 4.7).

4. The 'arenas' metaphor can be traced to a range of social and political theory scholarship (Healy, 2005; Hilgartner & Bosk, 1988), with varied emphasis from engagement to decision, policy, public and political arenas; arenas of development (M. S. Jørgensen *et al.*, 2017; U. Jørgensen, 2012) and localities and cities as arenas (Acedo *et al.*, 2019).

5. Gaventa (2006, 2019, 2021) also distinguishes invited spaces; claimed or created spaces; and closed spaces of participation. Power is central to his work, and he uses the metaphor of a 'cube' to depict the intersection of these spaces and different forms of power (visible, hidden, visible) across scales from the local to global level.

Table 4.7 Overview and illustrative examples of different arenas of engagement relevant to policy and sociopolitical options for nexus governance.

Arena of engagement	Description	Examples of contestations within arenas	Policy and sociopolitical options
Economic and financial arenas	Examples can include local markets for forest products or locations for international finance. Can be temporary or enduring in nature, with interaction spanning local to global scales (Schipper <i>et al.</i> , 2022)	Growth-based economies Ecological limits to growth Perverse incentives Not accounting for externalities of extractive industries	Monetary and fiscal policies, carbon pricing, taxes and subsidies (Schipper <i>et al.</i> , 2022) Green GDP (Boyd, 2007; Talberth & Bohara, 2006) or Blue Growth (Eikeset <i>et al.</i> , 2018) Alternatives to growth paradigms (e.g., well-being economy (Fioramonti <i>et al.</i> , 2022) or Donut Economics (Raworth, 2017)) System of Environmental Economic Accounting (Pirmana <i>et al.</i> , 2019), Natural Capital Accounting (Hein <i>et al.</i> , 2016; Wackernagel <i>et al.</i> , 1999) Degrowth (Kallis, 2011)

Table 4 7

Arena of engagement	Description	Examples of contestations within arenas	Policy and sociopolitical options
Sociocultural and ecological arenas	Local, place-based social-ecological sites where people meet to make decisions (Eriksen <i>et al.</i> , 2006)	Discrimination/ oppression or exclusion based on social differentiation Exclusion or removal of land rights or access to natural resources	Rights-based approaches (Cottrell, 2022; Franks, 2021; Jodoin <i>et al.</i> , 2021; Tauli, 2022; Tauli-Corpus <i>et al.</i> , 2020). Community or co-management arrangements (Muok <i>et al.</i> , 2021) Improving social connections, acknowledging anxiety, reconnecting to nature and finding creative ways to re-engage (Clayton <i>et al.</i> , 2017; Lertzman, 2010).
Knowledge –technology arenas	Exchange of ideas inside knowledge spaces that are associated with technological advancements and relate to the framework of institutions and politics that govern the flow of information and technology (Schipper <i>et al.</i> , 2022)	Varying capacities of actors to obtain and employ diverse forms of information to make decisions Dis/mis-information	Knowledge brokering, knowledge production, transdisciplinary research (Bielak <i>et al.</i> , 2008; Elliott, 2011; Ghodsvali <i>et al.</i> , 2022; Turnhout <i>et al.</i> , 2013) Social-ecological (Folke, 2006) and sociotechnical (Wesselink <i>et al.</i> , 2020) systems framing Science, technology and innovation policies (Fazey <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Schipper <i>et al.</i> , 2022) Artificial intelligence (Wang <i>et al.</i> , 2023) Media literacy (Logan <i>et al.</i> , 2021)
Political and governmental arenas	Can include government buildings, offices of private and public sector actors, universities, community halls and streets, as well as discursive spaces where actors involved in governance deliberations and negotiations from community to international levels (Schipper <i>et al.</i> , 2022).	Political arenas can be used to shut down option spaces for catalyzing change Power asymmetries among actors create opportunities for inclusion/exclusion in decision-making processes Misinformation and lobbying Rising social inertia for action Rise in populism and political conservatism	Collective action, which can include pacific protest and dissent (Bjork-James <i>et al.</i> , 2022; Mar <i>et al.</i> , 2023; Buzogány & Mohamad-Klotzbach, 2021) Social movements and litigation (Parth <i>et al.</i> , 2020) Policy coherence and mainstreaming (Bizikova <i>et al.</i> , 2018; Fürst <i>et al.</i> , 2017) Climate action (Brulle & Norgaard, 2019)

4.5.1.1 Actors, influence and power asymmetries

Underpinning many interactions in arenas of engagement are world views and values. World views according to the IPBES Methodological Assessment on the Diverse Values and Valuation of Nature (Values Assessment) (IPBES, 2022a) are mental lenses through which human social groups perceive, think about, interpret, inhabit and modify the world. They are rooted in cultural traditions, and they shape and are shaped by knowledge systems, languages and values. Thus, world views can shape multiple decision-making outcomes (Harmáčková *et al.*, 2023; Pascual *et al.*, 2023). They can inform the vision, beliefs, attitudes, values, emotions, actions and associated political and institutional arrangements and as such, can promote holistic, egalitarian and relational approaches to facilitate and scale transitions towards justice and sustainability (Chuang *et al.*, 2020; Singh & Chudasama,

2021). While these normative ideals are enshrined in many of the global policy frameworks and agreements, and feature strongly in many Indigenous and local governance arrangements (Cariño & Ferrari, 2021; Hill *et al.*, 2020; Locatelli *et al.*, 2022), the dominant world views currently underpinning many decision-making processes promote anthropocentric, mechanistic and materialistic decisions and associated utilitarian, individualistic and sceptical values and attitudes (Harmáčková *et al.*, 2023; Pascual *et al.*, 2023).

Some arenas therefore open up opportunities for inclusive and enabling interactions between governance actors. Other arenas close down such opportunities and privilege those with power and influence. In such cases, contestation is inevitable and pervasive given the associated array of values, needs and interests, and transformative change can be catalyzed through social mobilization, protest and dissent (della Porta, 2020). Alternatives to the more conventional

Box 4.8 **The role of social movements for enhancing nexus governance.**

The failure of current political, economic, health and environmental policies to address climate change, pandemics, environmental degradation and biodiversity loss and food and water insecurity has resulted in growing social discontent. This comes after decades of limited government action and social inertia to lower the risk of anthropogenic changes that impact on interconnected challenges affecting nature and human well-being (Brulle & Norgaard, 2019; Carpenter *et al.*, 2019). A rise in social movements to catalyse change have been occurring, e.g., through climate change protests and civil disobedience (Corry & Reiner, 2021; Haugestad *et al.*, 2021; Svensson & Wahlström, 2023; Zhanda *et al.*, 2021), intersecting water security and Indigenous rights protests and advocacy linked to pipelines and infrastructure (Bosworth & Chua, 2023; Brisman *et al.*, 2020; Hunt & Gruszczynski, 2019; Lindstrom, 2020), advocacy and awareness around environmental conflicts and defenders (Menton & Billon, 2021; Scheidel *et al.*, 2020), food and farming protests through food sovereignty movements (Jernigan *et al.*, 2023), and concerns regarding access to affordable healthcare (Mahajan *et al.*, 2021; Tzenios, 2019). These protests have increased public awareness and offer opportunities for broadening business-as-usual by leveraging the concept of arenas of engagement

to highlight the need for collective action across sectors and scales of governance.

Youth-led movements are increasingly emerging and employing evidence-based advocacy to reject gradual changes (e.g., youth led climate litigation (Cameron & Weyman, 2022; Donger, 2022), university divestment campaigns (Grady-Benson & Sarathy, 2016) and advocacy for drastic measures to combat climate change that go beyond reducing emissions (Han & Ahn, 2020; Trott, 2021)). Youth activists on climate strikes in particular have demonstrated the emergence of young people as agents of change and the urgency of engaging them in climate change governance and policymaking at the global scale (Han & Ahn, 2020). Youth-led movements such as those mobilized through the Global Youth Biodiversity Network, YOUNGO the official youth constituency of the UNFCCC and Youth4Nature have facilitated a global consultation of over 1000 voices from 118 countries within 5 months to produce a Global Youth Position Statement on nature-based solutions (NbS Youth Position, 2021). This statement is underpinned by an integrated and inclusive approach to bringing climate and biodiversity concerns through a justice lens to ensure that the co-benefits of ecosystem-based approaches have positive inter- and intragenerational outcomes for people and nature.

arenas of engagement range from flower markets and cinemas to op-ed pages, community radio / TV stations, factories and universities. The societal choices made in these arenas of engagement (or disengagement) shape different policy and sociopolitical response options, actions and systems (see **Chapters 6 and 7**) and consequently options for development.

Many governance actors are transforming prevailing arenas of engagement into 'struggle arenas' in which available power and influence is leveraged to gain voice, set agendas and make and implement decisions to foster development trajectories based on a specific set of values. If, for example, formal political arenas of engagement such as voting and election procedures yield outcomes that perpetuate business- and politics-as-usual, those striving for specific desired development outcomes might resort to protest, civil disobedience and resistance. Consequently, public spaces, streets and town squares may become sites of political struggle. Alternatively, when the limits of private profit- and growth-oriented and GDP-focused economic interactions become apparent, alternative economic lifestyles and livelihoods are pursued, e.g., through alternative approaches to production, consumption and exchange. Examples of these alternatives include well-being, post-growth, and degrowth approaches to economies (Coscieme *et al.*, 2020; Fioramonti *et al.*, 2022; Knickel *et al.*, 2021) or doughnut economics (Raworth, 2017). New forms of collective action

and social movements can enhance nexus governance as highlighted in **Box 4.8**, which presents an example of how youth and social movements are contesting the status-quo regarding climate action by dominant actors. Within these new and potentially disruptive modes of collective political action, new forms of governance related to political responsibility and accountability are needed which could allow the elevation and inclusion of the voices of marginalized actors in meaningful ways, such as young people and IPLC who are often at the forefront of impacts from declines in nexus elements (**Chapter 2, section 2.5.4**).

4.5.2 Indigenous and local knowledge and nexus governance

Knowledge and practices of IPLC that govern the use of nature and relationships with food systems, water systems, well-being and spirituality are underpinned by world views and values that conceptualize these elements as an integrated whole. Mobilizing and including ILK through dialogue and knowledge co-production, as has been done for this assessment (see **Chapter 1, section 1.5.1**), is particularly important to understand policy and sociopolitical options (Cottrell, 2022; Hill *et al.*, 2020; Pascual *et al.*, 2023; Tengö *et al.*, 2017) to enhance nexus governance. A better understanding of plural values and ways of knowing can strengthen the identification, negotiation and exploration

Box 4.9 **Indigenous peoples and local communities' policy and sociopolitical options for farming systems.**⁶

Recognizing food system response strategies by Indigenous Peoples and local communities (IPLC) are key to solutions in the biodiversity-food-health-climate change nexus, which can be facilitated by different policy and sociopolitical options. For example, Kozar *et al.* (2019) reviewed a set of 88 place-based, social-ecological production landscapes and seascape case studies in Asia and identified 485 policy and sociopolitical options. These included economic and incentive-based; social, cultural and behavioural; technological; and cognitive and knowledge-based responses. IPLC in South Asia show a

preference for economic and incentive-based responses such as strengthening livelihood resilience or renewal, IPLC in Southeast Asia demonstrate a preference for knowledge and cognitive based responses, and IPLC in East Asia favour technological responses particularly as agroecological practices (Kozar *et al.*, 2020). Lahoti *et al.* (2023) looked at 90 bioproduction systems in Japan, Indonesia and the Philippines and found 384 response options, with IPLC preference for a relational value or "nature as culture"/"one with nature" perspective represented in the Nature Futures Framework⁷ (IPBES, 2023c).

of potential policy and sociopolitical options in ways that reduce trade-offs for those actors that continue to be marginalized in policy- and decision-making (McElwee *et al.*, 2020; Wheeler & Root-Bernstein, 2020).

The systematic review of governance and policy options for the nexus conducted for this chapter found that IPLC are often the least represented actor category (section 4.3.4; Figure 4.7), even though their ILK provides substantial benefits to the development, implementation and monitoring of policy and sociopolitical options across the nexus (Cottrell, 2022; Nishi *et al.*, 2022). Only a limited number of studies (e.g., Nishi *et al.* (2022)) explicitly investigate the role of ILK to identify, implement and evaluate nexus policy and sociopolitical options, indicating a major gap. To fill this gap, an additional non-systematic review of literature in English of peer-reviewed publications and grey literature was conducted, including inputs derived from the three Nexus Assessment ILK dialogue workshops (held in June 2022, January 2023 and November 2023).⁸ The literature reviewed included materials submitted during the IPBES Nexus Assessment call for contributions on ILK literature, and those identified by Nexus Assessment authors as of relevance to ILK (1091 total). Out of these, 35 resources were identified as those detailing IPLC governance or governance based on ILK across at least two elements of the nexus (see Box

4.9 for examples). These resources were then analysed to understand how they relate to the four IPBES classes of policy instruments (Table 4.4) and the seven IPBES policy support tools families (described in section 4.6).⁹

There are many advantages to ensuring that ILK is considered and woven into nexus governance, including better understanding of the values and spirituality underpinning nature's contribution to people and response options to access and use these (Boafo *et al.*, 2016; Ogawa *et al.*, 2021); enabling knowledge cross-fertilization and exchange (e.g., Satoyama Initiative: IPSI Secretariat, 2023); assessing and monitoring ecosystem change (Reyes *et al.*, 2020); assessing policy outcomes compatible with IPLC practices and livelihoods (Lahoti *et al.*, 2023); and examining ILK and IPLC contributions to global targets and commitments, e.g., SDGs and the targets of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework) (Balehgn, 2016; Bjork-James *et al.*, 2022). In particular, the Local Biodiversity Outlooks (Forest Peoples Programme, 2020; Forest Peoples Programme *et al.*, 2016) showcase the important contributions of ILPC towards meeting the objectives of the Convention on Biological Diversity.

Governance regimes led by IPLC have effectively prevented deforestation and forest degradation, often more successfully than other policy instrument types (e.g., protected areas) (Schleicher *et al.*, 2017; Sze *et al.*, 2022). Indigenous Community Conserved Areas (ICCAs) and Other Effective Conservation Measures (OECMs) on both land and sea are prominent examples of conservation based on IPLC governance systems that demonstrate the important role of ILK and IPLC in meeting biodiversity goals (Alves-Pinto *et al.*, 2021; Arijumend & Beaulieu-Boon, 2018; Corrigan

6. Common case study highlighting Indigenous Peoples' and local communities' (IPLC) food systems. See Chapters 1, 2, 3, 5.1 to 5.5 and 6 for additional IPLC food system case studies. Lessons learned from the common case studies are presented in Chapter 7, online Supplementary material 7.1.

7. The Nature Futures Framework (NFF) is a flexible tool to support the development of scenarios and models of desirable futures for people, nature and Mother Earth (IPBES/10/INF/13). The NFF presents three value perspectives of nature in a triangle. In the "nature for nature" perspective, people view nature as having intrinsic value, and value is placed on the diversity of species, habitats, ecosystems and processes that form the natural world, and on nature's ability to function autonomously. The "nature as culture/one with nature" perspective primarily highlights relational values of nature, where societies, cultures, traditions and faiths are intertwined with nature in shaping diverse biocultural landscapes. The "nature for society" perspective highlights the utilitarian benefits and instrumental values that nature provides to people and societies.

8. It should be noted that this literature review focusing on ILK and IPLC is not based on a systematic approach and was conducted separately from the systematic reviews in sections 4.3 and 4.6.

9. In terms of the policy instrument classification used in the review, unless a publication explicitly discussed human rights of IPLC, rights of Indigenous Peoples (to their lands, territories or resources) or rights of nature (e.g., "rights-based instruments"), the other policy instruments relating to IPLC governance were categorized as "social and cultural instruments". These include, for example, Indigenous Peoples' laws, traditions, customs and land tenure systems.

& Graziera, 2010; Gurney *et al.*, 2021; WWF *et al.*, 2021) in ways that consider linkages with other elements of the nexus (IPBES, 2022b, 2023a).

The review found that social and cultural instruments (80%, n=28) are the most common policy instruments in IPLC governance or governance based on ILK, followed by rights-based instruments (20%, n=7). This is in contrast to the findings of the systematic review of these policy instruments for the nexus (described in **section 4.3**) which found more examples of policy instruments linked to legal and regulatory/economic and financial policy instruments. Within the category of social and cultural instruments, sacred sites and landscapes and Indigenous or customary institutions that govern management of resources were the most common instruments noted in the literature that contribute to nexus governance. These consist of institutions such as customary rules, laws, norms and tenure systems based on community or spiritual leaders, world views and values that regulate relationships between people and nature, which in turn guide hunting, fishing or gathering of certain species and engender and reinforce respect for the environment. Examples of customary governance systems to manage the nexus were found among IPLC all around the world, and their effectiveness was emphasised by participants of the ILK dialogues who underlined the need for such governance systems to be recognized and supported to enable IPLC to manage their own lands and waters, while at the same time adapt to new challenges, such as climate change (IPBES, 2023b).

While examples of such customary governance systems that are officially recognized by national and regional governments are emerging (Halim *et al.*, 2020; Utama *et al.*, 2020; Walmsley, 2023; Yoder, 2021), the process through which such recognition is codified requires careful attention, as there is the danger that ILK that underlies such governance systems are rendered static or distorted (IPBES, 2023b). Customary governance systems underpinned by Indigenous perspectives and ILK are subject to multiple pressures including official government laws and institutions that are usually at odds with customary governance (IPBES, 2023b). Indigenous perspectives are often in direct contrast to the human-centric world view that are common in non-Indigenous governance approaches. Thus ILK-based policy instruments are often ill-suited for mixing with other types of instruments, especially if a top-down approach to integration occurs (Borrini-Feyerabend & Ironside, 2010; Gurney *et al.*, 2021; Kothari, A., Camill, P., & Brown, J., 2013).

Another challenge for nexus governance by IPLC and based on ILK concerns scalar mismatches between where a resource is directly used and managed by customary rights (e.g., by IPLC) and other regulatory requirements by national or regional authorities. This can result in clashes and inconsistencies between levels and conflicts between

different knowledge systems. Examples include distantly administered fisheries management regimes that may attempt to regulate local culturally important fisheries stocks (Turner *et al.*, 2013) or restrictions on resource use based on scientifically monitored indicators (e.g., population size) while local indicators might address different aspects (e.g., animal health) (Berkes *et al.*, 2001).

Rights-based instruments and economic and financial instruments were also documented as being used in IPLC governance systems or using ILK, often to complement social and cultural instruments. In terms of rights-based instruments, some IPLC have made official legal arrangements with governments that recognize their right to govern their own resources, such as in Oceania (Ban & Frid, 2018; Te Waihora Co-Governance Group, n.d.), Asia (Forest Peoples Programme, 2020; Halim *et al.*, 2020) and in North America (Forest Peoples Programme, 2020). In terms of economic and financial instruments, benefit-sharing agreements between IPLC and entities officially in charge of managing protected areas were the most commonly found instruments, which were documented in Africa (Endorois Welfare Council, 2019) and Asia (Forest Peoples Programme, 2020; Forest Peoples Programme *et al.*, 2016).

Most of the studies from the review mentioned the interlinkages between biodiversity and food as central to the relationship with other elements, with 80% (n=28) mentioning nature/biodiversity and food systems (see for example **Box 4.10**), while others also included water (34%, n=12). This contrasts with the findings on the nexus elements considered in the systematic review in **section 4.3** in which water played a more prominent role. Although only one publication explicitly mentioned all elements of the nexus, the majority of the literature included the use of customary institutions based on religious or spiritual leaders and world views, and thus indirectly addressed an important component of health.

The findings of the review of ILK-specific literature differed from those of a systematic review of tools for integrating cross-cutting issues for nexus governance (see **section 4.6.2**). Using the same seven IPBES policy tools families for categorization, a significant percentage of the ILK/IPLC literature assessed or used implementation, outreach and enforcement tools (85%, n=30), while 60% (n=21) also used public discussion, investment and participatory processes. Examples of rituals, taboos or sanctions based on ILK were documented in Asia (Daguitan & Martinez, 2022; Hiwasaki *et al.*, 2015; Shimray *et al.*, 2017) and Africa (Mburu, 2016; Wekesa *et al.*, 2021), while village institutions such as council of elders or collective agreements were used to enforce customary rules, regulations and laws concerning shared use of resources as well as cultural values of the community by IPLC in Africa (Balehegn *et al.*, 2019; Endorois Welfare Council, 2019; IPBES, 2023b), Asia (Basnet & Chaudhary, 2017; Forest Peoples Programme, 2020; Galappaththi *et*

Box 4 10 **Reviving and strengthening Indigenous food systems in the Philippines: The Lampisa system of the Pidlisan tribe.**⁶

The Pidlisan peoples' ancestral territory is located in the northern part of Sagada in Mountain Province, Philippines, and is governed by a customary land tenure system of collective ownership and stewardship known as *saguchay*. Rice production is combined in landscapes (known as *mapayew*) with other crops alongside habitat for other non-human species and during land preparation and maintenance of the paddy fields, sweet potatoes, taro and edible weeds are harvested, as are fish, snails, frogs and mole crickets to supplement diets. Traditional rituals and practices govern the preparation, transplanting and harvesting of rice, following seasonal calendars (known as *Dap-ay*) for labour allocation, soil fertility maintenance, pest control and land productivity, all of which are embedded in cultural values and Indigenous spirituality. In particular, a system of irrigation care and maintenance and egalitarian water distribution (known as *lampisa*) helps the community govern these landscapes. The term *lampisa* also refers to a water manager who conducts regular inspection and repairs of irrigation systems. The *lampisas* are appointed by the *chumap-ay* (council of elders) and everyone is expected to entrust the water distribution to them throughout the duration of the rice cropping period, especially after transplanting to make sure the planted seedlings have enough. For the performance of tasks, the *chumap-ay* set the policy that a *lampisa* shall receive 5% of the total harvest of each farmer beneficiary as payment for his services.

Up to the 1970s, rice production by the Pidlisan occurred with minimal external intervention, but since the 1990s, various factors including adoption of technologies, hybrid rice and agrochemicals; children moving out to pursue higher education; and tribal members engaging in tourism and mining have negatively affected the rice production ecosystem. Yields decreased and fields were neglected, and the farmers could no longer produce the fair remuneration of the *lampisa*, leading to a decline in appointment of *lampisas* in several communities

in the 2000s. The absence of *lampisas* further aggravated the situation, as the community faced the problem of lack of irrigation and more people stopped cultivating their fields.

In 2011, the Indigenous Peoples' International Centre for Policy Research and Education (TEBTEBBA), an NGO, responded to a request to assist the Pidlisan community. After assessing the situation of the ancestral domain and its people, the association worked together with the tribe to increase awareness through participatory action research and education, enhancing the community's capacity for livelihood development, promoting Indigenous People's education and increasing their capacity for resource mobilization. A major innovation involved combining traditional knowledge with modern science to produce organic farm inputs such as biofertilizers (foliar fertilizers, fermented plants and fruit juices) and harnessing native microorganisms to restore soil fertility. New budgets were also developed to re-hire *lampisas*. However, during this campaign, people realised that reviving the *lampisa* was not enough, as the years of neglect of the irrigation canal caused major damage that needed rehabilitation. Therefore, a holistic plan was proposed, and its implementation led to several outcomes, including a Pidlisan Tribal Declaration of Commitment to restore their rice landscape and revive associated values and culture. This led to the revival of certain practices and adoption of innovations that have increased rice yields up to 8.9 tons/ha with significant savings on seeds. This in turn was supported by a significant increase in the number of people interested to be part of this organic, sustainable and regenerative movement, which extended training on biofarm inputs to new areas. Abandoned paddy fields were reclaimed, and a feasibility study undertaken to rehabilitate irrigation canals used to lobby for support with the National Irrigation Authority.

Sources: (Daguitan & Martinez, 2022; Kreja Vei Casiw et al., 2023; Romeo et al., 2021).

al., 2020; B. K. Tiwari et al., 2017), the Pacific (Ban & Frid, 2018) and Latin America (Masardule, 2023). These were often monitored by community members themselves to ensure compliance (Daguitan, 2023; Halim et al., 2020). For example, many IPLC set community protocols and ensured participatory processes through consensus-building or collective decision-making based on active participation of community members (Daguitan, 2023; Forest Peoples Programme, 2020; Masardule, 2023), or by leaders elected by community members (Basnet & Chaudhary, 2017; Endorois Welfare Council, 2019; Shimray et al., 2017). While social learning—in particular, ILK passed down through generations—were also important tools that support governance of the different elements of the nexus (20%, n=9), they were not used as much as other tools, raising a significant challenge in terms of the ability of ILK-based instruments or tools to continue long-term governance of the nexus.

Overall, while many IPLC conceptualize elements of the nexus holistically, the concept of the nexus itself does not necessarily exist among IPLC (see also **Chapter 1, section 1.2.1** and **Table 1.1**). It is also not explicit in ILK (IPBES, 2022b), which is also reflected in the literature on ILK governance. The review of ILK/IPLC literature found that only a small percentage (3.2%, or 35 out of 1,091 publications) described governance aspects in detail, reflecting a large gap in documentation of governance systems based on ILK and/or by IPLC for the nexus (IPBES, 2023b). The results thus highlight the importance of attention to ILK and partnerships with IPLC to ensure that their contributions, including their ILK, are recognized and can lead to changes in policies and institutions that take account of the interlinkages among nature, food systems, water systems, well-being and spirituality, and climate change.

Figure 4.15 Knowledge and practices of Indigenous Peoples and local communities that govern the use of nexus elements.

Indigenous and local knowledge (ILK) plays an important role in conceptualizing the close relationship among nature, water systems, food systems, well-being, spirituality, and climate change (see also **Chapter 1, Figure 1.4**). While it is not possible to capture all the relationships among the different nexus elements and the wide range of Indigenous Peoples' and local communities' (IPLC) and ILK governance, the thickness of arrows and the darkness of the triangles indicate the amount of literature found on relationships between elements. Biodiversity is placed in the middle, as the evidence pointed to the important role of nature in IPLC governance of nexus elements. Text around the triangles indicates examples of policy instruments found in the literature, while text inside the triangles indicate examples of policy tools. These instruments and tools are manifestations of customary institutions that are based on traditional world views and values, and multiple actors (far right) play important roles to ensure that such instruments and tools continue to govern the nexus elements.

4.5.3 Addressing equity and justice gaps for nexus governance

While equity and justice concerns are considered important to include in decision-making processes to foster more transformation outcomes, such as through processes like emancipation, empowerment, and benefit and information sharing, there are few examples where these concerns have been incorporated into governance decisions linked to managing nexus interactions (Hoff, 2018b; Koulouri & Mouraviev, 2019). Ideally, decision-making and choices of policy and sociopolitical options are sustainable and equitable over different spaces (e.g., across tele- or meta-coupled impacts) (Boillat *et al.*, 2022; L. Liu *et al.*, 2023; Newig *et al.*, 2020), between different actor groups of the present generation (intragenerational impacts), as well as temporally, ensuring that solutions do not have detrimental effects for future generations (intergenerational impacts) (Alam & Mohammad, 2019; Bastos Lima & Palme, 2022; Cisneros-Montemayor *et al.*, 2019; Leach *et al.*, 2018; Martin, 2017; Pascual *et al.*, 2022; Pickering *et al.*, 2022). Indeed, evidence suggests that approaches that centre

justice and equity can deliver nexus governance that is more intersectional, integrated and intergenerational (Biggs *et al.*, 2015; Newell *et al.*, 2019). Inter- and intra-generational justice and equity dimensions can be assessed through three main dimensions: recognitional, distributive and procedural, within specific social-ecological contexts (**Figure 4.16**) (Leach *et al.*, 2018; Martin, 2017; McDermott, 2013; Pascual *et al.*, 2014, 2022).

Recognitional justice entails recognizing and valuing diverse knowledge systems, perspectives and cultural practices of different communities and actor groups within the nexus (i.e., promoting epistemic justice) (Lotz-Sisitka *et al.*, 2016; Martin, 2017; Pickering *et al.*, 2022; Tengö *et al.*, 2014). It especially includes acknowledging the historical and ongoing contributions of IPLC to food security, food, water and health equity and sovereignty, sustainable resource management and conservation (Cariño & Ferrari, 2021; Sultana, 2018; Weiler *et al.*, 2015). Advancing recognitional justice in nexus governance includes acknowledging and addressing the impacts of colonialism, discrimination and cultural erasure, and

promotes interventions that foster cultural diversity, inclusion and respect for all actors (Schlosberg & Carruthers, 2010).

Distributive justice ensures equitable distribution of resources, benefits and burdens across the nexus. It seeks to address socioeconomic inequalities and disparities by promoting fair and equitable access to food, clean water, healthcare and environmental resources (Parsons *et al.*, 2021; Pascual *et al.*, 2022; Pickering *et al.*, 2022). Distributive justice also aims to reduce disparities in vulnerability and exposure to environmental risks, such as climate change impacts and air and water pollution. Distributive justice considerations are also important when considering cross-scale impacts linked to nexus trade-offs as highlighted by frameworks linked to tele- and meta-coupling (Boillat *et al.*, 2022; Jiang *et al.*, 2023; Li *et al.*, 2023; J. Liu, Hull, *et al.*, 2018; Munroe *et al.*, 2019; Zhang *et al.*, 2019; Zimmerer *et al.*, 2018).

Procedural justice refers to ensuring fair and inclusive decision-making processes in the governance of the nexus

(Adeyeye *et al.*, 2019; Meerow *et al.*, 2019; Naik, 2021). By promoting meaningful participation and representation of diverse actors, including IPLC, policy formulation, planning and implementation can have more transformative outcomes for people and nature (Kiss *et al.*, 2022; M. S. Reed, 2008). For example, participation in decision-making processes can be enhanced by facilitating transparent and accountable governance structures that allow for informed and inclusive decision-making through the implementation of free, prior and informed consent (Mahanty & McDermott, 2013; Ruano-Chamorro *et al.*, 2022; Tomlinson, 2017) or the implementation of specific environmental and social safeguards (Ramcilovic-Suominen *et al.*, 2021; Suiseeya, 2020).

Each of these three elements of justice can be related to nexus elements in specific ways (Table 4.8). The table highlights how achieving just and sustainable futures for the nexus are unlikely without specific attention to the ways inequitable outcomes are currently experienced, and strategies for overcoming these, which can be specific to individual elements.

Figure 4.16 **Dimensions of equity and justice for nexus governance.**

These include distributive, procedural and recognitional dimensions within a broader social-ecological context and scale (from local/individual to planetary justice scale) with consideration of inter- and intra-generational justice concerns. Given that the dimensions of equity and justice are interconnected and interdependent and strongly mediated by power asymmetries (Bennett *et al.*, 2019; Borras & Franco, 2018; Nightingale, 2017), addressing one dimension often requires enhancement in the other dimensions to ensure a holistic approach.

Table 4.8 **Illustrative table on how the dimensions of equity and justice are important for managing nexus elements for sustainability.**

Examples of policy and sociopolitical options that can facilitate more equitable nexus governance are provided. Full examples with citations are provide in online **Supplementary material 4.1, Table SM.4.1.**

Equity and justice dimension	Examples of policy or sociopolitical response options implemented to mitigate equity/ justice concerns
DISTRIBUTIVE	
<p>Biodiversity: Distributive justice involves the equitable distribution of benefits and costs associated with nature’s contributions to people and conservation efforts. IPLC often bear the brunt of biodiversity loss and environmental degradation yet may receive disproportionately fewer benefits from conservation initiatives compared to external actors and can be displaced of from their traditional lands and waters, depriving them of their livelihoods and cultural heritage. Addressing distributive justice requires recognizing and respecting the rights and knowledge systems of affected peoples and ensuring their meaningful participation and benefit-sharing.</p>	<p>Protected areas and rights-based approaches as <i>legal and regulatory policy instruments.</i></p> <p>Forest Law Enforcement, Governance and Trade agreements (FLEGT) and Reducing Emissions from Deforestation and Forest Degradation and the role of conservation, sustainable management of forests and enhancement of forest carbon stocks in developing countries (REDD+) as <i>economic and financial policy instruments.</i></p> <p>Community forestry, voluntary certifications and behavioural change as <i>social and cultural policy interventions.</i></p>
<p>Water: Distributive justice concerns access to clean and safe water resources. IPLC and marginalized populations often face inequitable access to water and water services and infrastructure which can be exacerbated by climate change, entrenching social disparities. Strengthening distributive justice in the governance of freshwater and marine systems involves prioritizing access to safe and clean water and ensuring rights for marginalized groups, promoting community-led water management initiatives, including citizen science and ensuring equitable allocation of water resources (UN-Water, 2018).</p>	<p>Economic incentives and Water User Association Markets as <i>economic and financial policy instruments.</i></p> <p>Multi-lateral agreements and rights-based approaches as <i>legal and regulatory policy instruments.</i></p> <p>Voluntary green stormwater infrastructure as <i>social and cultural policy instruments.</i></p>
<p>Food: Distributive justice intersects with issues of access to nutritious and culturally appropriate food. Food insecurity disproportionately affects marginalized communities, including small-scale farmers, Indigenous peoples and low-income urban residents. For example, agribusiness expansion and land grabs can displace smallholder farmers from their land, leading to loss of livelihoods, food insecurity and forced migration. Distributive justice from a food system perspective focuses on equitable access to land, resources and markets for small-scale producers, as well as policies that support agroecological farming practices, food sovereignty and promotion of sustainable local food systems.</p>	<p>Food reserves and agricultural policy as <i>legal and regulatory policy instruments.</i></p> <p>Climate smart agriculture as <i>social and cultural policy instrument.</i></p> <p>Considerations of woman’s rights as <i>a rights-based instrument.</i></p>
<p>Health: Distributive justice encompasses access to healthcare services, medicines and public health interventions. Socioeconomic disparities in healthcare access and outcomes lead to marginalized communities experiencing higher rates of disease burden, exposure to environmental risks such air and water pollution, and reduced access to quality healthcare. Distributive justice in health requires addressing social determinants of health (including employment, income, housing, food and access to healthcare), strengthening primary healthcare systems and ensuring universal health coverage to reduce disparities in healthcare access and outcomes.</p>	<p>Green housing regulations, urban green space planning and health care policy as <i>legal and regulatory policy instruments.</i></p> <p>Taxation as <i>an economic and financial policy instrument.</i></p> <p>Skills development and behavioural change as <i>social and cultural policy instruments.</i></p>
<p>Climate change: There are differentiated impacts of climate change on different groups across time and space, and those most at risk from climate change are often those who have contributed minimally to greenhouse gas emissions. Communities living in vulnerable, underserved or marginal landscapes, particularly in the Global South, often have limited options for anticipating, absorbing and adapting to climate hazards. Prioritization of the differentiated needs and rights of those communities most at risk, and policy and sociopolitical response options that can enhance climate resilience, can ensure equitable access to climate finance and appropriate technology transfer.</p>	<p>REDD+, carbon pricing and alternate global economic models as <i>economic and financial policy instruments.</i></p> <p>Urban planning as <i>a legal and regulatory policy instrument.</i></p>
RECOGNITION	
<p>Biodiversity: Recognitional justice in biodiversity refers to the acknowledgment of a diversity of values, practices and relationships regarding biodiversity and human-nature relationships that need to be acknowledged. Importantly, not only local communities but people living far away from the system can feel concerned about the biodiversity of a particular place and claim their right to be considered in decision-making.</p>	<p>Free Prior and Informed Consent (FPIC) as <i>a rights-based instruments and customary norms.</i></p>

Table 4 8

Equity and justice dimension	Examples of policy or sociopolitical response options implemented to mitigate equity/ justice concerns
RECOGNITION	
<p>Water: Water justice is the recognition of right-holders regarding water management. Increasingly, Indigenous water rights are being recognized by formal institutions and a diversity of approaches is being taken by governments, courts and Indigenous peoples in response to the long history of inequities in water governance.</p>	<p>Indigenous water declarations as a <i>rights-based and customary policy instrument</i>.</p>
<p>Food: Recognition in food justice involves respect for diverse food values and food cultures, including different conceptions of eating well. Diversifying the understanding of ethical, healthy and sustainable food consumption can support food recognition justice. Recognition justice also reaches farming practices and farmers, in the sense that misrecognizing peasant farmers creates dependence upon an industrial farming model limiting the emergence of alternatives, e.g., laws forcing farmers to buy commercial seeds prevents the use of seed varieties selected by farmers.</p>	<p>Voluntary certification and participatory certification as <i>social and cultural policy instruments</i>.</p>
<p>Health: Health justice refers to the acknowledgement of a diversity of health practices and cultures. Misrecognition can be derived from cultural differences as well as by the imposition of values and expectations by the dominant groups, e.g., gender or race/ethnicity-based health injustice. In addition, health research needs to incorporate the communities' perspectives of the problem as well as their solutions.</p>	<p>Participatory needs assessments and participatory parity as <i>social and cultural policy instruments</i>.</p>
<p>Climate change: Recognition of climate justice involves considering how the views and needs of local communities are taken into account for climate adaptation and mitigation, including for just transitions, to ensure that the burdens of climate mitigation and adaptation do not fall disproportionately on some.</p>	<p>The Adaptation Justice Index as a <i>social and cultural policy instrument</i>.</p>
PROCEDURAL	
<p>Biodiversity: Procedural justice refers to the right to participate in decision-making processes about biodiversity management and conservation. Participation in decision-making is fundamental to achieve successful conservation although the level of participation can range. Procedural justice in biodiversity decision-making processes has critical implications for the ecological outcomes of conservation. In turn, promoting procedural justice on biodiversity can contribute to decolonizing science and practice.</p>	<p>Transversal to all nexus elements: Policy levers or actions that decision makers can take to promote procedural justice criteria include 1) contextual fit; 2) scalar fit; 3) conflict resolution; 4) facilitation; 5) free, prior, and informed consent (FPIC); 6) integrating knowledge systems; and 7) adaptable and flexible processes (Ruano-Chamorro <i>et al.</i>, 2022).</p>
<p>Water: Procedural justice is based on three pillars: right to transparent and objective information, right to participate in decision-making, and access to justice to make it meaningful. Failing to promote procedural justice, such as the absence of statutory recognition of rights to water, can lead to uncertainties about water management procedures.</p>	<p>Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM) policy as a <i>legal and regulatory policy instrument</i>.</p>
<p>Food: Procedural justice is related to the concept of food sovereignty, e.g., claiming a greater distribution of power in the management of food and agricultural systems that goes beyond food security (distributive food justice).</p>	<p>Community-based conservation and collaborative management as <i>rights-based instruments and customary norms</i>.</p>
<p>Health: The main health justice claims ask for political representation, e.g., health sector policies development and the engagement of the disadvantaged in decision-making, promoting a greater understanding of health rights and responsibilities and political pressure.</p>	<p>Participatory human rights budgeting, participatory monitoring and increasing transparency, normalizing information exchange, sharing agenda-setting and decision-making power with partners as <i>social and cultural policy instruments</i>.</p> <p>Cross-subsidisation between population groups and training and accountability as <i>economic and financial policy instruments</i>.</p>
<p>Climate change: Procedural justice refers to the processes by which climate governance is developed and implemented, such as for instance having the political power to decide what is fair and just regarding the distribution of climate benefits and burdens or how are different perspectives included in climate decisions. Notably, the first climate assessments and negotiations lacked participation of scientists from industrializing countries, which led to disagreements regarding emission calculations and uneven climate responsibilities between industrialized and industrializing countries.</p>	<p>The Adaptation Justice Index as a <i>social and cultural policy instrument</i>.</p>

4.5.3.1 Operationalizing equity and justice

In seeking to achieve the three dimensions of equity, consideration of rights-based approaches, such as a human-rights based approach, can be useful (Box 4.11). They can facilitate a more equitable acknowledgement of the diverse values, needs and rights of marginalized actors, and can intersect with nexus challenges and governance in numerous ways. Participation guaranteed by human-rights based approaches and which makes use of safeguards like free, prior and informed consent (FPIC) can strengthen representation and effective engagement of key actor groups, supporting their agency to effectively assert their voices in policy and decision-making processes. For example, locally led climate change adaptation response options that involve Indigenous Peoples, local communities, women and youth are more likely to have positive outcomes for both people and the ecosystems on which they depend (Asugeni *et al.*, 2019; Global Centre on Adaptation & Climate and Development Knowledge Network, 2023; Nalau *et al.*, 2018; Westoby *et al.*, 2020). This can also lead to virtuous cycles: for example, when IPLC (and elders and women in particular) are afforded meaningful participation and representation as key actors with distinct knowledge and value systems, this can aid in passing these knowledges, practices and values onto younger generations, as well as leading to the co-design of innovative response options (COD-ILK, 2023; IPBES, 2023b). Moreover, establishing leadership roles can create the potential for these actors, including IPLC, to grow their adaptive capacity that will in

turn improve their ability to address future environmental issues (Kampanje & Kampanje, 2022).

This is particularly the case for women, including Indigenous women, who are disproportionately impacted by climate change, food, water and health insecurity and biodiversity loss. Ensuring their inclusion in the development and implementation of any response option to address these issues can ensure that benefits and burdens are distributed equally. Options for deepening gender transformative actions move beyond identifying women's rights to exploring the gendered roles of men and women, as well as the acknowledgement of LGBTIQ+ actors in nexus governance (Carthy & Landesman, 2023). By adopting a holistic gender-transformative approach (see also section 4.5.3.3 on intersectionality) which focuses on the economic, political, ecological and cultural underlying causes of vulnerability of different groups, co-designed interventions to address the root causes of vulnerability can transform power relations that have been shaped by unequal patriarchal and discriminatory norms and practices. In turn, this can facilitate overcoming barriers to the visibility and voice of marginalized actors and result in a better recognition of the importance of tailored approaches to address the differentiated needs of actors in a system (Humayra *et al.*, 2024; TEBTEBBA & ELATIA, 2022). Thus, a holistic gender-transformative approach goes beyond the symptoms of inequality to redress gender inequalities, remove structural barriers, such as unequal roles and rights of diverse gender identities and empower disadvantaged actors, and is increasingly being called for by multiple donors funding nexus related work (MacArthur *et al.*, 2022).

Box 4.11 Human rights-based approach as a cross-cutting nexus response option.

Both the Paris Agreement and the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework acknowledge the importance of a human-rights based approach for biodiversity and climate action. While there is no multilaterally agreed definition of a human rights-based approach (human-rights based approach), it is a key policy and sociopolitical option based on international human rights standards and directed towards respecting, protecting, promoting and fulfilling human rights. The Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR) has conceptualised a human-rights based approach to climate change (OHCHR, 2021) and to biodiversity (OHCHR, 2022). Applying a human-rights based approach can clarify the obligations of states and businesses, initiate bold action and draw attention to the challenges of the most vulnerable and impoverished, and give people the ability to participate in the process of creating and implementing solutions (UNGA, 2021).

States are the primary duty bearers in accordance with Articles 55 and 56 of the 1945 United Nations Charter. However, non-state actors, especially businesses, also have duties and responsibilities (OHCHR, 2021). OHCHR has highlighted key

human rights and key collective rights related to biodiversity and climate change (OHCHR, 2021, 2022). These include among others the right to life, to health, to adequate food, to safe drinking water and sanitation, to adequate housing and standard of living, to self-determination, to development, cultural rights, and the collective right of Indigenous Peoples to free, prior and informed consent (FPIC). The right to a clean, healthy and sustainable environment, which was recognized by the UN General Assembly in 2022, provides an opportunity for catalytic transformative action. While there is not a universally agreed definition of the right to a healthy environment, it is generally understood to include substantive and procedural elements. The substantive elements include clean air; a safe and stable climate; access to safe water and adequate sanitation; healthy and sustainably produced food; non-toxic environments in which to live, work, study and play; and healthy biodiversity and ecosystems. The procedural elements include access to information, the right to participate in decision-making, and access to justice and effective remedies, including the secure exercise of these rights free from reprisals and retaliation. Realizing the right to a healthy environment also

Box 4 11

requires international cooperation, solidarity and equity in action, including resource mobilization, as well as recognition of extraterritorial jurisdiction over human rights harms caused by environmental degradation (OHCHR, UNEP, UNDP, 2023).

In alignment with commitments made in the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework, states are encouraged to consider adopting a human rights approach in their biodiversity and ecosystem services' policies and actions, which include mitigating the impacts of climate change and biodiversity loss on food, water and health and preventing associated negative impacts on human rights; ensuring that all persons have the necessary capacity to adapt to climate change; ensuring accountability and effective remedy for human rights harms caused by climate change and biodiversity loss; ensuring equity in climate and biodiversity action, and guaranteeing equality and non-discrimination; as well as access to effective remedies for violations of human rights relating to the environment among others (OHCHR, 2021, 2022). While states are encouraged to act in this regard, there is variable enforcement of these rights in courts of law. However, where rulings and decisions have been made through a recognition of rights, including FPIC, they have the potential to catalyse transformative change by recognising alternative governance and economic systems particularly in holding private and public economic actors accountable for their actions (Borràs, 2016; IPBES, 2022c; Papillon & Rodon, 2020).

All human beings are rights-holders under the Universal Declaration of Human Rights. IPLC are critical rights holders in the context of land rights and self-determination, while Indigenous Peoples hold special collective rights as recognized by the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous

Peoples (UNDRIP), including customary rights to traditional lands, territories and resources and traditional knowledge. IPLC have successfully managed and conserved biodiversity due to their intimate relationship with nature in the places they live (Fa *et al.*, 2020; WWF *et al.*, 2021), providing evidence for the need to ensure their involvement in policies and response options.

Chapter 5 outlines several rights-based response options that show potential for improving nexus elements with positive outcomes for people and nature (see **Chapter 5.1, section 5.1.3.10; Chapter 5.2, section 5.2.3.7**).

In addition, other legal instruments have taken a human-rights based approach and addressed consideration of rights to land and territory, access to justice and to effective grievance mechanisms, including the Rio Declaration Principle 10; UNDRIP article 2; Aarhus Convention article 9; and the Escazú Agreement articles 8 & 9. The Escazú Agreement is the first regional environmental and human rights treaty in Latin America and the Caribbean, and the first legally binding instrument in the world to include provisions on environmental defenders. ILO Convention No. 169 concerning Indigenous and Tribal Peoples in Independent Countries also plays a key role in protecting the human rights of Indigenous Peoples. The convention is a binding international instrument that focuses on recognizing and protecting the rights of Indigenous and tribal peoples, including their rights to land and natural resources and participation in decision-making processes. It underscores the importance of respecting the cultural identity, traditions and social institutions of Indigenous Peoples, and by affirming their rights to autonomy and self-determination, the convention provides a robust framework for ensuring that Indigenous communities can be active participants in governance of the nexus (Silva & Rocha, 2018).

4.5.3.2 Additional justice considerations

Recent research highlights the need to also consider planetary and Earth system justice as a way to acknowledge the inseparability of human-nature or social-ecological systems, and the planetary scale of multiple, interconnected crises (Biermann & Kalfagianni, 2020; Gupta *et al.*, 2021; Gupta & Lebel, 2020; Kashwan *et al.*, 2020). The concept of planetary justice is compelling within the context of nexus governance as it takes a transformative angle (Gupta *et al.*, 2021), highlighting the need for transformations across multiple sectors and scales and the inclusion of key actors and considerations of the multi-dimensional impacts of response options (Pereira *et al.*, 2023).

Within the context of health, there is a need to consider additional dimensions of health equity, which refers to the concept of ensuring that all individuals have fair and just opportunities to achieve their full health potential, regardless of their social, ecological or economic circumstances

(Braveman, 2006; Friel *et al.*, 2011). Health equity involves addressing and eliminating systematic and avoidable health disparities that are unfair and unjust, rooted in factors such as colonization, race, ethnicity, socioeconomic status, gender, geography and other forms of disadvantage or oppression (Alexandra *et al.*, 2017; K. R. Jones *et al.*, 2018) (see also **section 4.5.3.3** on intersectionality). Health equity includes considerations of equal access to healthcare services, including diverse forms of healthcare such as those based on ILK (see **Chapter 5.4**) but goes beyond this to recognize that individuals and communities have different needs and challenges that impact their health outcomes. Thus, achieving health equity requires addressing the underlying social-ecological determinants of health, such as education, livelihood opportunities, housing, and access to resources and green spaces all of which significantly influence health (Braubach *et al.*, 2017; R. Jones, 2019).

Health equity and environmental justice are closely interconnected concepts that recognize the interplay

between social, economic and environmental factors in shaping health outcomes. While health equity focuses on eliminating health disparities and ensuring fair opportunities for health, environmental justice addresses the disproportionate burden of environmental hazards and pollution on marginalized communities (Garnier *et al.*, 2020; R. Jones, 2019; Lewis *et al.*, 2020). Health and ecosystems are intrinsically related to all areas of development, underscoring the importance of finding response options that acknowledge nexus interlinkages and address multiple SDGs (Langlois *et al.*, 2012; Romanelli *et al.*, 2015). Other existing global institutions and frameworks, such as the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework, Paris Agreement and the Convention to Combat Desertification could also expand biodiversity preservation and climate change mitigation and adaptation methods that specifically address and integrate health equity outcomes in order to lower poverty-related diseases and safeguard the health of the most vulnerable (Garnier *et al.*, 2020; Willetts *et al.*, 2023).

4.5.3.3 Intersectionality as an enabler of more just outcomes

Intersectionality is a theoretical construct which emphasises the interconnectedness of various forms of oppression,

including gender, sexuality, race, class and ability (Crenshaw, 1990). Applying this lens to the nexus can help recognize and address the specific power dynamics, vulnerabilities and experiences of marginalized communities and how they can be incorporated into research, policy and practice and supported by policies and laws, e.g., those enshrined in human-rights law (see [Box 4.12](#)) (D. E. Johnson *et al.*, 2022; Menton *et al.*, 2020; Rakhmatullaev *et al.*, 2018; Vercillo *et al.*, 2023). Using an intersectional approach can shed light on how social inequalities intersect and compound the impacts of environmental, social equity and health challenges, leading to differential access to resources and opportunities to navigate alternative development pathways (Gupta *et al.*, 2023; Mzimela & Ahmed, 2018)

As social groups are neither homogenous nor static, an intersectional approach is useful for acknowledging complexity by taking account of historical, sociocultural and political contexts. Thus, intersectional approaches can help build understanding of the differentiated nature of vulnerability and can draw attention to the social root causes of vulnerability, creating a more nuanced picture of where opportunities, levers or leverage points might exist (Gupta *et al.*, 2023). Intersectionality can contribute to advancing more equitable implementation of response options for the nexus through several ways as summarized in [Box 4.12](#).

Box 4.12 Intersectionality as an enabler of transformative change for nexus governance.

An intersectionality approach to nexus governance can assist with:

- **Foregrounding social justice and equity:** Intersectionality calls for social justice and challenges mainstream structures that perpetuate discrimination and exclusion. By incorporating intersectional considerations into the nexus, there is an opportunity to advocate for more inclusive and equitable policies and practices (Agyeman *et al.*, 2002; Allouche *et al.*, 2019; Schlör *et al.*, 2018). This includes recognizing and addressing the unique needs and perspectives of marginalized people, e.g., Indigenous Peoples, women and girls and those from LGBTIQ+ communities within food, water, biodiversity, health and climate change governance (Fletcher *et al.*, 2021; Mzimela & Ahmed, 2018).
- **Disrupting inequitable power dynamics:** Intersectionality theory challenges power structures and normative assumptions (Garcia & Tschakert, 2022; J. A. Johnson *et al.*, 2021). By applying this lens to the nexus, it is possible to identify and disrupt power dynamics that perpetuate inequalities in access to resources, decision-making processes and benefits (Malin *et al.*, 2019; Steinfield *et al.*, 2021). This can involve questioning and transforming gendered divisions of labour, roles and responsibilities

related to biodiversity conservation, water management, food production, health services and climate action (Garcia *et al.*, 2021; Sovacool *et al.*, 2023).

- **Acknowledging diverse knowledge systems:** Intersectionality theory challenges dominant heteronormative knowledge systems and opens up space for diverse ways of knowing and understanding the world (Hill *et al.*, 2020; Tengö *et al.*, 2014, 2017). By embracing multiple knowledge systems, including Indigenous, traditional and LGBTIQ+ knowledges, the a more holistic, robust and inclusive understanding of the complex relationships within the nexus can be built (J. M. Chambers *et al.*, 2021; J. A. Johnson *et al.*, 2021).
- **Facilitating more context specific data collection and analysis:** Collecting and analyzing data that captures intersectional experiences and impacts within the nexus can highlight these issues, especially collection efforts that support data sovereignty (García-Reyes *et al.*, 2022). This involves disaggregating data by various identity categories to understand how different groups are affected differently by biodiversity, water, food, health and climate change issues (Ahmed & Eklund, 2021; Kosanic *et al.*, 2022; Perkins *et al.*, 2018; Thompson-Hall *et al.*, 2016). This data can inform evidence-based decision-making and highlight the specific

Box 4 12

challenges faced by marginalized communities (Djoudi *et al.*, 2016).

- **Ensuring more participatory decision-making:**

Intersectionality theory emphasizes the importance of inclusivity and participatory decision-making processes. This can involve engaging diverse voices, including those from marginalized communities, in decision-making processes related to biodiversity conservation, water and food governance, health policies and climate change mitigation and adaptation. This can help ensure that the needs and experiences of marginalized communities are considered, leading to more informed and equitable outcomes (Assaduzzaman *et al.*, 2023; Collet *et al.*, 2022; Hill *et al.*, 2020).

- **Cultivating solidarity:** Intersectionality theory recognizes the importance of building alliances and solidarity among diverse social-ecological justice movements (Walsh & Wilson, 2020). By connecting multiple forms of activism with environmental, climate change, LGBTQIA+, food and health justice movements within the nexus, it is possible to foster collaborations and partnerships that address intersecting forms of oppression (Amorim-Maia *et al.*, 2022). By engaging with and learning from organizations and activists working on intersectional issues, alliances can be built that amplify marginalized voices within the nexus. This can lead to more inclusive and transformative actions that advance social and ecological well-being.

4.5.4 Key components of nexus governance

Section 4.2 highlighted gaps in the definition of nexus governance. This section uses the evidence from the reviews of the literature from **sections 4.3** and **4.4**, the discussions of actors (especially IPLC) and arenas of engagement from **sections 4.5.1** and **4.5.2**, and the synthesis of the important roles that equity and justice play in ensuring improved nexus outcomes from **section 4.5.3** to propose a more consolidated definition and comprehensive approach to nexus governance. The existing literature and evidence have been distilled into five key components that are associated with enhanced nexus governance outcomes and that can assist with navigating nexus challenges and providing guidance for decision makers towards just and sustainable futures (**Figure 4.17**). These are:

Integrative, holistic and transdisciplinary framing of problems and solutions (sections 4.2.2, 4.2.3, 4.3.3).

Nexus governance is more successful when it clearly identifies the underlying drivers of nexus challenges and explicitly delineates important relationships and dynamics, including through anticipatory planning (Hoolohan *et al.*, 2018; Tye *et al.*, 2022; Weitz *et al.*, 2017; Yuan & Lo, 2022). Transdisciplinarity relates to including skills and viewpoints that are underrepresented and those that cross disciplinary boundaries, which are needed because by definition nexus problems are often wicked ones with no clear solutions and thus can benefit from multiple perspectives, expertise and voices (Bréthaut *et al.*, 2019; Visseren-Hamakers & Kok, 2022).

Inclusive approaches that bring about enhanced arenas of actor engagement (sections 4.2.3, 4.2.5, 4.2.6, 4.3.6, 4.4.2, 4.5.1, 4.5.2, 4.5.3). Nexus governance can be improved by attention to participatory and

procedural justice alongside types of actors and where and how they can interact, including the role of power in these interactions (Howarth & Monasterolo, 2017; Tye *et al.*, 2022; Urbinatti *et al.*, 2020; Weitz *et al.*, 2017; Yuan & Lo, 2022). For nexus governance, inclusivity is important because by definition, nexus challenges cut across sectors and thus require multi-sectoral and multi-stakeholder solutions. Including multiple values and knowledge systems helps ensure participation, co-design and co-delivery of policy and sociopolitical options through full and effective participation of relevant rights holders and stakeholders (Ghodsvali *et al.*, 2019; Lebel *et al.*, 2020).

Normative considerations of equity and justice, alongside accountability (sections 4.2.5, 4.3.6, 4.4.2, 4.5.3).

Given known barriers and risks of poor and inequitable choices, nexus governance can be improved by foregrounding equity and justice in decision-making processes. This can surface and help solve for trade-offs, conflicts and power asymmetries, such as through more transparent and accountable actions and outcomes and more equitable sharing of information and benefits (Romero-Lankao *et al.*, 2017; Weitz *et al.*, 2017; Yuan & Lo, 2022). For example, human rights-based approaches that set out obligations and procedures on rights like access to water and food as well as access to information and participation help foster equity (Kooiman & Jentoft, 2009; Olawuyi, 2020; Sharma & Kumar, 2020). Specific measures can ensure that policymakers and other actors are held accountable for their commitments to multiple nexus goals (Bowen *et al.*, 2017; Büscher & Dressler, 2007; Pascual *et al.*, 2022; Pickering *et al.*, 2022). For example, where efforts or agreements fail to deliver or fall short of expectations, active monitoring agreements can enforce accountability, an example of which can be seen from the the Yasuní-ITT (Ishpingo-Tambococha-Tiputini) Initiative. This initiative consisted of leaving

the oil underground in a part of Yasuní National Park in the Ecuadorean Amazon and proposed a change of imaginaries by questioning the fundamental role of oil in our capitalist and productivist society (Le Quang, 2016).

Enhanced mechanisms and processes for collaboration and coordination across scales and sectors (sections 4.2.2, 4.2.6, 4.3.2, 4.3.3, 4.3.4, 4.4.1, 4.5.1). Nexus governance that accounts for interlinkages and maximizes synergies can be facilitated by improved coordination and collaboration (Hoolohan *et al.*, 2018; Kurian & Ardakanian, 2015; Urbinatti *et al.*, 2020; Yuan & Lo, 2022), ranging from transboundary cooperation to better resourced community venues (Kirsop-Taylor & Hejnowicz, 2022; Märker *et al.*, 2018; van Gevelt, 2020; White *et al.*, 2017). In some cases, new institutional forms may be needed: for example, the use of ‘special districts’ has been used to manage water towards conservation ends in the United States of America, which may allow for more nexus governance interactions (Portney *et al.*, 2017), while in other cases stakeholders may prefer to work within existing institutions but with better coordination (Al-Masri *et al.*, 2019). Interactions at different scales can reverberate

across them; for example, in the case of transboundary water management, the involvement of local actors may lead to improved cooperation between state actors, while better reflecting the needs of local communities in such agreements (Offutt, 2022). The co-creation and identification of multiple policy and sociopolitical options can provide experimental evidence for pathways to more sustainable futures (Jarzebski *et al.*, 2023), while evidence on scaling can help create and deepen these mechanisms (section 4.4). Collaborations and interactions can be enhanced by attention to sources of authority, information and resources across scales and sectors (Sixt *et al.*, 2020), alongside trust and willingness to share and other cognitive interactions (J. L. Jones & White, 2022).

Adaptive, reflexive and experimental approaches to learn from what works and to scale these solutions (sections 4.2.2, 4.2.3, 4.2.5, 4.3.7, 4.4.1, 4.4.2, 4.5.3). Adaptive approaches embrace complexity, surprise and change through exploration and informed and innovative decision-making (Hoolohan *et al.*, 2018; Howarth & Monasterolo, 2017; Tye *et al.*, 2022). This can help deal with feedbacks and compounding issues across the nexus

Figure 4 17 **Key components for nexus governance as a compass to navigate tackling nexus challenges.**

These include integrative, holistic and transdisciplinary framing of problems and solutions, inclusive approaches that bring about enhanced arenas of actor engagement, normative considerations of equity and justice alongside accountability, enhanced mechanisms and processes for collaboration and coordination across scales and sectors and adaptive, reflexive and experimental approaches to support learning and scaling.

elements, while navigating alternative future pathways. Embedding reflection and learning in monitoring can help to foster adaptive solutions and ensure accountability (Yuan & Lo, 2022). Iterative monitoring of the outcomes of policy and sociopolitical options can assist with managing future trade-offs and unintended consequences if the option no longer remains relevant or contexts have changed. Furthermore, reflexive approaches can help identify existing capacity gaps and needs.

These components of nexus governance can be summarized as the systematic coordinating structures and processes that enhance the engagement of multiple actors through horizontal (e.g., across various nexus elements at one scale) and vertical (e.g., cross-scale connectivity or multilevel governance) channels to address nexus challenges, identify policy and sociopolitical options, and manage their implementation towards just sustainable futures. Each of these five broad components are linked; for example, better coordination and collaboration might lead to more distributive equity (Sharma & Kumar, 2020). Each of the broad components can also be improved by strengthening enabling conditions, including capacity strengthening or inclusive finance mechanisms. They can also be enhanced by use of decision-support tools, which help to elaborate processes and pathways (see **section 4.6**). In this way, nexus governance can guide the implementation of specific policy and sociopolitical options that are appropriate for a specific context and location (Srigiri & Dombrowsky, 2022; Weitz *et al.*, 2017).

There is also a need to move from thinking about what constitutes nexus governance from a theoretical perspective to actually doing it (McGrane *et al.*, 2019; Simpson & Jewitt, 2019). **Chapter 7** takes up this challenge by proposing a roadmap that highlights a series of steps that different actors can take to enhance understanding of nexus approaches and improve nexus governance, resulting in more just and sustainable futures (**Chapter 7, section 7.3** and online **Supplementary material 7.3**).

4.5.4.1 Empirical examples of nexus governance

As explained in **section 4.2.3**, much of the existing literature on nexus governance focuses on what is not working, for example, governance failures as a result of fragmented, reactive, exclusive and opaque systems (Lebel *et al.*, 2020), rather than on empirical examples of nexus governance and on positive examples of successes. This section builds on the systematic reviews of existing policy and governance literature reported in previous sections (**sections 4.3** and **4.5.2**) to provide case study examples of nexus governance in real-world practice (**Table 4.9, Boxes 4.13** and **4.14**). **Box 4.13** offers an example of multiple actors at various scales trying to work together towards nexus governance in New Zealand, as actors managed to change policymaking from consultation-based towards a more participatory and collaborative mode at multiple scales and to understand the importance of choosing frameworks to support decision-making. **Box 4.14** offers an example of inclusive actor engagement and collaboration across scales and sectors through maize-based milpa systems in Mexico.

Table 4.9 Empirical examples of nexus governance.

Case studies of nexus governance	Nexus elements involved	Nexus governance components (Figure 4.17)
<p>Water and land management in the Canterbury region, New Zealand: See details in Box 4.13.</p>		
<p>Community based adaptation to climate change in the Arabana, South Australia: The Arabana Climate Change Adaptation project was a multi method, cross cultural and interdisciplinary adaptation project which aimed to assess the resilience and vulnerability of the Arabana people and then develop adaptation options (Nurse-Bray <i>et al.</i>, 2013). Project dimensions included an assessment of adaptive capacity via interrogation of well-being, governance, analysis of risk perception values and organization of adaptation workshops. Adaptation options in the Arabana strategy include the establishment of cultural centres in every rural and urban place where Arabana people live, setting up economic businesses in tourism and pastoralism, moving back to the country initiatives, establishing cultural camps, revitalization programmes and the establishment of land management, monitoring and research programmes.</p>		
<p>Landrace maize diversity in milpa systems, Mexico: See details in Box 4.14.</p>		

Table 4.9

| Case studies of nexus governance | Nexus elements involved
 |
|--|---|---|
| <p>Living lab for restoration of a landfill site in China (Yuan & Lo, 2022):</p> <p>This project aimed to understand the synergies and trade-offs between water, food and energy for restoration and future design of a landfill site. The project applied mixed methods including cost-benefit analysis through a questionnaire survey, environmental footprint evaluation through life cycle analysis and expert judgment on ecosystem service provision to explore response options and evaluate their performance. Three main groups of stakeholders associated with the resources were involved in the project through workshops, including local government and management authorities, scientific and technical experts, and local actors and NGOs. The project established an engagement process and knowledge sharing interface. To make response options and their impacts visible, the project built up an educational and knowledge base that can be used in the local community.</p> | |
| <p>Transformative change of paddy rice systems for biodiversity and Sado Living Lab for Sustainability in Japan:</p> <p>See details in Box 4.15 (section 4.5.4.2)</p> | |

Box 4.13 Water and land management in the Canterbury region, New Zealand.

The Treaty of Waitangi 1840 recognizes Māori rights and enshrines ‘the expectations of iwi and hapū today’, including ‘an expectation of an equal partnership in collaborative planning and decision-making, guided by the principles of the Treaty’ (Sinner, J., and G. R. Harmsworth, 2015). However, colonization and economic development in New Zealand over the last century, largely based on production of meat, wool, milk, arable and horticultural crops, involved dispossession of Māori land (Harcourt, N., Robson-Williams, M. and Tamepo, R., 2022). Although water and land remain contentious issues in New Zealand, the recognition and role of Māori as partners in the development of land and water plans has increased over the last decades.

Since 1991, freshwater use and allocation have been regulated by the Resource Management Act (RMA), which aims to promote the sustainable management of natural and physical resources, ‘in a way, or at a rate, which enables people and communities to provide for their social, economic and cultural well-being’ ((RMA. Resource Management Act, 1991) [sec.5 (1)(2)]). Under the RMA, the central government establishes national standards and objectives for freshwater use, while regional governments set rules through regional policy statements and plans. In 2011, the central government introduced a National Policy Statement for Freshwater Management, which requires regional councils to set limits for water quantity and quality on all waterbodies (MfE, 2017). As a result, several participatory and collaborative decision-making processes were undertaken for regional and catchment-scale resource management (Kirk, N. *et al.*, 2021), changing policymaking from consultation-based towards a more participatory and collaborative mode (Fraussen, B., and D. Halpin, 2017).

In the Canterbury region, the rapid intensification of land use, facilitated by greater access to irrigation and first-come first-served water allocation (Kirk, N., 2015), led to increasing concerns about declining groundwater levels and freshwater quantity and quality. These concerns as well as the lack of reflection of Māori values in decisions led to tensions around water management in the region. As a response, a Canterbury Water Management Strategy (CWMS) was collaboratively developed and published in 2009, which promoted collaborative governance. The CWMS vision was to “enable present and future generations to gain the greatest social, economic, recreational and cultural benefits from our water resources within an environmentally sustainable framework” (CMF, 2009). The vision is to be achieved through setting long-term targets for ecosystem health/biodiversity, natural character of braided rivers, kaitiakitanga (i.e., Māori stewardship), drinking water, recreational and amenity opportunities, water-use efficiency, irrigated land area, energy security and efficiency, regional and national economies, and environmental limits (CMF, 2009).

Collaborative committees working to implement the CWMS have become part of Canterbury’s regional planning process, which began with the establishment of a Zone Committee (ZC) for each of Canterbury’s ten sub-regions. A ZC consists of a representative from the regional council, local rūnanga (Māori tribal representatives) and 4-6 representatives from the community. The ZC, in consultation with interest groups, the broader community and industry, develop a Zone Implementation Programme defining their priority outcomes and describing a package of actions and proposed limits that are expected to deliver the CWMS targets.

The CWMS shows how the integration of community aspirations and Māori values in decision-making led to the

Box 4 13

development of policies and implementation programmes which, by acknowledging different values and knowledge systems, became more open to environmental interests and improved environmental outcomes. Implementation after five years indicated progress in many areas through a variety of funding mechanisms, including on-the-ground activities around biodiversity, wetlands and stream augmentation.

Such an outcome was made possible by collaboration mechanisms and arenas of engagement at various scales. At the national level, the Land and Water Forum (LAWF) was established with government support in 2009 to develop a shared, country-wide, stakeholder-led vision for freshwater management. Both the primary collaboration and the technical

working groups had Māori representatives, and LAWF made direct recommendations to central government through five reports between 2009 and 2018 (e.g., (LAWF, 2012)). While the process was not completely smooth, the LAWF was able to complete its work as planned in July 2018. At the regional level, the Canterbury Regional Water Management Committee was established following recommendations made in the CWMS for nested catchment, regional and national freshwater authorities (CMF, 2009) and addressed issues covering multiple catchment-scale zones and regional issues. At catchment and sub-catchment level, collaborations were established by the ten ZC, which embraced consensus decision-making. While the ZC do not have final decision-making power, they offer recommendations to regional governments.

Box 4 14 *The Milpa system in Mexico.*⁶

In Mexico, researchers have helped support IPLC conservation of agrobiodiversity in the milpa system, a system of polyculture in which each of the species support each other, by choosing to catalogue the landrace maize diversity in the Santa Marta Mountains south of Veracruz, where the Indigenous Nuntajiji people live (San Vicente Tello & Jönsson, 2019). The milpa works through the attributes of its physical form, with each plant having its own place and structure, but is also more deeply connected beneath the soil through fungal networks between their roots (Greenwood, 2023). In the milpa, the farmers have created their own seed and germplasm conservation system, each selecting and cultivating different varieties and contributing to the agrobiodiversity including unique pigments and characteristics of maize landraces. This agrobiodiversity in turn contributes to the basis of the diet, the staple of maize, and makes for culturally and environmentally appropriate foods. Each landrace is used for a variety of specific dishes as well as bolstering health as the anthocyanins, antioxidants and bioactive and anti-inflammatory compounds found in these varieties are known to help prevent chronic disease (Méndez-Flores *et al.*, 2023; San Vicente Tello & Jönsson, 2019). The Nuntajiji people have also co-evolved the milpa system in their mountain ecosystem together with the natural fluctuations in temperature, humidity and precipitation. This system also supports the water catchment and biogeochemical cycles, thereby protecting the water system of low-lying neighbouring cities.

The milpa system in Mexico could be further supported by bundles of responses, including shifting agricultural policies from favouring subsidies for high-input, high resource systems to helping IPLC conserve biodiversity through subsidies for selection and adaptation, higher prices in markets for products of agrobiodiversity of the milpa and introduction of new markets for biodiverse products (San Vicente Tello & Jönsson, 2019).

By exploring the role of corn as both an economic and relational entity, in the lives, livelihoods and cultures that surround it, Greenwood (2023) highlights that food, and especially a food as economically and culturally important as corn, constitutes a site through which power is exercised and sovereignty is claimed. Sovereignty encompasses not only interactions between the state, its citizens, and transnational actors, but also the assertion of community agency over their bodies, environments, and community dynamics. By acting as intermediaries, the civil organizations involved in milpa system allow for plurality, offering a way in which sciences and traditional knowledges can come together on the ground to push for a more inclusive vision of knowledge (Greenwood, 2023). The 'defense of corn' has promoted integration of science and traditional knowledge systems towards a more environmentally sound and equitable future (Greenwood, 2023).

4.5.4.2 Relationship of nexus governance to transformative governance

Current governance systems can not only take better account of the nexus, but can also be more transformative (Bulkeley *et al.*, 2020). The growing body of transformative change literature, as well as the IPBES Global Assessment Report on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (Global

Assessment) (IPBES, 2019), the IPBES Values Assessment (IPBES, 2022a) and IPBES Thematic Assessment of the Underlying Causes of Biodiversity Loss, Determinants of Transformative Change and Options for Achieving the 2050 Vision for Biodiversity (Transformative Change Assessment) suggest that for biodiversity governance to be transformative, it needs to address the underlying causes and indirect drivers of biodiversity loss (Pascual *et*

al., 2022; Razzaque *et al.*, 2019; Visseren-Hamakers *et al.*, 2021; Visseren-Hamakers & Kok, 2022). The IPBES Values Assessment (IPBES, 2022a) identifies that response options that support sustainability transitions are underpinned by the following features: (i) addressing the status quo by changing underlying direct and indirect drivers through social processes and innovations (see also **Chapter 2**); (ii) incorporating and acknowledging the importance of including diverse values; (iii) fostering institutional change by enhancing learning and experimentation; (iv) mobilizing and enhancing the capacities of different actors through transformative literacy; and (v) supporting integrative and adaptive governance (Kelemen *et al.*, 2022; Pascual *et al.*, 2022). Thus, facilitating transformative change and implementing response options across the nexus requires creating and supporting enabling contexts for mobilizing and translating knowledge, negotiating and acknowledging diverse values, and encouraging participation, deliberation and negotiation for the implementation of response options between and within different actor groups (Tengö *et al.*, 2017).

There is a strong relationship between the proposed components of nexus governance and those that are associated with transformative governance, although they may have different justifications and applications. Recent scholarship has focused on attention to inclusive,

transdisciplinary, adaptive, anticipatory and accountable components of transformative governance to address underlying causes and indirect drivers of biodiversity loss and climate change (Visseren-Hamakers *et al.*, 2021; Visseren-Hamakers & Kok, 2022). These mirror some of the foci of the nexus governance components and can be specifically related to transformative change and/or governance as summarized by **Table 4.10**. The IPBES Transformative Change Assessment identifies four principles as guidelines that govern behaviour, decision-making or actions for deliberate transformative change: equity and justice; pluralism and inclusion; respectful and reciprocal human-nature relationship; and adaptive learning and action. These principles/components need to be further embodied and promoted to deepen nexus governance or to make nexus governance transformative.

Box 4.15 offers an example of integrative, adaptive and experimental approaches to promote transformative nexus governance through implementing multi-stakeholder collaboration and integrated local policies including biodiversity friendly rice farming, and conservation of cultural landscape as well as revitalization of local communities in Sado Island, Japan.

Table 4.10 Mapping the key components of nexus governance to the nexus challenges and the principles and strategies of transformative change according to the IPBES Transformative Change Assessment.

Key component of nexus governance	Relationship to IPBES Transformative Change Assessment's principles and strategies
Integrative, holistic and transdisciplinary framing of problems and solutions	<i>Respectful and reciprocal human-nature relationships</i> Whole-of-society and whole-of-government approaches Integrative, transdisciplinary research
Inclusive approaches that bring about enhanced arenas of actor engagement	<i>Pluralism and inclusion</i> Inclusive governance Participatory experimentation Transparent and inclusive review processes Meaningful inclusion of people with shared goals but diverse perspectives and roles
Normative considerations of equity and justice, alongside accountability	<i>Equity and justice</i>
Enhanced mechanisms and processes for collaboration and coordination across scales and sectors	Accountable governance Strategy for stronger regulations, deploy innovative economic and fiscal tools and promote international co-operation
Adaptive, reflexive and experimental approaches to learn from what works and to scale these solutions	<i>Adaptive learning and action</i> Adaptive governance Participatory experimentation Monitoring, evaluation and learning for transformative change

Box 4 15 Transformative change of paddy rice systems for biodiversity and Sado Living Lab for Sustainability in Japan.

Sado rice is a high-quality brand product from Sado island. The island is famous for the traditional rice cultivation system, characterized by a dynamic mosaic of woodlands, plantations, grasslands, paddy fields, wetlands, irrigation ponds, and canals. Its cultivation not only provides food and habitat for local biodiversity but also supports various cultural customs, such as Noh theatrical performances and shrine rituals, which are still the foundation of the spirituality for people in Sado. The Food and Agriculture Organization recognized Sado as one of Japan's first Globally Important Agricultural Heritage Systems in June 2011.

The Japanese crested ibis is the most symbolic species among Sado's rich biodiversity, and it feeds on small living creatures, such as fishes, loaches, and worms that live in and around the rice paddies. To promote ibis-friendly agriculture, Sado City in collaboration with the Sado Agricultural Cooperative (JA Sado) introduced the "Toki-to-kurasu-sato" (Villages coexisting with the crested ibis) rice certification initiative in 2010. To help farmers attain this certification, Sado City encourages and supports farmers taking up the eco-farming certification by collaborating with JA Sado to sell the certified rice at higher prices than regular Sado grown rice.

According to innovation history analysis of the transformation of paddy rice (Takahashi *et al.*, 2023), the innovation history of the Crested Ibis Rice Certification scheme can be divided into four phases. The first phase is represented by experimentation with rice farming methods to rehabilitate the crested ibis' prey animals and biodiversity monitoring by a

farmers' group between 2001 and 2003, motivated by the first successful captive breeding of crested ibis in 1999. The second phase, i.e., stabilization of innovation design, spans from the establishment of Sado City in 2004 to the introduction of the Crested Ibis Rice Certification scheme in 2008. The third phase, diffusion, was observed between 2009 and 2020 when the certified paddy area gradually increased and peaked out at 25% of the total rice paddy area on the island. The fourth phase, full system deployment, has yet to be reached considering the gradually decreasing certified paddy area after the peak at 25% in 2016.

To coordinate fragmented initiatives and activities related to biodiversity conservation, water management, climate change mitigation and adaptation, traditional food culture in the island, local university, local government, NGOs and business sector launched the Sado Living Lab for Sustainability in 2022. This lab facilitates cyclic processes of learning, visioning and actioning through developing database of knowledge and actions, connecting and networking existing efforts, and forming communities. Three key functions of the lab include 1) generating innovations, 2) capacity building, and 3) participatory policy design. Currently, the lab is implementing more than 6 projects including exploring new possibilities to use sea grass and bamboo, mapping and visualizing local resources, ethical production and consumption, eco-tourism, job creation, capacity building, and future scenario building by using IPBES Nature Futures Framework.

Sources: García-Martín *et al.* (2022) and Takahashi *et al.* (2023).

4.5.5 Capacities needed for enhancing nexus governance

Given the noticeable gaps in realizing nexus governance, capacity strengthening is an important enabler and refers to the abilities, resources and skills that enable individuals, organizations and institutions to effectively carry out decision-making processes that address nexus challenges and foster pathways towards just and sustainable futures. These capacities can encompass a wide range of attributes, including knowledge, expertise, technical skills, institutional structures, financial resources and collaborative networks. Capacity strengthening goes beyond capacity development, which assumes a capacity deficit, to capacity mobilization and strengthening approaches which acknowledge that the multiple capacities of actors and institutions are already in existence. Examples of capacity strengthening initiatives from a range of case studies are given in Table 4.11.

Five broad capacity dimensions are identified that, if strengthened, can facilitate implementation of nexus governance: (1) analytical capacity to provide knowledge and tools; (2) bridging capacity to bring together different

ways of knowing and doing; (3) negotiation capacity to navigate trade-offs and uptake of response options; (4) social networking capacity for learning, adapting and acting together; and (5) motivational capacity to build awareness and desire for change (Figure 4.18). These capacities are related to the five components for nexus governance (section 4.5.4) in Table 4.12. Capacity strengthening needs can be addressed through decision support tools, which are reviewed in section 4.6 in terms to these capacity dimensions.

Analytical capacities help actors select and use suitable tools, including theoretical and analytical frameworks, that can help build understanding of the interconnections, feedbacks and relationships among nexus elements and in relation to various direct and indirect drivers of change (see section 4.6). While there are many frameworks that assist with understanding some of the dynamics within the food-water-energy nexus (Al-Saidi & Elagib, 2017; Avellán & Roidt, 2022; K. Jones *et al.*, 2017; McGrane *et al.*, 2019), there are limited ones available for understanding all the nexus elements covered in this assessment (section 4.3). All methods, tools, frameworks and approaches for

Table 4.11 Examples of existing capacity strengthening initiatives for advancing a nexus approach.

Case study	Nexus elements	Capacities strengthened	Description of intervention	Targeted actors	References
Transboundary basins: assessment of the water-food-energy-ecosystems nexus		Institutional capacities in transboundary and intersectoral issues	Monitoring capacities have improved (e.g., water quality monitoring), while others remain basic, for example, biodiversity monitoring	Actors from agricultural sector; water monitoring	United Nations Economic Commission For Europe (UNECE) (2015)
Development and testing of water-energy-food-ecosystem models and other tools in five sub-regions of Africa and Asia		Capacities for WEF governance and for planning and implementing nexus investments	Producing guidelines on multi stakeholder platforms facilitating local development; training practitioners to use groundwater governance tools; developing and implementing a practical near real-time scheme to monitor and respond to groundwater depletion as a critical threat to food security; co-developing and co-implementing WEF nexus training resources and programmes	Practitioners, farmers, women leaders, NGO leaders, local and regional communities' leaders	CGIAR Initiative on NEXUS Gains (2024)
Indicators as tools to deal with compartmentalized resources on planning and management cities		Analytical capacities by developing indicators through a sequence of interactive activities, such as workshops, meetings, and field trips	Co-creating sustainability indicators related to the WEF nexus in the city of São Paulo, Brazil. Through a transdisciplinary approach, non-academic actors were included in the different stages of the process using the Urban Living Lab methodology	Peri-urban and rural communities	Moreira et al. (2022)
The Nexus Observatory: a flagship initiative of the United Nations University Institute for Integrated Management of Material Fluxes and of Resources (UNU-FLORES)		Networking capacities by strengthening the links between scientific and policy dimensions	The programme aims to prepare participants to apply a more holistic perspective to the management of limited environmental resources, decision-making and planning, as well as in relation to financial matters	Development of nexus competences of decision makers, practitioners and researchers interested in the planning and management of environmental resources	Meyer (2017)
The Satoyama Development Mechanism (SDM)		Capacities to (i) create innovations and best practices; (ii) integrate governance and knowledge, particularly ILK; and/or (iii) mobilize people, partnerships and resources	The SDM identified five priority areas: (i) knowledge co-production, management and uptake; (ii) institutional frameworks and capacity development; (iii) area-based conservation measures; (iv) ecosystem restoration; and (v) sustainable value chain development. The SDM focuses specifically on supporting the development of other effective area-based conservation measures (OECMs); landscape or seascape restoration; conservation and collaboration with IPLC; resilience enhancement; and sustainable food or material production.	Members of the International Partnership for the Satoyama Initiative (IPSI) including local governments, farmers, practitioners, NGOs, and researchers	Satoyama Initiative (IPSI Secretariat, 2023)
Biodiversity-based transdisciplinary SDG-Labs		Capacity to: (i) find solutions for sustainability problems through leveraging local biodiversity; (ii) address multiple SDGs beyond SDG14 or SDG15; (iii) implement a transdisciplinary approach; and (iv) trigger positive change at the local scale (and with the potential to be scaled up).	The implementation process of the SDG-Labs sought to enable vertical and horizontal information exchange with international researchers in the form of coaching and presentations at international conferences and between groups. Each SDG-Lab group worked with one coach from the funding research organizations, including Future Earth. The role of the coach was to provide advice related to the design and implementation of the SDG-Lab, with all coaches being knowledgeable on aspects related to sustainability science, biodiversity/ ecosystem services and social-ecological systems.	Local communities, private sector, local government, NGOs, academia	Jarzebski et al. (2023)

improving understanding of the nexus are underpinned by a cognitive representation of the world and thus can privilege specific world views, values and perspectives (Ghodsvail *et al.*, 2022; Knapp *et al.*, 2019; Muller *et al.*, 2019). Strengthening analytical capacities also requires a deeper appreciation of multiple and diverse values in decision-making and a recognition of plural knowledge systems, connected to the capacity to bridge multiple ways of knowing and doing (e.g., scientific, Indigenous, experiential and practical) (Berkes *et al.*, 2000; Hill *et al.*, 2020; Muir *et al.*, 2023; Tengö *et al.*, 2017).

Bridging capacities for nexus governance include the ability to bring together different ways of knowing and doing through knowledge co-production processes that can facilitate legitimate, credible and salient knowledge (Cash & Belloy, 2020; Lotz-Sisitka *et al.*, 2016; Wahl *et al.*, 2021). Transdisciplinary approaches, especially those that pay careful attention to how power mediates decision-making processes, show potential for supporting this bridging work, especially those that are embedded in reflection and learning processes and facilitated by knowledge brokers and intermediary organizations (Bielak *et al.*, 2008; Chilisa, 2017; Lotz-Sisitka *et al.*, 2016; Scodanibbio *et al.*, 2023; Stein *et al.*, 2018; Turnhout *et al.*, 2013; Wiegleb & Bruns, 2018).

Negotiation capacities are important for surfacing and navigating inevitable trade-offs between values and interests of different actors and institutions engaged in

nexus governance (Artioli *et al.*, 2017; Lester *et al.*, 2013; Turkelboom *et al.*, 2018; Weitz *et al.*, 2017). Mobilizing and strengthening capacities to negotiate conflicts stemming from power asymmetries or arising from trade-offs can support decision-making processes that are more just and equitable (Boas *et al.*, 2016; Middleton *et al.*, 2015; Salmoral *et al.*, 2019). Negotiation capacities are especially important for navigating contestations arising from tele- and meta-coupled interactions where impacts on nexus elements can be driven by decisions made far from where the impacts are felt (Boillat *et al.*, 2022; B. Liu *et al.*, 2018; L. Liu *et al.*, 2023; Q. Liu, 2016; Munroe *et al.*, 2019; Nyam *et al.*, 2022; Zhang *et al.*, 2019).

Social networking capacities facilitate co-learning opportunities that can foster more adaptive governance and collaborative implementation of policies and response options (Armitage *et al.*, 2011; Bodin & Crona, 2009; M. S. Reed *et al.*, 2018; Urbinatti *et al.*, 2020). Nexus governance that can leverage existing networks of actors and institutions from across sectors and scales can use multiple social mechanisms (e.g., collective action or social movements (Bjork-James *et al.*, 2022; Martínez-Torres & Rosset, 2010; Tormos-Aponte & García-López, 2018)) to facilitate change and reduce negative impacts on nexus elements (Bodin *et al.*, 2020; Guerrero *et al.*, 2020). Social networking capacities can cultivate more relational approaches within nexus governance (Koulouri & Mouraviev, 2019; Stein *et al.*, 2018) whereby key relationships between nexus elements

can be understood and either amplified or dampened to reduce negative consequences for people and ecosystems.

Motivational capacities ensure that actors and institutions, connecting through arenas of engagement (section 4.2.5), have awareness of, and desire to, consider interlinkages across the nexus in their decision-making processes, and prioritize and mobilize the requisite resources (including financial and other enabling conditions – see Table 4.6) to

support these activities (Emerson *et al.*, 2012; J. L. Jones & White, 2022; Weitz *et al.*, 2017). Motivational capacities are embedded in sociopolitical, cultural and economic contexts (Meyer, 2017) and can have intrinsic sources which can stem from world views and sociocultural relations (e.g., Indigenous knowledge systems that view systems as inherently interconnected (Hill *et al.*, 2020)) and/or extrinsic sources which can be established by formal rules and policies (Kelemen *et al.*, 2022; Ryan & Deci, 2000).

Table 4.12 Summary of capacities required for each of the five components for nexus governance with illustrative examples.

Key component for nexus governance (see relevant chapter sections)	Type of capacities needed	Examples
Integrative, holistic and transdisciplinary framing of problems and solutions (sections 4.2.2, 4.2.3, 4.3.3)	Analytical	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Capacity to systematically identify direct and indirect drivers of nexus challenges through qualitative and quantitative analysis methods (workshop, interviews, focus group discussion, questionnaire survey, modelling, etc) (Hoolohan <i>et al.</i>, 2018; Tye <i>et al.</i>, 2022; Weitz <i>et al.</i>, 2017; Yuan & Lo, 2022) Capacity to address multiple nexus challenges with broader scope and system boundaries beyond the boundary of specific nexus element (Yuan & Lo, 2022) Capacity to monitor nexus elements and their interactions, with appropriate tools and technologies (Namany <i>et al.</i>, 2019)
	Bridging	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Capacity to bridge different disciplines, frameworks, approaches, sectors, actors and knowledge systems
	Negotiation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Capacity to evaluate options and make informed decisions based on heterogeneous information through multi-criteria analysis, ensuring comprehensive assessment of diverse factors (Hirwa <i>et al.</i>, 2021)
	Motivational	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Capacity to embrace different world views and representation about the nexus (Wiegleb & Bruns, 2018)
Inclusive approaches that bring about enhanced arenas of actor engagement (sections 4.2.3, 4.2.5, 4.3.6, 4.4.2, 4.5.1, 4.5.2, 4.5.3)	Bridging	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Capacity to engage and ensure the participation of IPLC in decision-making processes, considering their knowledge and needs (Radovich, 2023) Capacity to mobilize, negotiate, translate and synthesize knowledge (Tengö <i>et al.</i>, 2017)
	Motivational	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Capacity to engage in transdisciplinary work to generate new knowledge and address problem-oriented challenges effectively (Vallet <i>et al.</i>, 2023)
Normative considerations of equity and justice, alongside accountability (sections 4.2.5, 4.3.6, 4.4.2, 4.5.3)	Bridging	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Capacity to acknowledge and address different dimensions of equity based on diverse knowledge and values (Pascual <i>et al.</i>, 2023) Capacity to navigate different values and trade-offs, across space and time (L. Liu <i>et al.</i>, 2023) Capacity to negotiate conflicts due to power asymmetries arising from trade-offs between nexus elements and to support decision-making processes that are just and equitable (Boas <i>et al.</i>, 2016; Middleton <i>et al.</i>, 2015; Salmoral <i>et al.</i>, 2019)
	Negotiation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Capacity to develop new approaches to participation, including skills in facilitating participatory decision-making processes that ensure all voices are heard and considered (Castro-Arce & Vanclay, 2020) Capacity to develop conflict management skills and structures, and provide mediation training to facilitate the emergence of negotiated and consensual solutions (Emerson <i>et al.</i>, 2009) Capacity to ensure fair distribution of financial and technical resources, as well as benefits derived from nexus elements and their interactions (e.g., in the respect of Nagoya protocol) (Morgera, 2016; Morgera & Tsioumani, 2010)
Enhanced mechanisms and processes for collaboration and coordination across scales and sectors (sections 4.2.2, 4.2.6, 4.3.2, 4.3.3, 4.3.4, 4.4.1, 4.5.1)	Analytical	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Capacity to measure trade-offs and synergies across nexus elements, sectors, spatial and temporal scales, and multi-levels of governance (Mahanty <i>et al.</i>, 2013; Schroeder & McDermott, 2014) Capacity to navigate across scales, including spillovers and distant effects of nexus policies implemented in one place (J. Liu, Dou, <i>et al.</i>, 2018) Capacity to explore effective policy and sociopolitical options for maximizing the ecological, social and economic benefits (e.g., through an urban living lab approach) (Yuan & Lo, 2022)

Table 4 12

Key component for nexus governance (see relevant chapter sections)	Type of capacities needed	Examples
Adaptive, reflexive and experimental approaches to learn from what works and to scale these solutions (sections 4.2.2, 4.2.3, 4.2.5, 4.3.7, 4.4.1, 4.4.2, 4.5.3)	Analytical	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Capacity to make informed decisions in uncertain contexts by incorporating adaptive management strategies, scenario planning and robust risk assessment frameworks (Marchau <i>et al.</i>, 2019)
	Bridging	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Capacity to raise awareness about the importance of the biodiversity-climate-water-food-health nexus of the general public Capacity to develop educational programmes to educate future generations about nexus challenges and governance
	Social network	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Capacity to adapt and learn together (M. S. Reed, 2014) Capacity to adjust policies and practices based on new information and changing conditions, also called “adaptive capacity of resource governance regimes as multi-level learning processes” (Pahl-Wostl, 2009)
	Motivational	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Capacity to access to funding for research addressing nexus challenges, for the design and implementation of sustainable and equitable practices, and for capacity-building initiatives.

4.6 TOOLS SUPPORTING NEXUS GOVERNANCE

4.6.1 Rationale and aim

For those seeking to address nexus challenges and facilitate nexus governance, tools for integrating cross-cutting issues may help enable exploration and testing of nexus approaches and highlight areas for potential improvement. These tools are methods and techniques based on science and other systems, including ILK, that can inform, assist and enhance relevant decisions, policymaking, and implementation at the local, national, regional and international levels (IPBES, 2021). In this section, tools are considered that are specifically relevant to policy and sociopolitical options for positive nexus outcomes. These tools support iterative approaches to allow for learning, change and adjustment.

A systematic literature review of decision-support tools was undertaken covering resources in multiple languages, including peer-reviewed publications, grey literature and ILK resources (see data management report for detailed methods¹⁰). The review identified 179 resources detailing 203 unique tools, 22 of which included ILK (see https://rconnect.usgs.gov/ipbes_beta_viewer/ for full dataset). These tools were categorized into the seven IPBES policy tools families: (i) public discussion, involvement and participatory processes; (ii) training and capacity building; (iii) social learning, innovation and adaptive governance; (iv) assembling data and knowledge (including monitoring); (v) assessment and evaluation; (vi) selection and design of policy instruments; and (vii) implementation, outreach and enforcement (IPBES, 2021).

For each tool, information was gathered and analysed on the nexus interlinkages covered, holistic potential (based on a count of SDGs the tool supports), transformative potential (based on count of transformative capacities examined), dimensions of inclusivity (based on count of inclusivity measures examined, i.e., does it include ILK?, is it participatory?, is it multilingual?, does it address gender issues?), technical capacity needs (including operationalizing costs) and key actors needed in implementation. The aim of the analysis was to determine general trends within each tool family and it is recognized that this is not a fully comprehensive approach to evaluating holistic potential, transformative potential or inclusivity. It is also noted that the synthesized materials are biased towards academic research published in English (e.g., only 22% of the tools are from grey literature and ILK sources, and only 7% of them are in languages other than English). With a majority of the world’s local actors not speaking English, multilingual global-with-local networks such as those operated by IUCN (now in 43 languages) may provide suitable forums to exchange local knowledge for decision support.¹¹

This section examines these seven families of tools and determines how they can inform the context, policy design (e.g., gender policies) and implementation of sociopolitical options and contribute to facilitating nexus governance. The seven tool families are discussed in three thematic groupings:

Context (relevant to sections 4.2 and 4.5)

1) Public discussion, involvement, and participatory process

11. For example, Naturalliance.eu and Naturalliance.org are networks developed in response to findings that less than 5% of socio-ecological models in two EU projects were suitable for local use in languages other than English, and that sustainability of biodiversity and nature’s contributions to people benefitted most from knowledge leadership and adaptive management (Kenward *et al.*, 2011; Papathanasiou *et al.*, 2013)

10. The data management report for the review and assessment of decision-support tools is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10119750>.

Table 4.13 Summary of the systematic review of tools.

Tools are summarized by IPBES tool families. Indicators by which the tools were assessed include nexus elements, holistic potential, transformative potential, dimensions of inclusivity, technical capacity needs, and key actors in implementation.

TOOL FAMILY	Nexus elements 	Highest possible score				KEY ACTORS IN IMPLEMENTATION						
		Holistic potential	Transformative potential	Dimensions of inclusivity	Technical capacity needs	Intergovernmental organizations	(Sub-)national governments	NGOs and donors	Private sector	Researchers	Local communities	
		17	5	4	%							
TOOLS THAT ADDRESS CONTEXT	Public discussion, involvement and participatory process [n = 41]											
	Training and capacity building [n = 22]											
	Social learning, innovation and adaptive governance [n = 12]											
	Assembling data and knowledge (including monitoring) [n = 78]											
TOOLS THAT ADDRESS RESPONSE OPTIONS	Assessment and evaluation [n = 149]											
	Selection and design of policy instruments [n = 20]											
TOOLS THAT ADDRESS SCALING	Implementation, outreach and enforcement [n = 6]											

- 2) Training and capacity building
- 3) Social learning, innovation and adaptive governance

Policy and sociopolitical options (relevant to **section 4.3**)

- 4) Assembling data and knowledge (including monitoring)
- 5) Assessment and evaluation
- 6) Selection and design of policy instruments

Scaling (relevant to **section 4.4**)

- 7) Implementation, outreach and enforcement

Findings from the review are synthesized in **Table 4.13** and in online **Supplementary material 4.2, Table SM.4.2**.

A total of 180 resources met the criteria to be included in the review and 203 unique tools were identified. The number of tools included in each tool family are listed in brackets (note that some tools are represented in multiple tool families, so these do not sum to the total number of tools in the review). See **Supplementary material 4.2, Table SM.4.2** for quantitative calculations and the associated data management report for further information on the methods used to conduct the review and calculate the metrics.

4.6.2 Tools to address context

Three tool families primarily address setting nexus-relevant objectives and targets: (i) public discussion, investment and participatory process; (ii) training and capacity building; and

(iii) social learning, innovation and adaptive governance. Collectively, these three tool families help address the nexus challenges related to values, governance and financing by bolstering enablers and eroding barriers to nexus-relevant solutions. These tools have strong coverage of the nexus element of food, high holistic potential, moderate transformative potential, high inclusivity and a diverse set of key actors involved in implementation, including national and subnational governments, NGOs and the private sector (**Table 4.13**). Over 20% of the tools in this family include ILK.

4.6.2.1 Public discussion, investment and participatory process

Public discussion, investment and participatory process tools (41 examined in the review, 20% of total in review) aim to assist with the identification of problems and opportunities, the setting of goals and priorities, the establishment of a case for policy action, and the building of a shared understanding of requirements and consequences among (key) partners and audiences. These participatory tools often have a goal of integrating ways of knowing to convey issues across the nexus to develop a shared foundation to developing solutions. They may also facilitate the achievement of principles such as equality, equity, non-discrimination and effective co-production. These tools are particularly relevant for the policy formulation phase of the policy cycle.

This tool set pertains to various stakeholder engagement, consultation and co-production processes. Examples include participatory mapping, stakeholder-engaged ecological risk

Box 4.16 Example of a public discussion, investment and participatory process tool: The SHARE concept.

An example of this tool family can be found in the SHARE concept developed by multiple organizations related to water reservoirs (mostly for hydroelectric production and water storage). These reservoirs can provide multiple nature's contributions to people beyond electricity generation, such as water supply, flood and drought management, irrigation, navigation, fisheries, recreational activities and economic growth. These nature's contributions to people can conflict at times but are also often complementary; this creates a major challenge for sharing water among competing users of these multipurpose reservoirs. In 2012, Electricité de France (EDF) and the World Water Council (WWC) agreed to work on "the multipurpose water uses of hydropower reservoirs." In 2013, several other organisations and institutions also supported this framework and they all established an international multi-disciplinary Steering Committee to guide the shared vision. In 2015, the SHARE concept was released and communicated worldwide as a solution to the challenges of multi-purpose reservoir management.

Based on 12 case studies from around the world, the framework provides tools to avoid or minimize competition among water uses, tensions between water users and set an appropriate governance framework to coordinate the management of multiple water uses, including strategy, planning, decision-making and operation using economic models. It does this by targeting a sustainable approach for all users, higher efficiency and equity among sectors, adaptability, river basin perspectives and engagement of all users. In this way, the SHARE concept aims to create a shared vision involving resources, responsibilities, rights and risks, and costs and benefits for multipurpose water uses of hydropower reservoirs. This participative approach involves partners from multiple sectors, including governments, banks, NGOs, international organizations and hydropower utilities. This public discussion, involvement and participatory process tool requires a low technical capacity to be implemented.

assessment and co-production. The most prominent nexus elements included in this set of tools identified in the review were food and water, while health is the least represented. The holistic potential of this set of tools is high, while transformative potential and dimensions of inclusivity are moderate (19.5% of tools include ILK). Costs and technical capacity for implementing these tools are often unclear. Governments, NGOs and the private sector can often be instrumental but, perhaps surprisingly, local communities were not often identified as key actors in implementation. An example of this type of tool is given in **Box 4.16**.

4.6.2.2 Training and capacity building

The training and capacity building set of tools (22 examined in the review, 11% of total in review) aims to both identify and address gaps in capacity by providing training and enhancing skills among relevant actors, which include government officials, agencies, communities' representatives, businesses, non-governmental organizations and other stakeholders (IPBES, 2021). This decision support tool type is cross-cutting and included representation of all nexus elements, however, the most prominent was food, with climate change, water and biodiversity having weaker links and health being largely absent. Training and capacity building tools engage with the nexus from a variety of different entry points and include the indicator-based assessment tool *pro.eraa* (Yawar-Mehmood *et al.*, 2020), the Fish in Wetlands Decision Support Tool (Gawne *et al.*, 2012) and the Cape Horn Long-Term Socio-Ecological Research Network (Rozzi *et al.*, 2020). This family of tools was associated with high levels of holistic potential and moderate levels of transformative potential and inclusivity. Costs and requirements for technical capacity to implement are often unclear. Key actors in implementation include governments and the private sector. An example of this type of tool is given in **Box 4.17**.

4.6.2.3 Social learning, innovation, and adaptive governance

Social learning, innovation and adaptive governance is a set of tools (12 examined in the review, 6% of total in review) that considers people's capacities to learn from each other through observation, which facilitates the spread of innovations. Social learning is fundamental to implementing adaptive governance processes, designed to be flexible so that learning can be incorporated in decision-making, and these processes often involve a range of actors at multiple levels (Schultz *et al.*, 2015). Among all the tool families, this set is among those with the most equitable coverage of nexus elements; biodiversity is the most prominent but is closely followed by climate change, water and food with health to a lesser extent (**Table 4.13**). Tools belonging to this family include a conceptual framework for sustainable water-energy-food nexus management (Akinsete *et al.*, 2022), a multidisciplinary, model-assisted, climate change adaptation plan (C. Gonçalves *et al.*, 2022), QUICKScan (Verweij *et al.*, 2016), the adaptive capacity wheel (Gupta *et al.*, 2010), and REDPARQUES (REDPARQUES, 2020). These particular tools are not exclusive to this family but are also included as examples of other tool families as well.

The holistic potential of this family is the highest of all tools, identified as collectively contributing to almost all the SDGs, and it has amongst the highest representation of ILK (33% of tools include ILK). Their transformative potential and additional dimensions of inclusivity, however, are moderate. These tools can be implemented at multiple spatial scales, from subnational to the global level. However, implementing these tools seems to require high costs or technical capacity, with key actors being governments, followed by the private sector, researchers and intergovernmental

Box 4.17 Example of a training and capacity building tool: World Overview of Conservation Approaches and Technologies.

Land degradation is among the top environmental challenges globally and closely linked to the nexus elements, particularly biodiversity and water. Governance responses to this challenge involve a wide range of actors at all levels. Knowledge on sustainable land management practices is needed to tackle land degradation. The World Overview of Conservation Approaches and Technologies decision-support tool (WOCAT; <https://www.wocat.net/en/about-wocat/>) – is a global networking aiming at documenting, sharing, and applying sustainable land management knowledge to support evidence-based decision-making (*The World Overview of Conservation Approaches and Technologies*, 2020). The network provides training, support and capacity building on sustainable land management to over 400 users in the interest

of improving land resources, ecosystems and livelihoods. WOCAT, together with network partners, has developed a well-accepted framework and standardized tools and methods for documentation, monitoring, evaluation and dissemination of sustainable land management knowledge, covering all steps of data collection with several questionnaires for administering a global sustainable land management database and using the information for decision support. The database consists of 2,389 practices published from 136 countries (as of 19 February 2024) and is recommended by the United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification. WOCAT is an exemplary example of a nexus training and capacity building tool given its high transformative and holistic potential, with important links to several of the SDGs.

organizations, and, to a lesser extent, NGOs and local communities. An example of this type of tool is given in **Box 4.18**.

4.6.3 Tools to address policy and sociopolitical options

Three tool families predominantly address response option choices: (i) assembling data and knowledge; (ii) assessment and evaluation; and (iii) selection and design of policy instruments. These three tool families relate to nexus challenges of values and scaling by helping synthesize available information and evaluate options to select and scale appropriate policy solutions. These tools collectively have strong inclusion of the nexus element of water, moderate holistic potential, low transformative potential and low inclusivity. Their technical capacity needs are relatively modest and governments as well as the private sector, and to a lesser extent intergovernmental organizations and researchers, are often key actors in implementation (**Table 4.13**). Less than 10% of these tools include ILK.

4.6.3.1 Assembling data and knowledge

Assembling data and knowledge tools (77 examined in the review, 38% of total in review) address knowledge gaps by collating data related to biodiversity function, socioecological dynamics and nature's contributions to people. These tools synthesize, integrate or assess data or indicators

from mapping databases, long-term ecological monitoring and other data collection efforts. Identifying indicators for monitoring and assessing the nexus can be critical challenges. The most prominent nexus element covered by these tools was water, with climate change, biodiversity and food also common but health poorly represented. Tools within this family include assessment of ecosystem services, valuation of ecosystem services and trade-offs, integration of multiple knowledge sources, and decision-support tools for conservation, restoration or management. Specific examples include the Aquatic Species Invasiveness Screening Kit (AS-ISK; Copp *et al.*, 2016), a coastal restoration prioritization tool (Davis *et al.*, 2019) and an indicator framework for hydrologic alteration (Theiling & Nestler, 2010).

The holistic, transformative and inclusivity potential of this family are among the lowest in the review (**Table 4.13**). For example, most tools address only two or three SDGs. The transformative potential for this family includes addressing the status quo and integrative and adaptive capacities. Most tools showed few dimensions of inclusivity (e.g., only 10% include ILK). Many tools in this family offer instrumental or intrinsic value for addressing habitat and regulatory nature's contributions to people. Most tools in this family currently exist as a pilot or case study only, thus offering an opportunity for improvement in full implementation and spatial scaling. Limitations include high costs and high technical capacity for tool development and maintenance. An example of this type of tool is given in **Box 4.19**.

Box 4.18 Example of a social learning, innovation and adaptive governance tool: QUICKScan.

The management of wetlands in the Chinese Yellow River delta faces threats such as urbanization, pollution and decreased sediment loads due to river regulation. This has led to salinization and a significant reduction in wetland areas, endangering habitats for rare bird species. The challenge is to develop a more balanced water allocation strategy to support the sustainable development of wetland nature reserves amidst changing land use and flooding patterns. The key partner in the management of the water resources of the Yellow River Basin is the Yellow River Conservancy Commission. Hydrological and ecological experts from the University of Nanjing and the Chinese Academy of Sciences provide expertise on water management and ecological conservation, along with consultants who offer external expertise and support in scenario planning and strategy development. Finally, local partners, including the Nature Reserve Authority and urban planning representatives from Dongying municipality, also represent the interests of agriculture and aquaculture farmers within their respective territories.

QUICKScan was used as a decision-support tool that engages stakeholders in decision-making by merging their

insights with spatial and statistical data. Institutional capacity was a key enabler of this initiative. The tool is used in workshops to iteratively refine models based on stakeholders' input. At the start of each workshop, parameters were set for scenarios and spatial strategies, which were then fed into the models. The resulting maps showing groundwater levels and flood durations were examined and deliberated upon. Moreover, stakeholders collaborated to create a semi-quantitative ecological model, focusing on specific indicators and tracing the cause-and-effect relationships from habitat suitability to inputs derived from the water models. This ecological model underwent multiple refinements through daily sessions, where it was adjusted, executed and analysed for results. These workshops enhanced participants' understanding of potential water allocation approaches. Consequently, a portion of the wetland nature reserve was designated as a Ramsar site based on the study's outcomes (Verweij *et al.*, 2016). A key success for this tool is its development involving user input and agile software to ensure that real-world applications provide feedback and drive ongoing improvement.

Box 4 19 Example of an assembling knowledge and data tool: SocMon.

In the 1980s, top-down creation of protected areas with a predominant focus on biodiversity rather than nexus elements or inclusion of social concerns hindered nexus governance and marginalized vulnerable communities dependent upon those areas for food, livelihoods and well-being. A restrictive Marine Protected Area in locations traditionally used by local small-scale fishers in Paraty, Brazil, illustrates a key nexus challenge between biodiversity conservation and local livelihoods, including the food and health nexus elements. Extensive knowledge gaps in socioeconomic and cultural aspects related to coastal and marine biodiversity and nature's contributions to people meant that traditional knowledge holders, fishers and other users of local resources were marginalized from decisions.

SocMon was an assembling data and knowledge tool that addressed these knowledge gaps using a participatory process

with four main steps: preparatory activities, planning and recognition, field data collection and data analysis (Bunce *et al.*, 2000). The key actors collectively agreed to four monitoring objectives with respective indicators, as well as monitoring procedures. The established objectives aim to foster the sustainability of local fishing, emphasize the importance of fishing for the community, strengthen relations between fishers and protected area managers, and strengthen self-organization of fishers. To stimulate the sustainability of fisheries and the conservation of fish stocks, participants suggested that capacity-building courses could be offered to the community (Dias & Seixas, 2019). Institutional capacity leveraging partnerships with local fishers and researchers was a key enabler of this initiative. Financial investments, as for many tools in this category, are barriers for long-term monitoring, which is also subject to changes in the political system and social network of the protected area.

4.6.3.2 Assessment and evaluation

Assessment and evaluation tools are a large set of policy support tools (149 examined in the review, 74% of total) that aim to synthesise and assess knowledge, including ILK. They include a variety of methods and diverse conceptualizations of values of nature, nature's contributions to people and a good quality of life. The most represented nexus element in this tool family was water, while health was the least represented (with biodiversity, climate change and food in between). This tool family is the most well represented in this review, which reflects the inherent bias to scientific literature and that these tools are more likely to be

featured in scientific research than other tool families. Many of these tools are products of academic research, modelling and mapping exercises, and risk assessment approaches.

These tools scored moderately in terms of holistic potential; however, they scored poorly in relation to transformative potential and even more so in terms of dimensions of inclusivity (the lowest in the review; **Table 4.13**). These tools have the lowest proportion of ILK of any tool family (7%). They often have lower requirements on technical or financial capacity to implement and maintain. An example of this type of tool is given in **Box 4.20**.

Box 4 20 Example of an assessment and evaluation tool: Soil and Water Assessment Tool.

Anthropogenic factors like climate change, urbanization, and land use change are driving increased demands for food and water resources globally. As a result, the world's freshwaters are experiencing substantial impacts from competing demands for agriculture, industry, recreation and human consumption and are now considered some of the most threatened ecosystems globally. Water security and food security are highly interconnected, where food production requires adequate water quality and quantity and freshwater provisioning services can be highly impacted by expansion and intensification of food production ("Water Is Life, Water Is Food," 2023). Thus, integrated water-food-climate nexus approaches are needed to address governance challenges. Key actors involved in evaluating watershed impacts from land use and management practices include national agricultural and environmental agencies, regional and basin water management organizations, community-based organizations and water management

sectors. Assessment and evaluation tools developed for use at multiple scales are especially important when examining watershed impacts, which often occur across political and geographic boundaries and across heterogeneous landscapes.

One of the most widely utilized and well-developed assessment tools used to address the water-food-climate nexus is the Soil and Water Assessment Tool (SWAT; <https://swat.tamu.edu/>). The tool is an integrated ecohydrological model used to simulate water quality and quantity in river basins and predict impacts of land use activities, particularly agricultural management practices (e.g., fertilizers, irrigation, pesticides) on watershed dynamics. Using inputs such as climate, vegetation, soil and water variables, the model can simulate hydrological and agriculture processes, including the water balance and crop yield, to help decision makers identify best management practices based on model outputs (Arnold *et al.*, 1998).

Box 4 20

Examples of the use of SWAT for addressing nexus elements include evaluating impacts of snowmelt across mountainous landscapes that are vulnerable to climate change (Fontaine *et al.*, 2002), simulating pathogens of human health concern

at watershed scales (Sowah *et al.*, 2020), assessing wetland drainage impacts on hydrology (Perez-Valdivia *et al.*, 2017) and examining climate change impacts on ecosystem services in catchments (Uniyal *et al.*, 2023).

4.6.3.3 Selection and design of policy instruments

Selection and design of policy instruments is a set of tools (20 examined in the review, 10% of total in review) designed to aid the identification, evaluation and choice of potential policies and institutional structures. They evaluate and compare different policies, policy mixes and contexts from studies sourced globally. This category primarily focuses on policy selection and design, rather than supporting strategies to sustain and embed policies in decision-making processes once selected. This tool family's most prevalent nexus element is water, followed by climate change, food and biodiversity, with health being the least prevalent. Together, they illustrate which resources are under policy scrutiny.

This tool family pertains to a range of nature's contributions to people but is most typically clustered around clean water and sanitation and climate action. Examples include a conceptual framework to integrate models of social, economic, policy and institutional developments (Akinsete *et al.*, 2022), and a new adaptive decision-making framework for estuary management under climate change (Peirson *et al.*, 2015). The holistic, transformative and inclusivity potential of this family are moderate. Most of these tools address three or four SDGs. The tool family has a diverse transformative potential which most commonly manifests as addressing the status quo, incorporating diverse values and fostering institutional change. Most tools included at least one dimension of inclusivity, with the most common being participatory. Tools in this family possess a wide range of

cost and range from being relatively cheap to considerably expensive. Implementation is typically at a subnational scale, although there are exceptions at a national level. The key actors are typically governments, and the private sector followed, to a lesser extent, by intergovernmental organizations and researchers. An example of this type of tool is given in **Box 4.21**.

4.6.4 Tools to address scaling

One tool family primarily addresses scaling (see **section 4.4**): Implementation, outreach and enforcement. These tools span local to global scales of implementation and have strong inclusion of water, moderate holistic potential, high transformative potential and high inclusivity. They often require high technical capacity or costs to implement and governments as well as researchers and NGOs are often critical actors for implementation (**Table 4.13**). One-third of these tools include ILK.

4.6.4.1 Implementation, outreach and enforcement

Implementation, outreach and enforcement tools (6 examined in the review, 3% of total in review) support practical implementation of policies, including laws, regulations and quasi-regulations, economic instruments and incentives, as well as information tools, including through monitoring, providing information to stakeholders and through supporting enforcement and compliance activities. These tools aim

Box 4 21 **Example of a selection and design of policy instruments tool: Agent-based sustainability model.**

Public support for conservation policy can be affected by environmental drivers (such as recent abnormal weather patterns), although this linkage has often been difficult to discern. The Smoky Hill River Watershed is an agricultural watershed in the U.S. Great Plains that has recently experienced a widely varying flow regime as a result of both land use and climate change, and these intense hydrological changes are likely to negatively impact regional fish and other aquatic biodiversity. The local government has an opportunity to enact conservation measures to address these negative impacts by simple majority public voting. Using a tool for selection and design of policy instruments

related to the conservation measures may help streamline the policy creation process by improving the estimation of public support. Granco *et al.* (2019) developed an agent-based model to predict public approval for various conservation actions for the Smoky Hill River Watershed. The model incorporates hydrology, ecology, social-psychology and economics to predict individuals' hypothetical support using a value-belief-norm framework. They concluded that public perception of climatic irregularities, the timing of policy proposals in relation to such events and the individual awareness of conservation consequences all impact approval of potential policy proposals.

to support implementation of pre-decided policy. This tool family's most predominant nexus elements are water and biodiversity, with weak inclusion of climate change.

This tool family pertains to a broad range of nature's contributions to people, usually but not exclusively centred around freshwater quantity, quality and availability. While the holistic potential of this tool family is moderate, it has the most transformative potential and highest dimensions of inclusivity of any family (Table 4.13). Tools in this family require high technical capacity and high costs to implement, generally by governments, NGOs and researchers. While these tools are often more time- and cost-intensive than others, and high cost can be prohibitive, implementation and enforcement are necessary for any decided policy or action to come to fruition. Even though this tool family is the smallest in this review, it is expected that the number of tools in this family will grow in the coming years as emerging tools related to sensors, other big data (e.g., citizen science apps) and application of artificial intelligence for analysing and integrating these data are increasingly reported in the literature. An example of this type of tool is given in Box 4.22.

4.6.5 Integration of decision support tools with global policy frameworks

The Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework presents valuable opportunities to use decision-support tools as a resource to integrate nexus thinking as

implementation is being operationalized. On a fundamental level, Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework Target 21 is explicitly around data and knowledge, aiming to make the best available science accessible to decision makers as well as the public. The tool family on assembling data and knowledge can directly address this need.

Broader opportunities for using decision-support tools lie with supporting governments and other interested parties to align strategies across the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework targets as well as with other multilateral environmental agreements. For example, many of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework targets have direct linkages to the SDGs (Obura, 2023). Many of the tools in this review can strengthen capacities to achieve these aligned targets by helping to: (1) understand ways for reducing threats to biodiversity; (2) meet people's needs through sustainable use and benefit-sharing; and (3) assist with implementation and mainstreaming.

Tools to help understand ways to reduce threats to biodiversity fall predominantly in the category focused on addressing response options; namely, the assembling data and knowledge, assessment and evaluation, and selection and design of policy instruments tool families of this review. Biodiversity was well-represented across these tool families, which comprise the overwhelming majority of the tools in this review (Table 4.13). However, it is important to note that these tools are among the least holistic or transformative, but they often require a technical champion to implement (Table 4.13).

Box 4.22 Example of an implementation, outreach and enforcement tool: The Mi'kmawey Forestry Initiative.

The sustainable forest management system developed in Nova Scotia, Canada, dates to 1994, when the First Nations Forestry Program was initiated and funded by Natural Resources Canada. This programme was active until 2011 and achieved important goals, such as becoming the first Forest Stewardship Council certified property in Nova Scotia and the development of Forest Management Plans for all communities involved. From 2011 to 2013, a new "Economic Forestry Strategy" 2012/2013 was launched and a position paper was written to establish the Mi'kmaq Forestry Initiative, but it needed new funding opportunities to revive the programme. Since 2016, numerous sources have become available and a revised version of the programme was launched, the Mi'kmawey Forestry Initiative (The Confederacy of Mainland Mi'kmaq, 2023). The Mi'kmawey Forestry Advisory Committee was formed by appointing members from each community as representatives. Through this initiative, assessments of community needs were used to develop comprehensive individualized multi-year strategic plans for each community.

The Mi'kmawey Forestry Initiative is a holistic forestry approach applying and promoting the principles of Netukulimk (i.e., taking only what you need and leaving something for future generations) to balance immediate economic needs with forest protection for future generations and the other natural components of the forest ecosystem. In this way, all technical aspects of the forestry sector are covered, including sustainable forestry management, habitat and species at risk stewardship, silviculture, conservation and non-timber forest products. This initiative includes government agencies, private industry and other non-government organizations, which assist with funding, capacity building (workshops, training) and support to the communities through scholarships and grants. This tool integrates the nexus elements of biodiversity, food and health and it is underpinned by intrinsic values. This tool, like many in the implementation, outreach and enforcement category, contributes to the development of motivational and bridging capacities and is applied at sub-national governmental scale.

Tools that help meet people's needs through sustainable use and benefit-sharing have high dimensions of inclusivity. The social learning, innovation and adaptive governance tool family along with the selection and design of policy instruments and implementation, outreach and enforcement families are among the tools with the highest dimensions of inclusivity (**Table 4.13**). These tools can help address gender issues, including ILK, and can be participatory.

Tools that help with implementation and mainstreaming are those with the highest transformative potential (**Table 4.13**). For example, tools that address context and tools that address scaling generally have more transformative potential than those that address response options. Interestingly, though these tools have massive potential for affecting positive change, the diversity of stakeholders involved is quite limited and IPLC are rarely key actors. Therefore, equity and empowerment may not be well addressed by these tools.

Ultimately, these tools can showcase examples of how to support nexus governance. There is substantial and intentional overlap between the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework goals and targets and those in other multilateral environmental agreements. By design, countries can use similar metrics, indicators or approaches to make progress towards achieving goals and targets across multiple agreements as well, and these tools can help ensure that limited resources are well spent.

4.7 KNOWLEDGE GAPS AND EMERGING ISSUES

This section highlights knowledge gaps and emerging issues within policy and sociopolitical options for the governance of the nexus. This includes outstanding questions and research gaps that emerged from the systematic reviews conducted on governance and policy options and decision-support tools as well as additional gaps regarding methodologies and methodological approaches, cross-cutting issues, scaling, ILK and IPLC.

4.7.1 Knowledge gaps in nexus governance

The systematic review of governance and policy options conducted in this chapter revealed a number of critical knowledge gaps that may hinder successful efforts to govern across the nexus. In general, the review showed a limited number of empirical assessments of nexus governance and policy solutions, as most insights were derived from theory or conceptual models rather than empirical research or actual implementation (**section 4.5.4.1**). This scarcity of empirical

literature evaluating or comparing nexus governance/policy options indicates the need for more place-based research focusing on governance arrangements and policy instruments, including their combination into various policy mixes. It is important to note that this gap in the literature may represent a gap in scholarly knowledge, but not necessarily a gap in the place-based governance work being carried out. It is possible, for example, that such initiatives are being undertaken but not being reported in a way that connects with either the academic or grey literature. In this regard, efforts could be undertaken to identify initiatives already underway and integrate them with the existing scientific literature.

At the same time, regarding specific nexus elements, the nexus governance and policy literature predominantly focuses on water and food, especially through the significant body of research that looks at the food-energy-water nexus. There was much less focus on other elements of the nexus including biodiversity, health and climate change. The lack of integration with health is a trend that extends beyond the systematic review of governance options and decision-support tools as it is also seen in other chapters. This lack of engagement with the health sector is the result of both limited conceptual and empirical engagement and represents a gap in current research and literature (Nuwayhid & Mohtar, 2022). The lack of coverage across all five elements in most nexus governance and policy literature remains a major gap.

Additionally, the systematic analysis of governance options also found that nexus financing is generally underrepresented in the governance/policy literature, and the intersection of governance options and nexus financing is a priority for future knowledge generation. More work is also needed to better understand how governance and policy may be leveraged to enable nexus-related research, implementation and engagement across a variety of scales and among a diversity of actors.

Within the systematic review of decision-support tools to guide nexus governance, there are significantly more tools to address specific response options than there were tools to address either the context in which these response options occurred, efforts to scale these response options (i.e., scaling), or interlinkages among nexus elements (**Table 4.13**). This relates to a more general gap within nexus governance, in which larger scales (e.g., international, national, and sub-national) are more commonly represented, while smaller scales (e.g., local communities) are much less represented and interlinkages between nexus elements are still underappreciated (i.e., tools often focused on one (or few) nexus element(s) without specifically analysing linkages between them). In this sense, more research is needed on the effectiveness of different governance approaches and decision-support tools on community governance capacity

and the ability to achieve policy coordination at the local scale. Important too are future efforts to utilize these insights to address critical nexus governance challenges related to both local context and the scaling of response options beyond the local. On the other end of the spatial spectrum, there are also knowledge gaps regarding the transboundary impacts of nexus interactions, which occur at the border of geopolitical entities, especially between nation-states. From the perspective of nexus governance, more work is needed to better understand nexus interactions and successful mechanisms for nexus governance across these spatial transnational boundaries as well as across scale.

Related to the limited engagement with the local scale is a lack of engagement between nexus governance and certain actors. This was most notable regarding media and the arts, on one hand, and ILK and IPLC on the other, which were significantly underrepresented, as were studies that focused on the local scale more generally. Engagement with media and the arts was the least represented of these two and represents an important knowledge gap and perhaps a critical capacity gap as well for many institutions and organizations engaged in this kind of work.

Regarding ILK and IPLC, there are efforts to further engage both within formal institutions. On a global level, IPLC participation is formally incorporated in the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) as the Local Communities Indigenous Peoples Platform (LCIPP). On a regional level, the Arctic Council Indigenous Peoples Secretariat and the Sámi Parliament formally engage Indigenous Peoples in the Arctic, among other forums. Despite these formal institutions created for Indigenous participation, persistent power asymmetries create serious challenges in working with Indigenous, local and scientific knowledge systems (Hill *et al.*, 2020). Engaging with IPLC in decision-making and incorporating ILK into the definition and the development of nexus-informed approaches to governance, such as nature-based solutions (Townsend *et al.*, 2020; Tugendhat, 2021), represents an essential task for future nexus governance work going forward. At present, it represents a critical gap in current research and scholarly knowledge.

Within the literature on decision-support tools for nexus governance, there were also substantially more tools to address ‘assessment, evaluation, data assemblage and monitoring’ while there were significantly fewer tools to address ‘social learning, innovation and adaptive governance’. There were even fewer tools still to support actual ‘implementation, enforcement and outreach’. This reflects a broader knowledge gap also seen in the review of governance/policy options, which showed a lack of empirical and place-based research. In some cases, decision-support tools for empirical assessment and monitoring may exist, but their application to actual nexus

governance and policy options in practice is limited. In this regard, not only is better empirical monitoring and assessment required to inform improvements in the design of nexus governance, policy responses and decision-support tools but so too is the actual application and implementation of alternative and innovative approaches.

Another knowledge gap relates to the understanding of the temporal relationships between various nexus elements and how actions can produce unpredictable outcomes over time. In some instances, this can produce trade-offs or rebounding effects in the long run, with positive impacts on one nexus element and negative impacts for another. At the same time, temporal dynamics are also important to consider as they impact various actors over the lifespan of specific governance approaches even though these dynamics remain poorly understood. For example, long-term governance strategies sometimes fail to consider important actors (i.e., the private sector, health sector, local citizen group, etc), which remains a challenge not only in research but in the actual implementation of governance options, especially those with a strong policy component (Itayi *et al.*, 2021; Shannak *et al.*, 2018). More research is needed on the temporal dynamics as regards both nexus elements and actors in the implementation of nexus governance options, for example through advanced modelling and co-design methodologies which incorporate nexus elements and associated factors.

4.7.2 Emerging and cross-cutting issues

Beyond the specific knowledge gaps from the systematic reviews, there are several additional emerging and cross-cutting issues within the literature on nexus governance that merit discussion. First among these is the growing need for both public and private groups to implement more interdisciplinary and mixed methodologies into nexus-related research as a way of pursuing a more transdisciplinary approach (Albrecht *et al.*, 2018). Related to this is the challenge of incorporating more qualitative methodologies in nexus studies. To date, research on nexus governance has tended to focus on techno-economic and biophysical analyses while the consideration of social sciences methods and data has been more limited (Ramos *et al.*, 2022). This represents both an important gap in current research as well as a cross-cutting issue that defines much of the literature on nexus governance to date.

Along with expanding the methodological scope of nexus research, there is a need to deepen cross-sectoral and cross-scalar approaches of the response options themselves to consider multiple stakeholders in nexus governance. Energy, poverty, equity/justice and economic growth emerged as some of the most salient cross-sectoral

and cross-cutting issues that nexus sociopolitical options might target. Among these, equity/justice is of particular note. From the literature reviewed, equity/justice emerged as one of the most important cross-cutting issues with notable connections to a number of nexus challenges, including governance, complexity, values and scaling. At the same time, however, most of the research on equity/justice focused on the issue through the lens of legal and regulatory mechanisms or economic and financial instruments. Right-based and social/cultural-based approaches remained underexplored in the equity/justice literature representing an important knowledge gap within this critical cross-cutting issue.

Another important cross-cutting issue, which connects to all issues already raised, is that of capacity. On some level, addressing any of these issues is a question of the capacity for relevant actors to do so and can represent either a barrier or an enabler to successful management of the nexus depending on the context. For example, lack of inter-institutional coordination between government agencies may provide a barrier to the development of positive nexus management without appropriate measures to improve the transformative capacities of these institutions. Where these capacities are met, however, inter-institutional coordination can then become an enabler of better management of the nexus. Prioritizing and providing for improvements in all types of capacity across scales can help foster more positive nexus governance.

To address these various cross-cutting issues, a supportive yet diverse array of enablers, policies and other sociopolitical response options can help deliver positive outcomes across the nexus. Additionally, as detailed in **section 4.4**, there is an increasing need to scale both existing and future efforts in multiple ways (e.g., scale out, scale up, scale down and scale deep) to make nexus governance more transformative. Based on existing literature, there appear to be fewer examples of nexus governance/policy options that scale deep; however, it is important to note that such approaches are relatively difficult to measure as it relates to cultural changes.

There is also a critical need for the private sector to drive positive changes towards a more sustainable management of the nexus. The relationship between nexus elements represents an increasingly significant cross-sectoral issue and has an impact on the management of enterprises operating in the private sector (Borowski, 2020). To better understand the role of the private sector in nexus governance, it is important to consider not only *how* the private sector can become a vehicle towards more sustainable nexus management, but also *why* the private sector has not done so already (i.e., what structures, incentives, attitudes and policies currently exist that have resulted in the lack of positive engagement with the nexus to date). To address this, the private sector may consider, on one hand, improved involvement in nexus

governance, and on the other hand, taking more responsibility for the externalities caused by productive activities in the sector (see **Chapter 6**).

4.8 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

Given the tremendous social-ecological challenges society is currently faced with and that impacts are not distributed equally across space and time for either people or nature, identifying and selecting interventions and implementing actions that have the greatest potential for catalysing change towards just and sustainable futures is critical. Faced with a multitude of response options, how can decision makers respond in ways that acknowledge diverse contexts, world views, behaviours, norms, knowledge and values, and account for changes in interconnections among nexus elements through direct and indirect drivers of change at different scales?

This chapter's assessment of existing policy and sociopolitical options across the nexus can facilitate and enable transitions towards more just and sustainable futures across scales, sectors and actor groups. This included assessing the degree to which interlinkages among nexus elements are considered within governance literatures on response options, thus providing an evidence base of options, tools and scaling mechanisms that are discussed in more detail in subsequent chapters. Specific response option design features will depend on the nature of the actors and institutions involved and the scale of implementation. The five components of nexus governance that were considered can help drive stronger engagement by multiple actors and sectors to improve decision-making by helping create a framework for integrative framings of problems, inclusive approaches to engagement, consideration of equity and justice, enhanced coordination, and more adaptive and experimental approaches (**Figure 4.19**). The evidence assessed shows that those options that are co-developed with these components in mind can increase transformative potential to meet nexus challenges, but some actors remain underrepresented in the nexus literature, particularly IPLC.

Through this assessment, the policy and sociopolitical response options, which acknowledge enablers, trade-offs and barriers for these options, and associated decision-support tools and scaling mechanisms that have the greatest potential for facilitating change were defined. Policy design and implementation, as well as institutional capacity are the most common enablers and barriers of nexus challenges; they are important criteria to take into consideration when assessing the potential of different response options. The assessment of different

scaling practices (up, out, down and deep) provides a useful framing for response options to help accelerate their adoption and implementation, amplify their impacts and normalize them as mainstream solutions to nexus challenges (Figure 4.19).

Finally, decision-support tools can assist in advancing nexus governance and response option selection. While most decision-support tools that address nexus challenges were assessed to be holistic, the most common tools focused

on assembling data and knowledge (including monitoring) and assessment and evaluation, which are less likely to be inclusive (e.g., do not address gender dynamics, include ILK or local languages, or use participatory approaches) and have less transformative potential (e.g., do not incorporate diverse values, foster institutional change, or are integrative and adaptive) than other types of tools. This argues for a development of new tools to fill these gaps and the expansion of existing tools to address nexus governance needs.

Figure 4.19 The components of nexus governance discussed in Chapter 4.

The components ensure effective implementation of policy and sociopolitical response options towards a range of sustainable and just futures for current and future generations. Nexus governance requires the mobilisation and strengthening of nexus governance capacities which include enhancing analytical, bridging, negotiation, social networking and motivational capacities (section 4.5.5; Table 4.18). These nexus governance capacities are needed for coordinated action of actors and institutions working in a variety of arenas of engagement to drive change (section 4.5.1; Table 4.7). Enhanced nexus governance requires several components including integrative and holistic framings, inclusive approaches, considerations of equity and accountability and processes for collaboration and coordination that are adaptive, reflexive and experimental (section 4.5.4; Figure 4.17). These components are important for guiding the implementation and scaling of response options to address negative direct drivers and indirect drivers of change and unsustainable and unjust values and behaviour (section 4.4; Figure 4.14).

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